

The de Nuptiis System

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Key to Symbols Used:

- // encloses a phoneme
- [] encloses an allophone or feature

<> encloses a graph
' ' glosses manuscript forms
"" encloses quotes, definitions and foreign words
V any vowel
C any consonant
word boundary
\$ syllable boundary
+ morpheme boundary
= contrasts with
* marks a reconstructed unattested form
** marks an, according to this analysis, wrongly generated form.

() encloses an optional feature or symbol
SD structural description
SC structural change
CF conditioning factor

Phonological Rule:

[SD] → [SC]/[CF]

All de Nuptiis forms are cited by page and line, according to the Firchow printouts. ex:

cínken 'prong' 9,21

Forms taken from other Notker manuscripts are preceded by a Roman numeral, according to how they are listed in the Notker Wortschatz (Sehrt 1955). ex:

lám̄p 'lamb' II,239,9

1.000 Introduction

1.100 Introduction into some of the more well known Graph Patterns

1.111 Notker's de Nuptiis along with all other manuscripts attributed to him, shows a graph alternation that has occupied scholars since before J. Grimm. The lenes stops /b,d,g/ are written <b,d,g> after sonorants. After obstruents they come out <p,t,k>. Sonorant graphs include the vowels <a,e,i,o,u> and the consonantal sonorants <l,r,m,n>. The obstruents comprise the remaining non-sonorant graphs: stops <p,t,k,b,d,g>, fricatives <f,u,s,z,ch,h> and affricates <pf,zz,cch>.

1.112 Stops vary depending on the last letter of a preceding syllable. The stops affected then must be word or at least syllable initial. Perhaps this is why the alternation was christened early on as Notker's "Anlautgestz". An example of it from de Nuptiis is:

nóh tār 'still there' 48,8a (with <t> after an obstruent)

and únde dár 'and there' 17,6 (with <d> after a sonorant)

1.113 The fortition assumed to be operating here after obstruents also takes place in environments where the stop is left alone. That is, in places where the stop is not influenced by a preceding graph, regardless if that graph is an obstruent or a sonorant. According^{to} the Braune Althochdeutsche Grammatik, such places occur:

"am Anfang eines Satzes (oder Satzteils) (1975:103)"

Often these are marked by a scribal high point (°), a punctuation mark thought to have often coincided with such breaks. ex:

cogit futura ° táz tu benéimest 'he knows the future, that you determine' 42,2

ex ore uirginis defluebant ° tár mahtist tu séhen 'they flowed out of the mouth of a virgin. There you can see.' 124,19

1.121 As can be seen by the above quotes, this "Anlautgesetz" only applies to German words. The Alemannic /d/ in the word for 'you' is written with a <t> after an obstruent. ex:

táz tu 'that you' 42,2

However a Latin /d/ in this position remains unaffected. ex:

uirginis defluebant 'of a virgin they flowed' 124,19

1.122 Notker, monk and copyist in the 11th century monastery of Saint Gall, was above all else a teacher. To help his students learn Latin, he translated works from Latin into his native Alemannic. But never completely. de Nuptiis is a mixture, a "Mischprosa" of German and Latin. ex:

íro sune euandro rege den eneas tár fánt 'their son King Evander who Aeneas found there' 140,16

The frame of the above sentence is in German. Apparently, however, Notker believed that some names and concepts would be better expressed in Latin. These are left in Latin, even in the middle of German sentences.

1.123 Although Latin words are not affected by the "Anlautgesetz", they do, just like German words, influence a following German stop. ex:

eneas tár 'Aeneas there' 140,16

rege den 'the king who' 140,16

1.124 Notker never dared to tamper with the Latin spelling system--a system handed down to him from centuries of scribal tradition. But he apparently saw no reason why these foreign words should not also have

an effect on his German system.

1.131 At first glance, the labial and velar stops appear wholly dependent on the graph preceding them. They come out as and <g> after sonorants, and <p> and <k> after obstruents. ex:

únde blúot 'and blood' 24,9

mit plúot 'with blood' 67,22

érda getán 'made the earth' 129,1

úndódig ketán 'made immortal' 50,5

1.132 The only regular exceptions to this would be a few obviously borrowed Latinisms. So, for example, the <p> is retained after a sonorant in:

mit íro púrpurinen gúrtele 'with her purple belt' 12,17

The word for "purple" here, however, descends from Latin. ex:

purpeus 'purple Lat.' 64,18

1.133 The dentals have been analyzed differently. Grimm saw that <t> and <d> alternate in many words, depending on the preceding graph. ex:

noh tár 'still there' 48,8a

únde dár 'and there' 17,6

Nevertheless, that still left a large body of words in which <t> remained <t>, regardless if it was preceded by a sonorant or obstruent. ex:

des tages 'of the day' 74,12

die taga 'the days' 86,10

1.134 Grimm argued that the <t> that does not alternate with <d> reflected Alemannic /t/, from Proto-Germanic */d/. Modern English 'days' compares with German 'Tage' and de Nuptiis:

die taga 'the days' 86,10

1.135 This theory was challenged by A. Hofer in 1873 (Hofer 1873:200). He published a list of examples where Alemannic /t/ was indeed written <d> after sonorants. ex:

síben daga 'seven days' 153,4

Hofer argued for only one dental stop /d/, corresponding to the

single labial and velar ones /b,g/.

1.136 The controversy was not answered until 23 years later by M.H. Jellinek (Jellinek 1896:86). Jellinek pointed out that Alemannic <t> does alternate with <d>, but only when preceded by <n>. ex:

síben dága 'seven days' 153,4

des trítten dáges 'of the third day' 84,22

but, die tága 'the days' 86,10

der tág 'the day' 104,21

1.141 In addition to the alternation between <b,d,g> and <p,t,k> Notker's manuscripts also show another, parallel one between <u> and <f>. <u> appears after sonorants, and <f> after obstruents. ex:

so uílo 'so much' 151,17

uuas fílo 'was much' 23,2

1.142 The alternation is not complete however. <f> also occurs in many cases after sonorants--especially, according to H. Penzl (1964:292), in de Nuptiis. ex:

so fílo 'so much' 159,11

<u> also occasionally varies with <v>. ex:

únde 'and' 113,22

vnde 'and' 100,3a

At least in de Nuptiis, however, the writer cannot find examples of <v> in variation with <f>.

1.151 <k> occasionally alternates with <q> after obstruents, the latter graph only occurring before <u> or <uu>. ex:

des álles kuís 'certain of everything' 107,5a

táz íst quís 'that is certain' 36,21

1.152 After the back vowels <a,o,u>, the graph <c> is in free variation with <k>, although <k> is by far the dominant graph. ex:

uuélih cót 'which god' 41,9

táz kót ist 'that god is' 163,18a

1.153 Without evidence to the contrary, one would treat <c> before front vowels here as the velar stop too. Unfortunately in this position <c> alternates, not with <k>, but with <z>. ex:

fóne éinemo cínken 'from one prong' 91,21

día fier zínkun 'the four prongs' 95,8

And after sonorants, <c> before front vowels does not alternate with lenis <g>, as one would think a velar stop should. Instead, the graph remains written as <c>. ex:

éinemo cínken 'one prong' 91,21

not **éinemo gínken

1.200 Issues Excluded from the Paper

1.211 Eventually the workings of the "Anlautgesetz" in de Nuptiis will be interpreted here with the aid of computer printouts.

1.221 Fairly recent scholarship by Penzl(1972) and W. Moulton(1979) has claimed that /b,d,g/ become fortis after a pause. Unfortunately, pauses as such are not printed in the manuscript. A phonological theory based on them might be more accessible if structured differently. One could examine instead the punctuation marks or syntactic boundaries that are supposed to coincide with these pauses.

1.231 Though possible, a syntactical analysis of the "Anlautgesetz" has not been attempted here. It is difficult to always determine what is, and what is not one of Braune's "Satzteile". Understandably this information is not yet programmed into the computer.

1.232 Without evidence to the contrary, one might hope to see punctuation marks dividing sentence clauses. Unfortunately this is not always so. ex:

dáz chít uuélíche fóne ménniskón uuórten uuárin góta 'whch says which of the words of men were gods' 163,22

dáz chít, uuíolich er under díen ánderen uuáre 'which says which he was among the others' 75,12

1.233 In the first example the relative is separated from the main clause by just a space. ex:

chít uuélíche 'says which' 163,22

In the second, a low point, here notated with a comma, intervenes. ex:

chít, uuíolih 'says which' 75,12

1.241 S. Clausen(1980) used data from I. Weinberg(1911) to divide the Notker canon into stages. He splits de Nuptiis into two parts, based on the frequency of stops written fortis at the beginning of

sentences(1980:369).

11.242 In light of this, one could compare the "Anlautgesetz" in the different subsections of de Nuptiis. Although certainly feasible, this is not attempted here. The de Nuptiis data will be broken down into 3 graphemic and 6 sonorant environments. It is questionable as to whether there are enough forms in the manuscript to even justify this, let alone any further subdivision of the data into a chapter by chapter analysis. The manuscript is treated, justly or unjustly, as a whole.

1.251 And of course any literary, paleographic or historical analyses are also excluded.

1.300 Organization of the Paper

1.311 After a brief introduction into the history of the de Nuptiis manuscript, the first major half of the paper can begin: the analysis of Notker's ~~obstruent~~ system.

1.312 Eventually one would like to account for the statistics of the "Anlautgesetz". To start this analysis however, before establishing at least a phonemic inventory would render any calculations meaningless. So, for example, an analyst might tally the word initial <p>'s in:

ioh púrge 'also castles' 60,11

and in iro púrpurinen gúrtele 'their purple belts' 12,17

1.313 But do they reflect the same phoneme or two different ones? If the same, then both <p>'s could be counted in the same calculations together. If they reflect two different phonemes, then the two <p>'s should be entered into two different statistical columns.

1.314 Before even this can be done however, methods of graphemic analysis must be worked out. How might one differentiate phonologically from graphemically conditioned spellings?

1.315 Above all else, a boundary must be arrived at. Is the "Anlautgesetz" conditioned word, morpheme or syllable initially? How can these boundaries be drawn in a manuscript? In addition, crucial to this analysis should be the concept of sonority; especially relative degrees of sonority and their effect on syllable structure and fortition rules.

1.321 Only after defining methods and boundaries, could one address the issue of how well the sonorant system in de Nuptiis can be described, including two diacritics, a circumflex (^) and accent (/), that mark vowels. After this, an analysis of obstruents could begin, perhaps by first determining the number of stop phonemes. Stops could then be separated into labials, dentals and velars. For each place of articulation, discussion would be preceded by a chart. In it, stop graphs might be contrasted after varying degrees of sonority.

1.322 Spirants could be handled in the next section, partially to see what conclusions from them could be applied to their corresponding stops. So, for example, if one can posit underlying fortition contrast in spirants, is it really possible, given linguistic universals, not to posit it in the stops?

1.323 The end result should be a minimal structure of the manuscript system. That is, the phonological and graphemic components needed to generate the major spellings in de Nuptiis.

1.331 This would conclude the first, and lay the foundation for the second half of the paper; the "Anlautgesetz" in de Nuptiis. In order to more carefully formulate a rule, its structure could be examined. Should the "Anlautgesetz" be a fortition of obstruents, or can it also or rather be shown to be a lenition? Might voice or sonority condition the change? The statistical section of the paper could follow.

1.332 The "Anlautgesetz" was examined across 3 graphemic boundaries. They include:

1) the high point (°), signified by a period followed by a word boundary (.##). ex:

romulo.##ter 'Romulus who' 54,19

2) the low point (°), written as a comma followed by a word boundary (,##). ex:

man chad,##kebieten 'it is said, they offer' 158,14a

3) and the word boundary, a blank space between two meaningful series of graphs (##). ex:

unde##gab 'and gave' 124,14

1.333 An analysis of stops across these boundaries might be more clearly structured if begun with a chart, and continued with discussion and examples to interpret it. The examination could be broken down into two sections:

1) stops after sonorant plus boundary.

2) stops after obstruent plus boundary.

1.334 The questions that might be answered in this section could include:

1) What effect does the nationality of a preceding letter (i.e. whether it is in a German or Latin word) have on a following German stop?

2) Does the "Anlautgesetz" favor either the labials, dentals or velars?

3) How do the three different boundaries affect the workings of the "Anlautgesetz", and to what degree?

4) What role does sonority, especially finer grades of sonority, play in Notker's alternation of stops?

1.335 A summary of the paper should follow, along with a definition of the "Anlautgesetz" in de Nuptiis.

1.400 The Manuscript

1.411 Between 410 and 439 a Carthagian named Martianus Capella composed his de Nuptiis Philologiae et Mercurii. It was a mythological fable, an allegorical marriage between Philology and Mercury.

Martianus intended it to be bound together with his compendium de Septem Liberaribus Artibus Septem Libri. This Latin de Nuptiis was copied and spread throughout the monasteries of Medieval Europe.

1.412 Hartmut, a ninth century abbot of the monastery of Saint Gall, had a copy in his private collection. In 833 he willed it to the monks in Saint Gall. When he died, 63 years later, his wish was carried out.

1.413 Scholars believe this is the manuscript Notker translated from, but one cannot compare the two to find out. Hartmut's Latin manuscript is lost, possibly loaned away at the close of the Middle Ages. A letter dated June 1602 tells how a Saint Gall Martianus manuscript (perhaps de Nuptiis) was borrowed by the philologist Goldast in Geneva. Goldast loaned it to another man who refused to give it back.

1.414 de Nuptiis was popular. Three commentaries were written on it in the ninth century. J. King writes that Martianus Capella served as:

"die Grundlage des Unterrichts im Trivium und Quadrivium das ganze Mittelalter hindurch(1979:8)"

1.415 But de Nuptiis was not an ideal beginner's text. It covered the material, but Greek constructions and obscure phrases made it difficult to read. Perhaps this is why Notker translated it into his Alemannic/Latin "Mischprosa" around 1000 A.D.

1.416 It is unfortunate that we do not have Notker's autograph, the manuscript he himself wrote. Saint Gall does have, however, a fairly early copy from the 11th century. It is bound together in a 15th century codex catalogued as the Codex Sangallensis 872 J. On pages 2-170 of this codex is the de Nuptiis manuscript. It remains in Saint Gall.

2.000 Syllable Boundaries

2.111 Penzl, in his three treatments of the graphs in Notker's writings(1956,68,72), speaks of graphs occurring:

"im Anlaut, Inlaut, Auslaut(Penzl 1968:142)"

While the term "Laut" is not defined, an approximation of its meaning can be gleaned from Penzl's use of it. The lenition of [t] to [d] after [n] in

índúon 'open' I,209,7

and úndróst 'motherlessness' I,13,27

is classified as taking place "im Inlaut(1968:148)".

2.112 "Im Inlaut" then cannot mean:

"morpheme internally".

As Penzl himself points out,

túon 'do' 101,17

and tróst 'comfort' 111,21

also occur as separate forms. in and un are morphemes too. And un, accented in

úndróst 'motherlessness' I,13,27

may very well be marked stressed here. That would exclude the possibility of limiting "im Inlaut" to mean:

"morpheme internally, or at least not between two stressed morphemes".

"Im Inlaut" appears then to denote, at least here:

"within a word"

The term word might be best defined graphemically as:

"a meaningful series of graphs bordered by spaces"

2.113 Arriving at a more phonologically suitable boundary is difficult. This is all the more so because de Nuptiis is a manuscript and not a speech sample. For "Laut" or word, one could substitute morpheme. A morpheme might be defined graphemically as:

"the smallest meaningful unit in a series of graphs"

2.114 The word

úndróst 'motherlessness' I,13,27

would then have two morphemes. The lenition of [t] to [d] after [n] in

úndróst 'motherlessness' I,13,27

would occur across a morpheme boundary. But, as this lenition also takes place "im Anlaut", ex:

mín déil 'my part' 48,1

perhaps one would be capturing an important generalization here. Morpheme boundaries include more than just word ones.

2.115 But they are also not identical with syllable boundaries. While many morphemes are monosyllabic, ex:

ún in úndróst 'motherlessness' I,13,27

some comprise two syllables. ex:

únde 'and' 68,19

A few, like [n], the past participle marker in

gebórn 'bore' 19,19

might even surface as non-syllabic.

2.121 Empirically, one would think that the syllable boundary should be the phonologically significant one. Since de Nuptiis reflects a dead language however, any theory of its syllable boundaries cannot be checked with tapes. Instead, one might turn to a related living language, provisionally adopting its syllabification process to the manuscript system, and then refining it as the analysis progressed. Unfortunately, the writer is not familiar with any treatments of syllable structure for Modern Alemannic. There are, however, some generally available books on the subject for Modern German:

2.122 The two referred to in this paper, Giegrich(1984) and Benware(1986) approach syllables and their boundaries from two different directions. Benware, in a book devoted to German phonology, offers some prose observations on syllables and three guidelines for dividing them in German. Giegrich presents a more comprehensive treatment. He accounts for German syllable structure "metrically"; that is, with tree structures and a syllabification rule.

2.211 Syllables are considered basic to all languages. Like phonemes, speakers claim to be able to count them. Nevertheless, defining them is still difficult. Instead, Benware offers a number of terms and observations, which:

"while not a definition of a syllable, find widespread acknowledgment(1986:81)"

Those referred to in this paper include:

1)the peak or nucleus of a syllable, which is:

"the vowel or syllabic consonant 'responsible for forming the syllable(Benware 1986:81)'."

So, for example, the vowel and syllabic [l] in English 'kennel' [kenəl] are peaks.

2) the onset is:

"the string of consonants to the left of the peak"

while the coda is made up of:

"the consonants to the right of the peak".

An interlude, then, could comprise:

"the string of consonants between peaks".

In the English word 'findings' [faɪndɪŋz] then, the onset of the first syllable would be [f]. The coda of the second is [ŋz], and the interlude between the two syllables should consist of [ɪnd].

3) the optimal syllable structure in any language is CV--consonant plus vowel.

4) The minimum syllable, at least in German, is a vowel or syllabic consonant. Obstruents in German cannot form syllable peaks.

2.311 This last observation raises an issue which is perhaps more fully treated by Giegerich. Syllables, he writes, are "associated with sonority peaks(1984:43)" in strings of phonemes. For him, and in this analysis, the syllable peak or nucleus is:

"the most sonorous segment in the syllable; viewed from left to right, sonority typically increases between the left hand boundary and the nucleus and decreases between the nucleus and the right hand boundary(Giegerich 1984:43)"

The concept of relative degrees of sonority, so crucial to syllable structure, runs through this entire paper. As such it might be best dealt with here.

2.312 Unlike voicing or aspiration, it is difficult to formulate what exact articulatory movements sonority corresponds to. P. Ladefoged defines it phonetically as:

"the loudness of sounds relative to that of other sounds with the same length, stress and pitch(1982:284)"

This may not be as scientific as one would hope. What determines "loudness", decibels? Nevertheless sonority has generally been accepted as a legitimate phonological feature.

2.313 Like all other phonological features, sonority is treated in the standard theory as binary. Vowels, liquids and nasals are [+sonorant]. Stops, fricatives and affricates are [-sonorant]. Unlike voicing or nasalization however, the different "intrinsic degrees of sonority(Giegerich 1984:43)" in phonemes allow one to further subdivide them universally.

2.314 The non-high vowels /a,e,o/ are not only [+sonorant], they are

also more sonorant than the high vowels /i,u/. These are, in turn, more sonorant than the glides /w,j/. The glides are more sonorant than the liquids /l,r/. These are themselves more sonorant than the least sonorant sonorants, the nasals /m,n/. Stressed vowels are more sonorant than unstressed ones. Of the obstruents, fricatives are more sonorant than stops.

2.321 If, as Giegrich maintains, syllables are associated with sonority peaks, English 'kiln' /kiln/ is monosyllabic. Sonority increases from the stop /k/ to the vowel /i/. From /i/ however to the liquid /l/ the sonority level drops. A sonority, or for that matter, syllable peak is left between /k/ and /l/. From /l/ the sonority level drops again a notch to the nasal /n/.

2.322 'kennel' /kenl/ on the other hand, has two syllables. The sonority level peaks between two consonants in the vowel /e/. It rises again after the nasal /n/ to form another peak in the liquid /l/.

2.323 Carrying this analysis into the obstruents, English 'sticks' /stiks/ should be trisyllabic. Since fricatives are more sonorous than stops, the sonority level should peak at /s/, /i/ and /s/. Any native speaker however would recognize this as nonsense. The only syllable peak is in the vowel /i/.

2.324 Apparently the gradations of sonority in obstruents are not relevant to syllabic structure in English. If

stant 'stood' 66.3a

is analyzed as monosyllabic, the same could be said for de Nuptiis.

2.331 Giegrich argues that syllable structure, like stress or tone, is not an inherent feature best dealt with with phonological rules. While /l/ is inherently [+voice] in English, it is not inherently a syllable peak. In English 'play' /plei/, the /l/ gets devoiced after an aspirated obstruent. This binary change in voicing can be written in a rule:

Devoicing:

[+lateral] → [-voice] / [+aspirate]_____

2.332 One could account for syllable peaks in this fashion too. Sonorants could become [+syllabic] when not bordered by a phoneme of a greater degree of sonority:

Syllabification:

2.333 While such a rule generates a syllable peak, it does not take into account strings of sonority levels. These lead up to and drop down from peaks. To better account for these strings, Giegrich uses a "metrical" format. All the phonemes of a syllable are connected to

each other in a branch. The branch relates the different sonority levels of the phonemes to each other. The syllable branches are in turn connected in a tree. The tree relates the different stress levels of the syllables to each other. Sonority is then elegantly analyzed as:

"the intra-syllabic counterpart of stress(Giegrich 1984:2)".

2.341 A syllable branch was assigned by Pike(1947) the universal structure(Giegrich 1984:44):

Onset, nucleus and coda have already been defined by Benware. The rhyme then, is just:

"the sum of the nucleus and coda".

2.342 Kiparsky(1976) built upon Pike's model. He proposed a universal syllable template, able to account for syllables in all languages(Giegrich 1984:44):

2.343 The template is laid onto the string of phonemes in a syllable. The "sonority contour of the syllable(Giegrich 1984:44)" is then reflected in a way that no phonological rule could. In Giegrich's book, the onset, nucleus, rhyme and coda are circled, so that one might then more easily compare Kiparsky's template to Pike's earlier model. The s and w, referred to collectively as nodes, stand for "stronger" and "weaker". "Stronger" means more sonorant, and "weaker", less sonorant. Phonemes can only be compared to each other if one is governed by only s-nodes up to the root of the branch that connects the two phonemes.

2.344 So, for example, in English /snarl/, /r/ and /l/ connect in the coda. Before that, /r/ is only governed by s-nodes. It can then be compared to, and is more sonorant than, /l/. /l/ is governed by a weak node. /a/, the syllable peak, can be compared to, and is more sonorant than, any phoneme. /n/ however, though governed initially by an s-node, cannot be compared to, and is not necessarily more sonorant than, /l/. This is so even though the latter is initially

governed by a weak node. To reach a common root, both phonemes must go through weak nodes--the onset and coda respectively.

2.351 Giegrch points out, however, that the template:

"says nothing about syllable boundaries(1984:45)".

It can be expanded both left and right, leaving, for example, /t/ in German 'gutes' /gutes/ as part of two syllables:

2.352 To avoid this, Giegrich posits a syllabification rule for Modern German:

"The syllable template is expanded maximally to the left and syllables do not overlap(1984:46)."

This, in Giegrich's system, governs where syllable boundaries are drawn. /gutes/ divides syllabically between the /u/ and /t/:

2.411 Instead of accounting for syllables in a system, Benware only gives them a rough, prose definition:

"a vowel with consonants or consonant clusters possibly occurring on either side(1986:79)"

This is later refined to include that:

"Sonorants may also be responsible for creating syllables(1986:84)."

2.412 This treatment of syllable structure is obviously less methodological than Giegrich's. Nevertheless, Benware does propose three guidelines for placing syllable boundaries, two of which conform to Giegrich's analysis:

1) "Onsets are maximized(Benware 1986:85)." /t/ in /gutes/ is analyzed as the onset of the second syllable, not the coda of the first(ex: /gu\$tes/). Giegrich accomplishes this by having the syllable template expand "maximally to the left(1984:46)."

2) "Syllable boundaries coincide with word boundaries (Benware 1986:85)." While not every syllable boundary is a word boundary of course, every word boundary is a syllable one. Likewise, Giegrich's system takes place in the lexicon, not in sentences. It is then "insensitive to any environment beyond the word boundary (1984:51)."

On Benware's third guideline the two men disagree:

3) "Syllable boundaries within the interlude must not result in sequences of phonemes which do not also occur in word initial or word final position (Benware 1986:85)."

2.413 Giegrich does not contradict this explicitly. He does not raise the issue. Nevertheless, when handling the stress patterns of "non-native" words, he does offer a counterexample.

2.421 "While no such distinction has to be made in the phonology of English", the German lexicon, Giegrich argues, draws a dichotomy between "native" and "non-native" words (1984:2). What all helps code a word as "non-native"--nasalized vowels, Latin endings, e.t.c.--is unclear. It is not merely etymology. All "native" words (ex: "Club") are not necessarily Germanic. Not all "non-native" ones (ex: "Ameise") are necessarily borrowings (1984:77).

2.422 For this paper only Giegrich's lexical dichotomy native/non-native, not his analysis of stress is important. Nevertheless it is here, in his discussion of stress, that he contradicts Benware's 3rd guideline. In Giegrich's system "non-native" suffixes:

"receive metrical structure in the lexicon (1984:76)."

"Native" ones do not. "Non-native" suffixes can then get stressed by his stress rule. "Native" ones cannot.

2.423 Roughly, stress in German:

"falls on the final syllable if it is 'heavy' (1984:23)."

The suffix in "Bibliothekar" can then be stressed because it is heavy and in a "non-native" word. Giegrich draws a tree (1984:40):

The second syllable can begin with [lj], an unacceptable word onset in Modern German.

2.431 Apparently Benware's 3rd guideline is not exceptionless. Before

dropping it altogether however, one should perhaps consider two things.

2.441 Giegrich's counterexample comes from a living language. *de Nuptiis* reflects a dead one. In the absence of phonetic evidence for placing syllable boundaries, one is left with graphemic guidelines. If Benware's 3rd guideline is ignored, only a word boundary and sonority levels will check Kiparsky's template from "expanding maximally to the left".

2.442 Gradations in the sonority of obstruents was not judged to be relevant for syllable structure in *de Nuptiis*. /s/, although more sonorant than /t/, does not form a syllable peak in:

stant 'stand' 66,3a.

Given this, Benware's first two guidelines--the ones Giegrich agrees with--will always divide strings of obstruents to "maximize onsets". The word

dahta 'thought' 10,17

would then split syllabically between the <a> and <h>:

**/da\$Xta/ 'thought' 10,17

2.443 While most readers would find this intuitively wrong, there is, outside of Benware's 3rd guideline, only one other way to avoid it. Syllable onsets and codas could be constantly compared to the ones in the modern dialects. Since /daX\$te/ divides between the /X/ and /t/ in Modern Alemannic, perhaps it should also do so in *de Nuptiis*. While this may very well be true, it amounts to little more than reading the text with a thick Swiss accent.

2.444 Diachronic evidence will be cited a lot in this paper. Always, however, an attempt will be made to find manuscript corroboration for it. To do that here, perhaps allowable syllable onsets and codas should be, when possible, restricted to those clusters that also occur at word boundaries. If so, then

dahta 'thought' 10,17

gets divided between the <h> and <t>. /Xt/--marked by <h><t> or <ch><t> in *de Nuptiis*--cannot occur word initially.

2.511 So Benware's 3rd guideline is useful. There may however also be historical reasons for keeping it. Giegrich's counterexample to it, /Bibl[j]othekar/, was brought up in his analysis of "non-native" words. This category, in fact the entire "native"/"non-native" dichotomy, might not necessarily need to be posited in the *de Nuptiis* lexicon.

2.512 Massive borrowing over the centuries built up and eventually codified a "non-native" class in Modern German. Nevertheless, this borrowing was only just beginning in the 11th century. The *de Nuptiis* lexicon is still overwhelmingly Germanic; even more so than in Modern

English, which, according to Giegrich, has no "non-native" class. 2.513 One could try to establish that speakers in Medieval Switzerland had already dichotomized their lexicon according to nativeness. In light of the near absence of "non-native" examples, however, such an analysis would be hard pressed not to collapse on a lack of supporting data. If so, Benware's guidelines for placing the syllable boundary may be strangely more valid for de Nuptiis, than for the language they were originally written for.

3.000 Interpreting Graph Alternations--Methods

3.111 Penzl has spent much of his scholastic career working out a method to interpret manuscript graphs. Perhaps it would be fitting then, if the first third of this section (3.200) listed some of his contributions to the field.

3.112 Unfortunately, however, the scholar published most of his work on Notker before, or shortly after, 1967. As such he was unable to incorporate the Greenberg universals and the generative theory into his methods. As this analysis will be nevertheless rooted in the generative framework, several graph alternations will get accounted for with phonological rules. The second third of this section (3.300) then, might concern itself with guidelines, drawn from textbooks on generative phonology. These could help one write rules as acceptable to the theory as possible.

3.113 The generative school, however, has not yet, at least as far as the writer knows, formally extended its method of analyzing phonological data to also account for graphemic data. Secondly, the question has received little attention--by the generative school or Penzl for that matter--as to which graph alternations can be interpreted phonologically, and which ones might perhaps be more elegantly accounted for graphemically. Some of the writer's suggestions on how to come to grips with both these problems are offered in the third part (3.400, 3.500).

3.211 Diachronic evidence, argues Penzl, should be used, both:

"der Vergleich mit früheren St. Galler Denkmälern" and "die Lautwerte der Gegenwart(1968:135)"

3.212 Unfortunately, unlike Penzl, this writer knows little about Alemannic paleography. He cannot cite with authority earlier Saint Gall texts. Some of the phonemic oppositions in Modern Swiss, however, are available to the layman, being discussed by Penzl and Moulton. With them, for example, one might confirm in de Nuptiis a 3-way labial+dental+velar opposition in place. ex:

[+anterior]
[-coronal] [+coronal] [+back]

<u>b</u> índet	<u>d</u> ín	<u>g</u> ínet
'bind'	'your'	'yells'

I,281,13 I,42,6 I,64,2

3.213 Alemannic obstruents also contrast today, except possibly in the Basel area in Northwest Switzerland (Moulton 1979:248), in continuancy and fortition. In light of the situation in Modern Swiss then, perhaps one should prefer these types of oppositions for de Nuptiis, and not, for example, a voice~~7~~voiceless or aspirate~~7~~non-aspirate one. ex:

[-fortis]	[+fortis]
t [^] odes 'of death' 131,11	t [^] aten 'did' 122,14
[-continuant]	[+continuant]
áber 'but' 149,16	hóue 'court, dat.' 102,3

3.214A phoneme, in the generative theory, gets described as a set of features, not all of which are needed to distinguish it from other phonemes. So, for example, in Modern Swiss /t/ is not only [+fortis], which distinguishes it from lenis /d/, but also, like /d/, [-voice] (Clausing 1980:365). One might of course try something like this for de Nuptiis, assigning values in voice, aspiration and stridency to the obstruent phonemes.

3.215 While more comprehensive, such an analysis would also assume more, more feature specifications than the contrast in phonemes motivates. It will be argued later that one should posit as little as necessary in a manuscript analysis (3.500). In order to do that here then, an analyst might limit descriptions of phonemes to include only those features needed to distinguish them from other phonemes. An exception would have to be made however, when a rule needs to be conditioned by a phoneme's secondary feature. So, for example, /u/ can be distinguished from other phonemes as [+hi, -anterior, -consonantal]. Nevertheless, if the vowel is also described as [+round] it can condition rounding of, for example, /i/ to [y]--a phenomena hinted at by the <u,i> alternation in:

guu^uínnen [guynnən] from underlying /guínnen/ or /guýnnen/ 'to win' I,50,19

guuⁱínnen [guynnən] from underlying /guínnen/ or /guýnnen/ 'to win' I,140,21

3.216 All obstruents are inherently [-sonorant]. In Modern Swiss, however, they are also according to Clausing (1980:365), phonemically voiceless. If one assumes the same for Notker's dialect, then either [voice] or [sonorant] can differentiate sonorants and obstruents. An analyst however who chooses [sonorant] need not make any assumptions

about voicing.

3.217 Nasals could be differentiated from each other by the place features needed for obstruents. One could further separate them as a class with the feature [+nasal]. As the only sonorant stops, however, nasals could also be distinguished as [-continuant, +sonorant]. This would of course complicate rules, forcing an analyst to use ~~two~~ two features instead of one in any rule specifying nasals. At the same time, however, dropping the feature [nasal] could reduce the feature inventory by one. If this can be done, even at the cost of complicating rules, perhaps it should be.

3.218 The liquids /l,r/ might then be separated from the nasals through [continuant], and from each other through [laterl].

3.221 12 different vowel positions might be differentiated with [anterior], a feature already used to describe obstruents, and three new ones: [hi, lo, and round].

	[+ant]		[-ant]	
	[-rnd]	[+rnd]	[-rnd]	[+rnd]
[+hi]	i	y	ɨ	u
[-hi, -lo]	e	ø	ɘ	o
[+lo]	æ	ɛ̃	a	ɔ

3.222 Without evidence to the contrary, one might argue that the same set of vowels could be differentiated by substituting [back] for [anterior].

	[-bk]		[+bk]	
	[-rnd]	[+rnd]	[-rnd]	[+rnd]
[+hi]	i	y	ɨ	u
[-hi, -lo]	e	ø	ɘ	o
[+lo]	æ	ɛ̃	a	ɔ

[back] could also be used instead of [anterior] to distinguish labial, dental and velar obstruents. ex:

	[-coronal]	
	[+back]	[+coronal]
	/k/	/t/
		/p/

3.223 If [back] is used, however, both /a/ and /ə/ get labeled as [+back], a specification one might wish to avoid. In addition, analyzing /ə/ as [-anterior] instead of [+back] allows an analyst to describe schwa, the neutral vowel, in completely negative features: [-anterior, -round, -hi, -lo]

3.224 The manuscript seems to mark vowels according to quantity or quality. ex:

táǵ	tát
'day'	'deed'
I, 45, 22	I, 131, 5

It is difficult to say whether this should be taken as marking tense, length, gemmination or some combination. In order to avoid an, at least with graphemic evidence, unanswerable issue, an analyst might instead just juxtapose single vowels with vowel sequences.

táǵ	tát
[tag]	[taat]
'day'	'deed'
I, 45, 22	I, 131, 5

3.225 Diphthongs might also be similarly analyzed as a sequence of two vowels. ex:

túot [túæt] 'does' I, 9, 26

How all of these vowels and vowel sequences are realized on the surface could be, and therefore in a graphemic analysis perhaps should be, ignored.

3.226 Vowels could conceivably be differentiated from other sonorants as either [+vowel] or [-consonantal]. While [+vowel] only applies to vowels however, [-consonantal] can be used to describe vowels and glides.

3.227 If glides need not be distinguished as separate phonemes, an analyst might hope to ignore them. Listing vowels as [-consonantal] allows this, letting glides be analyzed as an /i/ or /u/ in the same syllable as a stressed vowel. ex:

úoben. with stressed /u/ [úɔbɔn] 'to practice' I, 65, 20

uuólf, with stressed /o/ [uólv] 'wolf' II, 345, 2

3.228 A final feature, [stress], differs from the others discussed so far in that, according to Giegerich, it is not an inherent feature in any phoneme. So, for example, while /u/ is inherently [+consonantal], it is not inherently [+stress]. Not analyzing the feature as phonemically significant, however, might be contradicted by the contrast in 3.227.

3.229 The following list of features then might comprise the minimum needed to distinguish phonemes in de Nuptiis:

[sonorant, consonantal, fortis, continuant, anterior, coronal, lateral, hi, lo, round, stress]

3.231 Penzl also used diachronic evidence to interpret a single graph as marking two different phonemes. So, for example, both

fínf 'five' I, 197, 29

and flégest 'you care' 134, 13

begin with <f>. The former word begins with the fricative /f/ in today's Swiss German, while the latter starts with a stop-fricative combination [pf]. In Proto-Germanic too, the obstruents were different. The word for 'five' began with an */f/, and the verb 'to care', with a */p/. With these things in mind, it seems difficult to maintain that both phonemes collapsed in de Nuptiis, even though they are both written with the same <f> graph.

3.232 To codify into a guideline Penzl's analysis of Notker's initial <f>, one might offer the following. Occasionally one graph in a manuscript marks what is two phonemes in the modern dialects. If this was also so in the proto-language, perhaps one might be justified in positing two phonemes in the manuscript too.

3.233 Grammatical treatises, writes Penzl, and metrical material showing rhymes and assonance should of course also be considered. Unfortunately, de Nuptiis is written in prose. There is however a letter, attributed to Notker and written to his bishop, in which the monk discusses his Alemannic writing system. Unfortunately the letter is more of an apology for the system than an explanation of it, the only technical information being a note on two diacritics, an accent and circumflex, that mark vowels. The issue might be best dealt with in the analysis of sonorants(4.000).

3.231 "Die zeitgenössischen Alphabets werden uns durch eine Reihe von mehr oder weniger genauen Beschreibungen lateinischer und griechischer Grammatiker vermittelt(Penzl 1972:20)"

Since de Nuptiis represents German words with Latin graphs, one must also be familiar with these.

3.241 The cornerstone of Penzl's "Lautforschung", however, is the positing of phonemes through minimal graphemic pairs. Each phoneme should be marked by a specific graph or system of graphs. Graphs contrast in minimal pairs, if they occur in words that are otherwise spelled the same but have different meanings. When graphs so contrast, they represent different phonemes.

3.242 So, for example, the Alemannic word for 'your Sg.' is spelled with <d> after sonorants. ex:

únde din 'and your' 115,14

After obstruents, it is written with a <t>. ex:

nóh tin 'also your' 31,20

This system of graphs does not contrast with itself. Both words mean 'your Sg.'. But it does contrast with <m>. ex:

min 'my' 48,1

3.311 Always, however:

"die Struktur des Systems muß stets erwogen werden(Penzl

1968:134)"

By this Penzl may be in part hinting at the importance of linguistic universals. One cannot just propose isolated phonemes. Instead, an analyst must continually consider, for example, what effect the positing of a labial fricative would have on the positing of a dental one.

3.312 In Phonology, R. Lass cites a 1979 language survey by J. Nartey. The survey had established for obstruents:

"cross linguistic frequency hierarchies for place of articulation(Lass 1984:154)"

Nartey, according to Lass, concluded that the dental/alveolar obstruents were:

"more frequent across languages(Lass 1984:154)"

than the labial ones. These were in turn themselves "more frequent" than the velars. Stops as a class are "more frequent" than fricatives, which are themselves "more frequent" than africates.

3.313 Besides just being a survey of language typologies, Lass believes that:

"the frequency distributions can serve as a partial check on reconstruction of unattested language states: the 'odder' the sysem we construct, the more argumentative support it needs(1984:155)."

In effect, a phrase like "should probably imply" could be inserted into Nartey's conclusions. It might substitute for "more frequent than" when analyzing unattested language states.

3.314 Of course any analyst looks for manuscript and diachronic evidence. In additon to this, however, one might try out Lass's advice. Perhaps velar consonants should probably imply labial ones. Labials in turn, could themselves probably imply dentals. Positing africates would probably imply fricatives. Fricatives then could probably imply stops. A phonemic contrast posited in the labial fricatives might then not only be reflected in the dental fricatives, but also in the labial stops. Through the labials it could be implied into the dental stops too.

3.315 Such a rigorous application of universals, especially in respect to place of articulation, is not born out in all modern languages. Hawaiian, according to Lass, has a labial and velar stop, but no dental one(1984:152). Rotokas contrasts two velar stops in voice(1984:149). Nevertheless it has only single voiceless labial and dental ones. Maori has labial /f/, but no dental fricative(1984:152).

3.316 Perhaps Medieval Swiss also does not pattern exactly after Nartey's original "frequency distributions". In the absence of tapes, however, something is needed to supplement the often scanty diachronic and manuscript evidence. Universals can serve as Lass's "partial check" toward a, if not attested, at least more probable system.

3.321 Another check comes through the desire of any analyst to posit the most simple and natural system possible. This paper will attempt to account for the "Anlautgesetz", along with other obstruent graph alternations, with a phonemic system and a set of phonological rules. Criteria need to be set up to determine how simple and natural these two things, and the system as a whole are.

3.331 A rule is simpler the less symbols it uses. Positing syllable final fortition then is simpler than positing syllable final fortition only after consonants. The first rule needs one less symbol. ex:

Syllable Final Fortition:

$[+sonorant] \rightarrow [+fortis] / _____\$$

Syllable Final Fortition after Consonants:

$[+sonorant] \rightarrow [+fortis] / [+consonantal] _____\$$

3.341 A rule is more natural the more common it is across languages, and the more phonemes it affects. A fortition rule that affects all obstruents is in this way more natural than one that only applies to stops.

3.351 A set of phonological rules is simpler the less rules it has, and the less times that rules need to be ordered. A phonemic system is simpler the less phonemes it has.

3.352 So, for example Penzl, in his analysis of Notker's sonorants, does not posit a velar nasal phoneme /ŋ/. Instead, he derives [ŋ] as an allophone of /n/ before velars:

"Der dentale Nasallaut /n/ hat wohl ein velares Allophon [ŋ] vor velaren Konsonanten (Penzl 1968:143)."

Although this eliminates a phoneme, it adds an additional rule:

Nasal Assimilation:

$[+sonorant] \rightarrow [\alpha place] / _____\$$ ($\$$) $[-sonorant] \rightarrow [\alpha place]$

Trading off phonemes for rules, however, is generally accepted as making a system simpler overall.

3.361 One could further derive just a velar nasal [ŋ] from [ng]. To do this, a second rule would have to be posited, and ordered after the nasal assimilation. After [n] assimilated in place to velar [g], [g] could delete after the homorganic nasal [ŋ].

Velar Deletion:

$[-\text{anterior}]$
 $[\text{+consonantal}] \rightarrow \emptyset / [-\text{anterior}]$
 $[\text{+consonantal}]$

3.362 There are no strict guidelines on simplicity. Perhaps in this case, however, it might be simpler for the system overall to just posit the phoneme /n/. After all, deriving it from [ng] requires two rules and one rule ordering.

3.363 This would at least be more natural. Using /g/ to condition a change in /n/, only to later delete the obstruent, constitutes an "absolute neutralization". Whether such tactics should be allowed in the theory at all is disputed. No one supports them as natural though.

3.411 In the generative model, the feature inventory, syllabification restrictions and rule, phonological restrictions and rules, the phonemic inventory, and rule orderings of de Nuptiis would comprise its phonological component. Perhaps no analyst, however, would argue that all graph alternations in the text need be phonologically motivated. To integrate a graphemic analysis into the transformational framework then, one could perhaps expand on the theory. A second, graphemic component could map the phonologically derived forms onto manuscript graphs. Phonemes or allophones could be assigned graphemes, which, on analogy to phonemes, could represent basic, if somewhat arbitrarily chosen, graphemic values. Graphemes could then undergo various graphemic rules, generating, on analogy to allophones, allographs--that is environmentally conditioned variant graphs. In the interests of simplicity, however, perhaps graphemic rule orderings could be avoided; at least for those rules not morpheme specific.

3.412 So, in an example of a non-morpheme specific rule, [k] might be written <c>, unless placed before a front vowel, where <k> could be generated. ex:

<c> --> <k> / (<C>) <i,e>

scródando 'examining' 46,7

but, skrícchen 'jump' 136,19

A morpheme specific rule, however, could account for the <c> before <i> in:

scrífte 'writing' 24,12

If the spelling was analyzed as conditioned by the <c> in Latin

scriptio 'writing' 64,5

then a rule generating it might read:

<k> --> <c> / <'write'>

In order to not generate

**skrifte 'writing'

the above morpheme specific rule would have to be ordered after

<c> --> <k> / ___(<C>) <a,o,u>

If this paper is only to address "major" graph alternations however, perhaps its graphemic component could restrict itself from positing such morpheme specific rules and the possible rule orderings they can entail.

3.413 An important question might be at what point should the graphs be assigned--at the phonemic level before the application of rules, at the surface structure, at somewhere in between, or at various points for different graphs. In Modern German, for example, syllable final obstruents presumably receive a graphemic value at the phonemic level, or at least before the fortition rule. In Classical Middle High German, however, obstruents are assigned graphs nearer the surface structure, or at least after the fortition rule. ex:

"Weg" 'road' MG

"wek" 'road' MHG

3.414 Ideally, however, in a graphemic analysis one would not propose surface forms, but only those phonological rules that could be based on graph alternations. By its very nature then, such an analysis would assume that graphemes are assigned to allophones--those allophones left generated after the application of the phonological rules the analysis posits.

3.415 So, for example, a graphemic analysis of Modern German, could not propose a syllable final fortition rule. ex:

"Weg" 'road' MG

"Wege" 'roads' NHG

And precisely because of this, it would not err in having the graphemic component begin after the application of the phonological rules it proposed. In a manuscript analysis then, graphemes might be assigned to allophonic, and not phonemic or surface values, and the graphemic component be ordered at the end of the phonological one.

3.421 Before graphemic rules can be set up however, their data must be separated from that of the phonological rules. The following, remaining paragraphs offer some suggestions on how to limit what types of graph alternations might be analyzed as phonologically conditioned, and by this, how to separate them from possible graphemicly

conditioned ones.

3.431 A few phonological rules in de Nuptiis seem to apply across syllable boundaries. Dental stops are lenited after [n]. ex:

fíndest [fín\$dəst] 'you find' 109,18

Obstruents undergo fortition after an obstruent. ex:

físken [fis\$kn] 'fish, dat. pl.' 67,06

3.432 In Modern German, obstruents are made fortis not only syllable finally, but also of course word finally. ex:

"endlich" [ent\$liç] 'finally'

"Hund" [hunt] 'dog'

Benware believes that a word boundary, at least in Modern German phonology:

"is always interchangeable with a syllable boundary(1986:86)"

3.433 Assuming that something like this is true for de Nuptiis, one would like to see rules that apply across syllable boundaries also apply across these when they double as word boundaries. And, as was pointed out in the introduction, very often they do. ex:

fíndest [fin\$dəst] 'you find' 109,18

min déil [min##d[^hilil] 'my part' 48,1

físken [fis\$kn] 'fish, dat.pl.' 67,06

uuelih cot [wéliX##kot] 'which god' 41,9

That scholars have lauded Notker's ear for marking ths, seems a little overblown. There should be no difference separating a word boundary from a syllable one.

3.434 No phonological difference that is. What separates words from syllables is a very large graphemic difference. Words are bordered by spaces.

3.435 Perhaps only the most pedantic neogrammarian would insist that every graph variation or lack of variation should be interpreted phonologicly. ~~de Nuptiis is not written in the IPA alphabet, but~~ rather its writing system was very possibly subject to scribal tradition, the influence of Latin, concerns about conserving parchment and other non-phonological but rather graphemic motivational factors. The most glaring graphemic boundary is the blank space between words. One cannot help wondering that as the syllable boundary may condition some phonological spellings, so might the word boundary condition some purely graphemic ones.

3.436 Distinguishing phonologicly from graphemicly conditioned.

spellings has, so far as the writer knows, only been attempted piecemeal for Notker's writings. Penzl was hindered in this, perhaps in part because he used the word boundary as both phonologically and graphemically significant.

3.437 So, for example, the scholar remarks that <g> after <s> in

fléisg 'flesh' II,88,21

and físg 'fish' I,67,28

is not surprising:

"sg im Auslaut wie bei fisg, fleisg stimmt mit der sonstigen Schreibung des velaren Verschlusslautes überein(1968:49)"

3.438 Does this mean that the graph <k> is restricted from word final position and that rather <g> can mark here both velar stops--whether fortis or lenis? If so, then along with this purely graphemic conclusion Penzl goes on in the next sentence to use the same evidence to draw a phonological one. For the velar stops:

"Es besteht keine phonemische Opposition zwischen Lenis und Fortis im Auslaut(1968:149)"

Velar stops are made fortis here(1972:104).

3.441 Any alternation or lack of alternation could of course be graphemically conditioned. Nevertheless, one might prefer a phonological explanation within certain restrictions.

3.451 Word boundaries were analyzed phonologically as:

"always interchangeable with a syllable boundary(Benware 1986:86)."

So, for example, an analyst might not want to write the following rule:

Word Final Fortition:

$[-\text{sonorant}] \rightarrow [+ \text{Fortis}] / \text{---} \# \#$

It conditions fortition word finally, but not also syllable finally.

3.452 One could codify the above example into a guideline by positing the syllable boundary as the only allowable phonological one. Rules conditioned by word morpheme or sentence boundaries could be then analyzed in a graphemic framework.

3.461 As was mentioned in the introduction, de Nuptiis marks some allophones. ex:

ter teil 'the part' 170,11

min deil 'my part' 48,1

This is, however, for writing systems, at least according to Penzl:

"eine groBe Seltenheit(1968:147)."

3.462 Benware proposes that fortition, and not voicing, distinguishes /g/ from /k/ in Modern German(1984:36). Voice need not then be analyzed as phonemically significant in the stops.

3.463 After obstruents, the otherwise voiced lenes phonemes in German become voiceless. ex:

"dem Guten" [demguutn] 'the good thing, dat. sg.'

but, "das Gute" [dasguutə] 'the good thing, nom. sg.'

A rule could be written:

Obstruent Devoicing:

$[-\text{sonorant}] \rightarrow [-\text{voice}] / [-\text{sonorant}] (\$) \text{ —}$

3.464 In a different process, obstruents are made fortis syllable finally. ex:

"Wege" [veg] 'roads'

"Weg" [vek] 'road'

Obstruent Fortition:

$[-\text{sonorant}] \rightarrow [+fortis] / \text{ — } (\$)$

3.465 Many native speakers may not sense the allophonic difference in fortition here between [g] and [k] in "Wege", "Weg". Even fewer, however, are probably conscious of the voicing difference between [g] and [g] in "dem Guten" and "das Gute". Fortition, as mentioned above, is a phonemically significant feature in the German obstruent system. The speaker must be already familiar with the feature in non-sonorants in order to understand speech. Voice, however, is not needed to distinguish any obstruents, and German speakers might then be perhaps less trained to detect it in allophones.

3.466 The marking of allophones may be a "groBe Seltenheit". If so, then it must be even rarer that a speaker marks allophonic features with which he is not already familiar with in his phonemic inventory.

3.471 The devoicing of [g] to [g] in [demguten], [dasgute] represents

a change in a non-phonemic feature, while the fortition of [g] to [k] in [vege], [vek] affects a phonemically significant feature. A third type of rule, one that falls somewhere between the above two, might be illustrated in German by the fronting before front vowels and consonants of [X] to [ç]. ex:

"Bach" [baX] 'stream'

"Bäche" [becə] 'streams'

A rule could be written:

Velar Fronting:

3.472 The feature [anterior] can distinguish the velars from the non-velars. As such, one could analyze the feature as phonemically significant. With this in mind, the rule fronting [X] in "Bäche" [becə] differs from the devoicing of [g] in "das Gute" [dasgute], but resembles instead the fortition of [g] in "Weg" [vek]. Both the fortition and the fronting rules affect features that are, for the obstruent system, phonemically significant.

3.473 If similar on one level, however, the fortition and fronting rules are different on another. Fortition not only applies to a phonemically significant feature, but in addition also illustrates a phonemically significant change. The allophone [k] from /g/ in "Weg" [vek] corresponds to the [k] from a different phoneme /k/ in "leck" [lek] 'lick'. Fronting of [X], however, does not generate such a phonemically significant change.

3.474 It is unknown to the writer how many German speakers would consciously differentiate between the "Ach-und Ich-Laut", and how many of them first became aware of it, not "naively" in their own language, but in the classroom, or upon hearing other dialects. In any case allophones, according to Penzl, are rarely marked in manuscripts. If he is right, then perhaps a set of rules based on graph alternations could be restricted to those type of rules most likely to be marked--those marking phonemically significant changes. ex:

"Wege" [vegə] 'roads'

"Weg" [vek] 'road'

3.481 Penzl proposes word final fortition of labials and velars (1972:102,104). One might write a rule:

Word Final Non-Dental Fortition:

There seems to be nothing about word final position that should exclude dentals however. Why should just labials and velars become fortis. One wonders just how natural the above rule should be judged. It specifies, for non-vowels, place of articulation in the structural description without mentioning a place feature in the conditioning factor.

3.482 Such rules are, as far as the writer can tell, accepted in the theory. Lass and Anderson, in an account of Old English phonology (1975:208), posit a rule:

Word Final Velar Stop Devoicing:

$$\left[\begin{array}{l} -\text{sonorant} \\ -\text{anterior} \\ -\text{continuant} \end{array} \right] \rightarrow [-\text{voice}] / _ \# \#$$

3.483 The rule, however, "raises the problem of 'explanation' or motivation (1975:183)", a problem that can only be solved by appealing to "positional strength-hierarchies". According to Giegrich, a model that is "more highly constrained (1984:4)" should be adopted, if it can be. If one could then successfully analyze a text without positing rules like the one above, perhaps one should.

3.491 In order to motivate trying to phonologically interpret the exclusion of certain spelling patterns, an analyst would need to assume that the excluded sequences of phonemes could occur. To provide this motivation then, one might propose the following guideline. All phonemes, subject to sonority restrictions on syllable structure, should be allowed to occur underlying in any order.

3.492 So, for example, while <t> and <d> contrast syllable finally after liquids, only <t> occurs here after nasals, ex:

<d>	<t>
u <u>u</u> ard	u <u>u</u> ort
'became'	'word'
I, 5, 17	I, 502, 18
	f <u>a</u> nt
	'found'
	I, 98, 19

But in order to motivate trying to interpret this phonologically.

however, an analyst would have to first allow both dental stops to come after nasals here.

3.493 In addition, a phonological interpretation might take either of two forms. That only [t] comes syllable finally after nasals might be accounted for with either:

a) a rule:

Fortition:

$[-\text{sonorant}] \rightarrow [+ \text{fortis}] / \left[\begin{array}{l} \text{Nasal} \\ \text{sonority} \\ \text{or lower} \end{array} \right] _ \#$

b) or a restriction:

$** \left[\begin{array}{l} \text{nasal} \\ \text{sonority} \\ \text{or lower} \end{array} \right] [-\text{fortis}] \#$
 $** \left[\begin{array}{l} -\text{sonorant} \end{array} \right] \#$

3.494 In deciding between the two options one might perhaps use the following guideline. Restrictions could be preferred, except when one had reason to believe that a restricted sequence might occur as underlying in some word. ex:

$\text{f}^{\text{h}}\text{indest}$ underlying /fin $\$$ dVst/ or fin $\$$ tVst/ 'you find' I,104,7

$\text{f}^{\text{h}}\text{ant}$ underlying /fant or fand/ 'found' I,98,19

3.495 If one accepts this guideline, then the restrictions should perhaps be the least controversial part of the phonological component. Perhaps even just an overview of the manuscript could provisionally justify the following ones.

$** [+ \text{stress}] [+ \text{stress}]$

$** [\alpha \text{consonantal}] [\alpha \text{consonantal}] [\alpha \text{consonantal}] [\alpha \text{consonantal}]$

$** \left[\begin{array}{l} -\text{consonantal} \\ +\text{hi} \\ \alpha \text{anterior} \\ +\text{stress} \end{array} \right] \left[\begin{array}{l} -\text{consonantal} \\ +\text{hi} \\ -\alpha \text{anterior} \end{array} \right]$

ex: $\text{u}^{\text{h}}\text{i}^{\text{h}}\text{set}$ [u $\text{i}^{\text{h}}\text{z}^{\text{h}}\text{et}$] 'leads' I,97,25

** [+consonantal
+sonorant
α continuant
β lateral] [+consonantal
+sonorant
α continuant
β lateral]

ex: fórn [vorn] 'before' I,176,1

**# [+consonantal
+sonorant] [+consonantal
+sonorant]

ex: nals [nalz] 'not at all' I,14,20

3.511 There are perhaps two major sources a linguist can use when analyzing earlier language states: related living languages and ancient texts. Methods of internal reconstruction--the comparison of related modern languages to help describe a related ancient one--have been incorporated and debated in the generative framework. A guideline for using it was codified in (3.200).

3.521 For the second source of phonological information, ancient texts, perhaps Penzl was the first to apply methodological rigor. But his method, the comparison of minimal graphemic pairs, can, on its own, arrive at little more than the number of phonemes. A more exact description of the phonemic inventory however, and any discussion of phonological rules, has relied on, even in recent essays, on internal reconstruction. The alternative, if not "Schallanalyse", might be best referred to as graphemic analysis unmotivated by method.

3.522 So, for example, in a 1968 essay Penzl discusses word initial <ch> in Notker's works. Methods of internal reconstruction, as the scholar admits, allow the graph to mark either an affricate [kX] or fricative [X]:

"Nach Konsonant könnte ch das Zeichen der einfachen Afrikate sein, die im Auslaut bei Nasal als Verschlusslaut (däng) bei Liquida als Spirans (uuérh, scalh) vertreten ist. Das wurde darauf hinweisen, daß ch im Anlaut in chünning 'König', chraft 'Kraft', chömen 'kommen', chléine 'klein' auch als Afrikate [kX] bestimmt werden könnte. Auf

Grund der modernen Dialektverhältnisse wäre die Spirans [x] im Anlaut durchaus möglich. Der erwähnte paradigmatische Wechsel mit g spricht aber dafür, daß ch auch das Zeichen für die Afrikate sein kann(1968:146)."

3.523 In a later essay however, the scholar attempts more, in a statement that neither Penzl's method nor internal reconstruction can support:

"Ich sehe im ch des Anlauts (chünninga, cheiser) die Spirans /X/, wie die Inlautsschreibung (riccho) und die Werte des gegenwärtigen Stadtdialektes zu scheinen zeigen(1972:103)."

3.531 And in an analysis published this decade, Clausen explores the "Anlautgesetz" and <t/d> alternation after <n>. In them he sees that:

"Notker's German must have lacked precise syllable and word boundaries, that the language was more flowing, and less choppy than Modern German is today. This, in turn, leads me to the conclusion that the glottal stop was not present in Notker's time, since the use of a glottal stop would institute a pause which would make sound assimilations arising out of close juncture impossible(1980:364)."

3.532 The above quote strikes the reader with perhaps two errors in analysis. The first is perhaps purely technical. A glottal stop, if present in Notker's speech, may have only appeared before syllable initial vowels, as in Modern German. ex:

"und" [ʔunt] 'and'

In neither the <t/d> alternation nor the "Anlautgesetz" are vowels affected.

3.633 A second, perhaps more structurally significant problem has to do with the motivation for the analysis itself. Glottal stops are not marked in the manuscript. Why discuss them then?

3.541 Already in 1968 Penzl had tried to answer this question, outlining what he saw as the task of historical phonology:

"Die historische Lautlehre darf sich nie damit begnügen, nur das Phoneminventar zu erforschen. Die Erkenntnis der Allophone ist wichtig, ebenso eine Bestimmung der Lautwerte, denn die phonetischen Tatsachen ermöglichen erst die genauere Analyse des Systems(1968:133)."

So stops, for instance, are differentiated by Penzl according to fortition. In addition, however, he also assigns them values for the secondary, phonemically insignificant features [voice] and [aspirate]:

"Wir müssen b d g als stimmlose Lenisverschlüsse bestimmen, t in tag als stimmlosen, aspirierten Fortisverschlüssen, ebenso p und k in den Stellungen in denen sie vorkommen(1968:147)."

3.542 The scholar's ambition was not restricted to the structuralist school. Lass and King, in a generative approach to Old English phonology, admit that:

"as far as we can tell, historical investigation does not permit us to recover much more than grossly binary (i.e. classificatory) specifications(1973:203)."

Nevertheless:

"this does not mean of course that we can permit ourselves the luxury of a purely 'algebraic' approach to historical phonology, where only 'oppositions' and not their content count. We must attempt as we have all along here, to achieve reasonably full specification at the phonological and systematic phonetic levels(1973:203)."

In their epilogue each consonant gets described with respect to 13 features, at least two of which, [hi] and [lo], are not needed to distinguish any consonant phoneme(1973:225).

3.551 The reader may have noted by now how this paper could break with the philosophy of Penzl, Lass and King. Instead of interpreting the maximum possible out of the manuscript, it could rather posit the least phonological and graphemic information necessary to generate spellings.

3.561 Labial stops do not occur word finally after nasals in de Nuptiis. But then again, neither does the word for "lamb", written

lám̄p 'lamb' II,239,2

in the Psalms. One could ignore this form, and with it /b/ and /p/ syllable finally after nasals: While the analysis would then account for the graphs in de Nuptiis, it would neglect part of the system that generates these graphs.

3.562 This paper is about the de Nuptiis obstruent system, not just the sum of graph sequences in the manuscript. The system of course generates words outside those of de Nuptiis. One would want it to generate them correctly.. ex:

lám̄p 'lamb' II,239,2

and not **lám̄b or **lám̄

Notker's other manuscripts can help an analyst make the best guess. Frequent use is thus made of Sehrt's Notker Wortschatz(1955), the complete list of all the forms in the Notker canon.

3.563 Examples from de Nuptiis will of course always be preferred. Nevertheless this paper will not hesitate to support rules for de Nuptiis with forms that do not occur in it.

3.571 Ideally one would hope to trace every decision made in an

analysis back to a section on methods. While the author believes this can be done with the analysis on obstruents, the treatment of sonorants uses some more guidelines, proposed in section(4.000).

4.000 Vowel Phonemes

4.100 Single Stressed Vowels

4.111 According to Penzl,

"das Schreibungssystem Notkers erleichtert die Erkenntnis von Langvokalen (ī, ē, ā, ō, ū) und phonetisch nahstehenden, wohl etwas offeneren, weniger gespannten Kurzvokalen (i, e, a, o, u) als zwei Phonemreihen(Penzl 1972:99)"

Rather than posit length or tense as phonemic in vowels, this analysis has chosen to simply juxtapose single vowels with vowel sequences. ex:

[i]	[ii]
blīg	līb
(blik)	(līib)
'glance'	'body'
I.743,23	I.8,21

4.112 In determining the number of vowel phonemes then, an analyst might start with the single vowels. ex:

blīg (blik) 'glance' I.743,23

He could begin by contrasting at least five vowels, differentiated by the five vowel graphs in the Latin alphabet.

sín [sin] 'sense' I.161,7

er [er] 'he' I.5,3

scáf [skaf] 'created' I.790,18

doñ [doX] 'nevertheless' I.22,20

unde [unde] 'and' I.54

In light of diachronic evidence in Modern Swiss and Proto-Germanic one might assign them categories, differentiating them with a minimum of 3 features.

+anterior	-anterior
+hi i	u

-hi, -lo e o

+lo a

4.121 Beyond this, however, scholars have traditionally argued for an additional row of 3 umlaut vowels /y, ø, œ/. That these are not always marked is given a graphemic explanation by Clausen:

"The primary reason for Notker's failure to indicate affricates or rounded front vowels was the lack of suitable orthographic symbols at his disposal (Clausen 1980:367)."

Nevertheless attempts to mark vowels can be seen, according to Penzl, in the following patterns.

[-anterior]	[+anterior]
hūs [hūuz] 'house' I, 405, 24	hīuser [hyyʒz r] 'houses' II, 186, 19
frō [vro] 'happy' I, 208, 4	frōemidiu [vrømædy] 'alien' I, 676, 4
hānt [hant] 'hand' I, 252, 20	hēnde [hænsde] 'hand dat.' I, 388, 14

4.122 In the section on methods a guideline was proposed for using diachronic evidence. In it, a graph was interpreted as marking two different segments if it could be shown that these were different in Proto-Germanic and Modern Swiss. So, for example, <f> in

flégest [pflegʒst] 'you care' I, 815, 20, Modern Swiss [pflekst], PGmc. [plegest]

fīlo [vilo] 'much' I, 42, 30, Modern Swiss [fil], PGmc. [filu]

4.123 For the umlauted vowels, however, diachronic evidence, if measured against this guideline, could not be used. Although /y, ø, œ/ are phonemes in Modern Swiss dialects, they had of course not separated from /i, e, a, o, u/ in Proto-Germanic. In light of this, an analyst then is left with purely graphemic evidence to base a decision on.

4.124 In general, the umlaut vowels are traced back to allophones of /u, o, a/, fronted before front vowels. ex:

hūs [hūuz], from an earlier underlying /huuz/ 'house' I, 405, 24

híuser [hýy\$zɔr], from an earlier underlying /huu\$zir/ 'houses'
II,186,19

Without evidence to the contrary, one would of course hope to continue to analyze [y, ,] as allophones of /u,o,a/, and so simplify the phonemic inventory by three vowels. A fronting rule then might account, for example, for the <u,iu> alternation:

hús 'house' I,405,24

híuser 'houses' II,186,19

Fronting:

$[-\text{consonantal}] \rightarrow [+ \text{anterior}] / _ \left(\begin{smallmatrix} \circ \\ \infty \end{smallmatrix} \right) (\$) \left(\begin{smallmatrix} \circ \\ \infty \end{smallmatrix} \right) [+ \text{consonantal}] [+ \text{anterior}]$

4.125 Beyond this Penzl notes a similar alternation between "front" and "back" vowel graphs in

fínf 'five' I,66,26

funf 'five' II,424,7

guuínnen 'to win' I,140,21

guuúnnen 'to win' I,248,14

If this <i/u> alternation reflects an [y] in de Nuptiis however, it cannot, at least in

fínf [vymf] 'five' I,66,26

funf [vymf] 'five' II,424,7

be generated by the fronting rule. The [y] is not followed by a front vowel.

4.126 In addition, at least historically the <u> in

fúnf 'five' II,424,7

guuúnnen 'win' I,248,14

descends from a Proto-Germanic /i/, reflected, in part, by their Modern English glosses. And /i/, as a front vowel, would of course remain unaffected by a fronting rule.

4.127 Instead, Penzl posits a rounding of /i/:

"u neben i (guuúnnen, guuínnen) deutet auf den Lautwert [ú], den

gerundeten hohen Vordervokal, der sich aus [i] nach stark gerundetem [w] entwickelte (Penzl 1972:99)."

If such a process could be maximized however, then according to the guidelines perhaps it should be. One might write a rule:

Rounding:

$[-\text{consonantal}] \rightarrow [+round] / [+round]$

Such an analysis however, if to account for

fünf 'five' II.424,7

guúnnen 'to win' I.248,14

would entail specifying /u/ and labial consonants as [+round].

$\left[\begin{array}{l} +\text{anterior} \\ -\text{coronal} \\ +\text{consonantal} \end{array} \right] \rightarrow [+round]$

$\left[\begin{array}{l} -\text{anterior} \\ +\text{hi} \\ -\text{consonantal} \end{array} \right] \rightarrow [+round]$

4.131 Two rules then could generate the umlaut vowels from /i, e, a, o, u/. Such a solution, however, entails, at least in the case of Fronting, specifying the vowels after the umlaut vowels as [+anterior]. ex:

húser **[hýʏʒər] 'houses' II.186,19

fróemiddu **[vrømədy] I.676,4

4.132 Although these are marked by <e> and <i>--graphs that mark front vowels in Latin--both graphs are taken by Penzl to mark a [-anterior] schwa here. That this [ə] could not condition fronting:

"macht die Unabhängigkeit der Umlautsvokale von ihrer Umgebung deutlich, sie müssen daher Phoneme, können nicht länger stellungsbedingte Allophone sein(1972:100)."

4.133 Penzl's proposal might be examined later, in an analysis of rules affecting unstressed vowels. For now then, perhaps an additional argument would be needed to establish umlaut vowels as phonemes. A guideline was proposed that only changes of phonemic significance should be marked. Since umlaut vowels are often marked, then that, according to the section on methods, should point to them

being phonemes.

4.134 If one accepts this, then 8 vowels could be differentiated with a minimum of 4 features.

	[+anterior]		[-anterior]
	[+rnd]	[-rnd]	
[+hi]	ɣ	i	u
[+hi, -lo]	∅	e	o
[+lo]	æ		a

4.135 In addition, Fronting and Rounding need to be proposed to account historically for /y, ∅, æ/. Since the writer cannot find evidence for deleting these rules from the grammar, an analysis might be simpler if it left them in.

4.200 Unstressed Vowels

4.211 Stress time languages like Modern German or English often have environments in which vowels, or at least [-hi] vowels, are "reduced", and so do not contrast. ex:

findet [findæt] 'he finds' MG

Ideally one would hope to describe the vowel generated in these, usually unstressed environments, as neutral--that is in completely negative features. For de Nuptiis that would mean [-hi, -lo, -anterior, -round], the allophone [ə].

4.221 In his analysis of the vowel system in Notker's manuscripts, Penzl notes that <e> often takes the place of an earlier <i> (1968:136). de Nuptiis

liute 'people' I, 84, 6

compares to Old High German 'liuti'.

4.222 Penzl sees in this:

"den Lautwert [ə], d.h. den eines zentralisierten Vokals von unbestimmter Klangfarbe (1968:136)."

4.231 The same schwa value is interpreted into the collapse of all short vowels to <e> interconsonantly in inflectional endings (1968:136). Penzl's examples again juxtapose:

Notker	OHG
stuonden 'stood' 61,12	'stuontun'

fáren 'faran'
'go'
50,3

tágen 'tagon, tagun'
'days'
II,14.10

One might write a rule:

Vowel Reduction:

$[-\text{cons}] \rightarrow \text{schwa} / [+ \text{cons}] _ [+ \text{cons}]$
 $[-\text{stress}]$

4.232 In addition, Penzl points out that:

"Der diagraphische Vergleich mit früheren Denkmälern zeigt, daß bei Notker im Auslaut oft o für pragraphisches u eingetreten ist: nimo(1.Sing. Pras. Ind), minno(Gen., Dat. Sing. Fem.), frido(Nom. Sing.)(1968:136)."

The above examples correspond to Old High German "nimu" 'I take', "minnu" 'of love', and "fridu" 'peace'.

4.233 Earlier short syllable final <u> and <o> fall together to <o>. Maybe the phenomena should only be analyzed as marking a syllable final collapse of [u] and [o] here. If so, the resulting rule could also account for the alternation of <i> and <e> here. Instead of Penzl's [ɤ], however, the <e> in

liute 'people' I,84,6

would then mark an [e].

Vowel Lowering:

$[-\text{consonantal}] \rightarrow [-\text{hi}] / [+ \text{consonantal}] _ [+ \text{stress}]$ #

4.234 The only position where, in a manuscript, a phoneme can be clearly analyzed as occurring syllable finally is, of course, word finally. Rules are more natural the more phonemes they affect. <i> and <u>, the most frequently used graphs for high vowels, do not

occur, stressed or unstressed, word finally. Given this, perhaps the above rule could be simplified, and its application maximized, by dropping the [-stress] specification in the conditioning factor.

Vowel Lowering:

$[-\text{consonantal}] \rightarrow [-\text{hi}] / [+ \text{consonantal}] _____ \#$

4.300 Vowel Sequences

4.311 What have been traditionally analyzed as long vowels by Penzl have been taken here as vowel sequences. ex:

líib [líib] 'body' I,8,20

When done so, they become comparable with other sequences of 2 or even 3 vowels, sequences not normally grouped together with "long" vowels. ex:

rúoh [rúoh] 'raw' I,167,28

uúieha [uúieha] 'holy' I,746,1

4.212 Restrictions can help narrow down the number of 3 vowel sequences to those beginning with unstressed high vowels. ex:

** $[-\text{consonantal}] [-\text{consonantal}]$
 $[-\text{hi}] [+ \text{stress}]$

uúieha [uúieha] 'holy' I,746,1

They could also likewise limit 2 vowel sequences beginning with unstressed vowels. ex:

uuólf [uuólf] 'wolf' II,345,2

4.313 Even so, however, with 8 vowel phonemes that still leaves 8x8 or 64 different possible sequences of

$[-\text{consonantal}] [-\text{consonantal}]$
 $[+\text{stress}]$

Unfortunately, Notker only seems to have at best under 20, and that is even if one assumes differences in umlaut, differences not always marked. ex:

túot 'does' I,9,26

líenti 'light' I,203,12

cnúege 'enough' I,463,10

níomer 'newer' I,30,15

éa 'law' I,262,19

día 'the, fem. acc.' I,44,23

éid 'oath' II,366,19

híuser 'houses' I,97,20

gelóubta 'believed' II,522,29

gelóubti 'may believe' I,9,15

rát 'council' I,321,23

ríten 'ride' II,146,9

rót 'red' I,456,26

hús 'house' I,405,24

tate 'he may do' I,63,23

téta 'he did' I,7,5

4.321 If possible, an analyst would of course like to account phonologically for this. The small amount of minimal pairs would, according to the guidelines, motivate excluding certain sequences by collapsing them into others. But into which ones? Penzl, for example, chooses to stick close to the orthography. <ou> then in

gelóubta 'believed' II,522,29

marks [óu], the allophones the graphs correspond to in the IPA alphabet. But is this justified? Can one seriously maintain that the <ou> here could not also denote, for example, an [áu] or even [áo], as <au> does in Modern German. ex:

'Haus' [háos]

4.322 Nevertheless some sequences, for example [áo], are rare among languages, arguably unnatural. An analysis then might be justified in

excluding these for other, more common sequences. Specifically, diphthongs between different vowels of the same height (ex: [eo, iy, a, o]) are, so far as the writer knows, rare. If one also excludes with this group sequences of mid to low vowels (ex: [, ea, o]), the writer finds examples of this expanded group primarily, not in modern languages, but rather in proposed reconstructed ones. So Penzl sees [ea] in Isidor's hear 'here' and [eo] in OHG beotan 'to offer' (Penzl 197:100). Two rules could be written then, excluding such sequences from de Nuptiis:

Vowel Assimilation 1:

$\begin{bmatrix} \alpha hi \\ +lo \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow \begin{bmatrix} \text{matrix} \end{bmatrix} / \begin{bmatrix} \alpha hi \\ +stress \\ \text{matrix} \end{bmatrix}$

Vowel Assimilation 2:

$\begin{bmatrix} \alpha hi \\ -lo \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow \begin{bmatrix} \text{matrix} \end{bmatrix} / \begin{bmatrix} \alpha hi \\ -lo \\ +stress \\ \text{matrix} \end{bmatrix}$

4.331 While this wipes out some sequences (ex: [íy, íu]), it still allows de Nuptiis to contrast an array of different diphthongs, all beginning with the same stressed element.

4.332 To avoid this one could depict those sequences going from a [+hi] vowel to a [-hi] one as ending in $\begin{bmatrix} V \\ -hi \end{bmatrix}$. ex:

ruoh [ruθh] 'raw' I,167,28

With this restriction, and the rules proposed earlier, an analysis would limit itself to positing only one diphthong for each sequence beginning in a high vowel. In a sense, a restriction on contrast gets proposed:

$\begin{bmatrix} -consonantal \\ \alpha matrix \\ +stress \\ +hi \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} -consonantal \\ -hi \end{bmatrix} \neq \begin{bmatrix} -consonantal \\ \alpha matrix \\ +stress \\ -hi \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} -consonantal \\ -hi \end{bmatrix}$

4.341 Perhaps three more guidelines need to be mentioned before proposing an analysis of the VV sequences. Some languages, like English, contrast diphthongs of the same direction (rising or falling) and place (front or back). ex:

bye [báj]
bay [beí]

This of course might also hold true in manuscript languages too. If so, however, an analyst might perhaps hope to see the diphthong of the

widest dispersion, that is the one that covers the greater distance in height, marked with two different vowels. So if [ou] and [au] contrast in

gelóubta 'believed' II,522,29

and rôt 'red' I,456,26

one might hope to see <ou> mark [áú].

4.351 Secondly, a type of vowel sequence, for example $\check{V}V$, might certainly have more variants than the number of vowel phonemes. If so, however, one might hope to see each vowel phoneme occur as the stressed element in at least one variant.

4.361 Thirdly, the analysis so far has concerned itself with intrasyllabic vowel combinations. Vowels can however of course also occur across syllable boundaries. A very obvious example being when these double as word boundaries. ex:

lebéndiu óuh 'living also' 45,7a

In addition, however, Penzl also draws a syllable boundary between vowels when these occur across a morpheme boundary, before, for example, the feminine marker [a] in

día [di\$a] 'the, fem. acc.' I,4,23

éa [e\$a] 'law' I,262,19

and after the negative particle [ni] in

niomer [ní(i)\$ome[i,e]r] 'never' I,30,15:

"bei Zirkumflex eine Morphem- und Silbengrenze bestehen kann (sía, día; éa) lex). ío (niomer) (Penzl 1972:100)."

A syllabification restriction could be written.

***[-consonantal] + [-consonantal]

If so, it could allow an analyst to not try to contrast <íó, íá, íe> as 3 different diphthongs, all probably beginning in [i].

4.371 If one accepts the preceding analysis, then 13 syllable internal $\check{V}V$ sequences could be depicted phonologically as:

riten [ríi\$tan] 'to ride' II,146,9

híuser [hyy\$zər] 'houses' I,97,20

hús [húuz] 'house' I,405,24

tēta [té(e,i)sta] 'did' I,7,5

rōt [ró(o,u)t] 'red' I,456,26

tāte [tæste] 'he may do' I,63,23

rāt [raat] 'council' I,321,23

liēnti [liəhsti] 'light' I,463,10

cnūēge [knýæge] 'enough' I,463,10

tūot [túot] 'does' I,9,26

éid [[V̄,-hi]id] 'oath' II,366,19
[V̄,+lo]e

gelóubti [gel[V̄,-hi]ybsti] 'may believe'
[V̄,+lo]ø

gelóubta [gel[V̄,-hi]ubsta] 'believed' II,522,29
[V̄,+lo]o

4.4000

4.411 As mentioned earlier, vowel graphs are distinguished not only by graph, but also often by a diacritic; either circumflex (^) or accent (´):

sīn 'to be' I,6,3

sín 'mind' I,161,7

4.412 Notker himself admitted that the decision to mark a vowel with a diacritic or not was at least partially graphemicly conditioned. In a letter to his bishop he writes:

"Opertet autem scire quia uerba theutonica sin accentu scribenda non sunt. preter articulos ipsi soli pronuntiantur acuto et circumflexo (Penzl, 1972:92)."

The only stressed vowels that should not receive diacritics would then be in, according to Penzl:

"Namen, Formen des Artikels der Personalpronomina, Präpositionen (1972:92)."

Scholarship might be agreed on the difference between those vowels marked with diacritics and those not. Nevertheless that still leaves room for considerable debate about the conditioning factor behind the choice of diacritic, when one is used, i.e. on what conditions a circumflex or accent in, for example:

s^ˆin
'to be'
I,6,3

s^ˆin
'mind'
I,161,7

t^ˆuot
'does'
I,9,26

gel^ˆoubta
'believed'
II,522,29

4.421 Edward Sievers saw the diacritics as marking tone, circumflex over falling tone, accent over rising tone.

4.431 Several years later Lloyd contrasted single vowel graphs in length. Diachronic evidence pointed to a circumflex over long vowels and accent over short ones.

s^ˆin
[sin]
'to be'
I,6,3

s^ˆin
[sin]
'mind'
I,161,7

4.432 Having established this, he extracted the diacritics as length markers. Diphthongs with circumflex then could contrast in length with those marked with accent.

t^ˆuot
I,9,26

gel^ˆoubta
II,522,29

4.441 Penzl, agreed with Lloyd in his analysis of single vowel graphs. Nevertheless when discussing vowel graph sequences the scholar breaks with both Sievers and Lloyd. After a circumflex:

"eine Morphem-und Silbengrenze bestehen kann (s^ˆia, d^ˆia; e^ˆa>'lex'. t^ˆo (niomer)(Penzl:1972:100)"

Given this, the accent mark in diphthongs:

"scheint eine gr^ˆoßere Einheitlichkeit der Artikulation anzudeuten(Penzl:1972:100)."

4.442 How this "gr^ˆoßere Einheitlichkeit" should be expressed formally is difficult to say. Even if Penzl means "without a syllable boundary" his analysis would seem not to capture 3 graph sequences marked with circumflex and yet not divided by a syllable boundary.
ex:

t^ˆuot 'does' I,9,26

cn^ˆuege 'enough' I,463,10

l^ˆiehti 'light' I,463,10

It is difficult to say why these sequences should be any less

"einheitlich" than <óu> and <éi> in:

gelóubta 'believed' II,522,29

éid 'oath' II,366,19

4.451 In addition, however, an analyst might find a second disadvantage with Penzl's "größere Einheitlichkeit" theory, a disadvantage it shares with Lloyd's introducing length as phonemic in diphthongs, and Siever's tonal theory.

4.452 According to the section on methods, a graphemic analysis should strive to propose as little information as possible needed to generate manuscript spellings. Ideally then, an analysis of the diacritics might be least burdened if it could avoid proposing any new information, but rather interpret the circumflex and accent redundantly, that is by letting them mark things already marked in the graphs.

4.453 That this is impossible with single vowel graphs might be shown with minimal pairs. ex:

sín	sín
'sense'	'to be'
I,161,7	I,6,3

A difference in diacritic changes meaning.

4.454 Likewise when over vowel graph sequences the placing of the diacritic gives otherwise unmarked phonological information.

íomer	íoh
'always'	'also'
I,29,30	I,6,2

The stressed vowel receives the diacritic.

4.455 When one analyzes the type of diacritic however, that is whether circumflex or accent, an analyst wonders if the difference is needed to distinguish VV graph sequences. If not, perhaps the choice of diacritic here could be interpreted redundantly, that is without burdening the analysis by having it propose any additional phonological information. The sequences marked by circumflex <úo, íe, úe, ío, ía>, have not all been given exact phonological values. Their interpretations, however, though loose, all share one trait. In each sequence, whether separated by a syllable boundary or not, the vowels change in height, going from higher to lower. ex:

túot [túot] 'does' I,9,26

And in those graph sequences marked with accent <iu, ei, ou>, this does not happen. ex:

híuser [hýy\$zar] 'houses' I,97,20

4.456 A summary of the diacritics then might allow them to be conditioned phonologically. One type of diacritic placement then would

be redundant:

$[-\text{consonantal}]$
 $+\text{stress}$ \rightarrow $\alpha \wedge / \text{---}$ $[-\text{consonantal}]$
 α lower than the
preceding vowel

$+\wedge = \text{circumflex}$

$-\wedge = \text{accent}$

A second would be phonemically necessary. ex:

$[\acute{i}] \rightarrow \langle \uparrow \rangle$

4.500 Consonantal Sonorants

4.511 The words:

mán 'man' I,10,31

námo 'name' I,68,8

lánt 'country' II,206,6

and rán 'ran' I,707,3

all contrast their initial graph in near minimal pairs. Diachronic evidence, in Modern Swiss and Proto-Germanic, allows one to interpret them as consonantal sonorants, and differentiate them from each other as:

/n/ [-continuant, +coronal]

/m/ [-continuant, -coronal]

/l/ [+continuant, +lateral]

/r/ [+continuant, -lateral]

5.000 Stop Phonemes:

5.111 Stops will be treated in individual sections: first the labials, then the dentals and lastly the velars. This same order can then be repeated for their corresponding fricatives. Nevertheless the number and distribution of stops is disputed and pertains to the stops as a class. The issue could of course be dealt with piecemeal in the individual sections. It might, however, be more succinctly handled beforehand.

5.112 Scholars are not agreed as to how many stop phonemes are represented in Notker's writings, and where they occur. Penzl(1972)

allows for six phonemes word medially /p,t,k,b,d,g/. Nevertheless he insists on only four word initially /b,d,t,g/. This same group minus /t/ is advanced most recently by Clausen (1980). He reanalyzes, however, his three stops as fortis /p,t,k/. One year before, Moulton (1979) devoted an entire paper to establishing six stop phonemes /p,t,k,b,d,g/. He too, however, like Penzl, only contrasts /b,t,d,g/ at word boundaries.

5.211 Penzl and Moulton have made lists of near minimal pairs between /t/ and /d/. The contrasts occur after vowels and liquids, across and within syllable and word boundaries. In these positions, Alemannic /d/ is written <d>, and /t/, <t>.

	/d/	/t/
after vowel	állero díernon 'of all girls'	állero tíero 'of all animals'
w.i.	77,6	127,9
after <r>	uuard 'became'	uuórt 'word'
s.i.	19,9a	109,20
after <l>	uuálde 'woods'	uuáltet 'governs'
s.f.	21,5	151,10

5.212 But neither scholar stops here. Word medial and <g> contrast with <pp> and <kk> after what can be reconstructed as a short vowel:

fortis	lenis
síppun 'relation' 110,8	síben 'seven' 153,4
rukkes 'back Gen.' II,256,12	régen 'rain' 59,9

5.213 The phonemic significance of this contrast is not beyond dispute. <pp> and <kk> do not necessarily need to be analyzed as single fortis phonemes. They could also, as their spelling suggests, be taken for stop clusters. That these sequences of stops differ from single lenis phonemes would then be undeniable. It is, however, hardly a cause for positing a velar and labial fortis phoneme. The spellings <pp> and <kk> raise two issues. First, should these spellings be analyzed as marking single fortis phonemes? If so, then a second question can be asked. Are these phonemes in the first or second syllables of

rukkes 'back Gen.' II,256,12

and síppun 'relation' 110,8.

5.221 The issue gets all the more muddled by a 3-way opposition in the dentals. <d>, <t> and <t><t> contrast intervocalically after short vowels. ex:

líde 'songs' 49,9

síto 'custom' 103,10

mítti 'middle' 96,2a

5.222 Moulton accounts for this 3-way contrast by positing length in addition to fortition as phonemic in intervocalic stops:

"Short lenis /d/ + short fortis /t/ + long fortis /tt/ (1979:245)"

Length has remained, if not a primary phonemic feature, at least a secondary phonetic one down into the present day:

"Modern Swiss German dialects show a two way opposition which can be described phonetically as lenis-and-short/d/ vs. fortis-and-more-or-less-long /t/ (1979:245)"

5.223 In the interests of keeping an analysis simple however, as few phonemically significant features might be proposed as possible. A lenis-fortis opposition was already posited for the dentals. ex:

/d/	/t/
uuáalde 'forest' 21,15	uuáltet 'governs' 151,10

In light of this, even though length may play a phonetic role in the modern dialects, it might be simpler to analyze the <t><t> in

mítti 'middle' 128,22

as two fortis stops, rather than as one long one. If so, then [t] can be juxtaposed with [tt] in:

Single Stop	Stop Cluster
síto 'custom' 103,10	mítti 'middle' 128,22

5.224 Unfortunately, there are no forms corresponding to

síto 'custom' 103,10

with single <p> or <k> after short vowel (ex: **luko, **ripo). These could be juxtaposed with <pp> and <kk> in:

Single Stop	Stop Cluster
**rípo	síppun 'relation' 110,8
**lúko	rúkkes 'back Gen.' II,256,12

<kk> and <pp>, like <t><t> in

mitti 'middle' 128,22

could then be identified as stop clusters.

5.231 Instead, Moulton believes that Modern Swiss points to single fortis phonemes in Notker's <pp> and <kk>. He also raises a second argument, based on complimentary distribution, but first proposed by Penzl for Old High German /f/ as a whole:

"Der häufige direkte Wechsel zwischen ff nach Kurzvokal und f nach Langvokal deutet darauf hin, daß die ursprünglichen Geminata sich in einen einfachen labiodentalen Fortisreibelaute verwandelt hat(1972:148)"

If with "Langvokal" Penzl also includes diphthongs, <ff> and <f> are in complimentary distribution. ex:

óffen 'open' 65,22

tíefo 'deeply' 103,16

5.232 As mentioned earlier, single <p> and <k> do not occur intervocalically after short vowels. One would expect this if they stand in complimentary distribution with <kk> and <pp>. Unfortunately, at least in de Nuptiis, <p> and <k> also do not come after long vowels or diphthongs.

5.233 The form

trákón 47,3

makes a lone exception to this. Sehart's Notker Glossar, however, lists the word as:

"trákón (trágon?) pigrescere: träge, langsam werden(1962)"

As such, it is hard to place the <k> in this word in complimentary distribution with the <kk> in

rúkkes 'back Gen.' II,256,12

5.234 The words for "trickery" and "sheepskin", however, are unambiguously glossed by Sehrt. ex:

scápáre "sheepskin" II,284,1

cóukele "trickery" II,246,24

Both words are written with single <p> or <k> after long vowel or diphthong. Complimentary distribution can then be established in:

	/k/	/p/
after	rúkkes	síppun
V	'back Gen.'	'relation'
	II,256,12	110,8
after	cóukele	scápáre
VV	'trickery'	'sheepskin'
	II,246,24	II,284,1

5.311 With <kk> and <pp> both established as single fortis phonemes, the second issue of which syllable they belong to can be addressed. Should the syllable boundary in

rúkkes 'back Gen.' II,256.12

be drawn before the <kk> (ex: [ru\$ks]) or after it (ex: [ruk\$ s]).

5.312 Without reasons to the contrary, one would of course want to maximize onsets. Fortis labial and velar stops occur word initially in:

cántiken 'canticles' II,590,28

púrpuren 'purple' 63,7a

The significance of the Latin origin of these words will be handled later. They might for now, however, be provisionally accepted as helping [p] and [k] satisfy Benware's 3rd guideline. If both stops are posited word initially, they should also be able to occur syllable initially. ex:

rúkkes [ru\$ks] 'back Gen.' II,256.12

and síppun [si\$pn] 'relation' 110,8

5.313 Unfortunately, this puts a single <i> or <u> syllable finally. And this cannot happen word finally. A rule prevents it:

Vowel Lowering:

$[- \text{consonantal}] \rightarrow [- \text{hi}] / [+ \text{consonantal}] \text{ — } \$$

5.321 If the stops cannot be placed syllable initially, perhaps they can come syllable finally, leaving <u> and <e> syllable initial in:

síppun [sip\$ɔn] 'relation' 10,8

rúkkes [ruk\$ɔs] 'back Gen.' II,256,12

Unfortunately [ə] is an unacceptable word beginning in de Nuptiis, except perhaps when followed by a stressed syllable. <i> occasionally alternates with <e> here. ex:

erráten 'to guess' I,101,6

irráten 'to guess' I,166,21

Apparently then the single fortis stops here might fill a dual role. They could serve as codas after the short [i] and [u], and as onsets before the schwas.

5.324 Such an analysis has a precedent, or perhaps in the case of de Nuptiis, an antecedent, in treatments of Modern German. A single consonant between a short vowel and a schwa in German is usually written "double" (Benware 1986:82). ex:

"bitte" [bitə] 'please'

German speakers, Benware argues, perceive that the syllable boundary:

"falls on the consonant itself which serves both as coda and onset (1986:84)"

5.325 Giegrich admits that readers will not find the concept of ambisyllabicity "intuitively very agreeable (1984:80)". Nevertheless his system forces positing it, not only word medially in "matte", but also word finally in the uninflected form of the word (1984:80).

5.331 Syllable boundaries between two graphs have been marked by dividing the word. A dollar sign can then be placed between the two graphs. ex:

uaáltet [uaá\$taət] 'governs' 151,10

5.332 Although [k] in

rúkkes [ruk^hs] II,256,12

begins and ends syllables, it does not occur next to a syllable boundary. It is ambisyllabic, and one would want to exempt it from rules conditioned by a syllable boundary. To better illustrate this, the syllable marker could be raised above the [k], and the word left undivided. ex:

rúkkes [ruk^hs] 'back Gen,' II,256,12

5.411 In addition to dental /t/ then, fortis labial and velar stops also occur after vowels as syllable onsets and codas. They contrast with lenis /b/ and /g/. ex:

fortis	lenis
síppun 'relation' 110,8	síben 'seven' 153,4
rúkke 'back' 69,2a	régen 'rain' 59,9

5.412 /t/ and /d/, however, also contrasted after consonantal sonorants. ex:

/d/	/t/
uuálde 'forest' 21,5	uuáltet 'governs' 151,10
uuárd 'became' 19,9a	uuórt 'word' 109,20

One is of course curious to see if the labial and velar stops continue this same lenis=fortis opposition after liquids and nasals.

5.421 The words

cínken 19,21

and zínkun 95,08

are glossed by Sehrt as 'prong'. They contrast with

síngen 'sing' 45,4.

The forms

púrpurínen 12,17

and púrpurun 63,74

are glossed 'purple'. A syllable boundary might be drawn between the <r> and <p>, and this sequence contrast with <r> in

árbeite 'work' 118,14

5.422 These examples, among others, "leave no doubt(1979:245)", according to Moulton, as to a lenis=fortis contrast after consonantal sonorants too. His de Nuptiis examples, and all others the writer can find in the manuscript, occur in near minimal pairs.

/p.k/	/b.g/
górpoton 'bodies' 141,17	árbeite 'work' 118,14
púrpurínen 'purple' 12,17	"
púrpurun 'purple' 63,74	"
cínken 'prong' 91,21	síngen 'sing' 45,4
zínkun 'prong' 95,08	"
glónken 'slime' 124,10	"
furkun 'trident' 51,19	búrgo 'castles' 19,10

5.431 But are these seven forms relevant? Four are of Latin origin, and for three of these, parallel Latin words are even found in de Nuptiis. Alemannic

górpoton 141,17

compares with Latin

gorpeios 150,12

Both are glossed 'bodies'. Alemannic

púrpurînen 12,17

and púrpurun 63,74

mean the same as Latin

'purple' 102.4.

The word

furkun 'trident' 57,19

does not have a Latin counterpart in de Nuptiis. It comes from Latin "furca" 'trident' though.
5.432 These four words:

furkun 57,19 gorpoton 141,17

purpurinen 12,17 purpurun 63,74

are declined like Alemannic and not Latin words. Nevertheless their Latin origin makes them suspicious. It suggests that the <p> and <k> in

górpoton 141,17

and fúrkun 57,19

might not represent two fortis phonemes, but rather only Latin spelling influences.

5.433 In other words, Notker might have written <p> insted of after <r> in

górpoton 'bodies' 141,17

because he recognized the word as related to Latin

gorpeios 'bodies' 150,12.

If so, he would not necessarily have had to phonemically differentiate the <p> in

górpoton 'bodies' 141,17

from the in

árbeite 'work' 18,14.

5.441 One possible problem with an appeal to Latin spelling influence specifically concerns the word

fúrkun 'trident' 57,19.

Before non-front vowels, <c> is often substituted for <k> in other German words. ex:

cot 'god' 41,9

kot 'god' 163,9

5.442 Perhaps Notker really did not phonemically differentiate the <k> in

fúrkun 51,19

from the <g> in

burgo 'castles' 19,10

But if he was instead only trying to copy Latin "furca" here, why did he not at least stick to the Latin orthography? Instead he writes <k>, not Latin <c>. ex:

fúrkun 'trident' 51,19

not **fúrcun 'trident'

5.451 The words

cínken 'prong' 91,21

zínkun 'prong' 95,08

and glónken 'slime' 124,10

are not of Latin origin and cannot be explained away through spelling influence. But they are only 3 words in a very large manuscript. Could they not just represent spelling inconsistencies on the part of Notker or one of his copyists? That is what Sehrt and Starck might say. They corrected deviations from the "Anlautgesetz" in their edition of Notker's works.

5.452 Such an argument would be boosted by citing "correctly" spelled parallel forms. That is, places in where the scribe did not fail to write in <g> after the sonorant. ex:

**glóngen 'slime'

alongside glónken 'slime' 24,10

5.453 Perhaps such corrected forms are lacking for

glónken 124,10

because the word for "slime" only occurs once in the text. But "prong":

zínkun 95,08

cínken 91,21

is written twice, and both times it is "misspelled". And these two "misspelled" forms contrast in a minimal pair with

síngen 'sing' 45,4.

5.454 "Purple" also occurs twice in

púrpurun 63,74

and púrpurúben 12,17.

It contrasts with

árbéite 'work' 18,14.

In light of these contrasts, the writer cannot find an easy way out of also positing after consonantal sonorants, as after vocalic ones, a lenis-fortis opposition in the labial and velar stops.

5.511 In the section now ending, velar stops contrasted after nasals. ex:

/g/	/k/
síngen	zínken
'sing'	'prong'
45,4	95,08

The dentals however did not. Dentals did contrast syllable finally after liquids. ex:

/d/	/t/
uuárd	uuórt
'became'	'word'
19,9a	109,20

Yet a parallel example in the labials could not be found. 5.512 Fortition has been established as phonemic throughout the stops as a class. Perhaps any further discussion of these stops should be broken down into the individual places of articulation.

6.000 Obstruent Analyses--Format

6.111 The following table contrasts the graphs that, according to this analysis, /p/ and /b/ are generated as in different syllable environments, and after various sonorant ones.

Labial Stops

		/b/	/p/
after VV	s.i.	uu ^ˆ iben 'women' 94,2	scá ^ˆ pá ^ˆ re 'shepskin' II,284,1
	s.f.	uu ^ˆ ib 'woman' 14,15	?
after VV	s.i.	áber 'but' 149,16	síppun 'relation' 110,18
	s.f.	ab 'from' II,391,14	?
after liquid	s.i.	uuer ^ˆ ben 'recruit' 161,12	púr ^ˆ purun 'purple' 63,74
	s.f.	uuar ^ˆ b 'recruited' 146,22	?
after nasal	s.i.	l ^ˆ ember 'lambs' II,486,6	gump ^ˆ iten 'pond' II,21,3
	s.f.	l ^ˆ amp 'lamb' II,239,9	
after obst.	s.i.	ih peg ^ˆ inne 'I begin' 35,19	
	s.m.	sp ^ˆ ere 'spears' 38,7	
Word Initial		beg ^ˆ onda 'began'	púr ^ˆ pur ^ˆ inen 'purple'

6.112 The same type of chart will also precede the discussions of the dental and velar stops, and then in turn, those for the labial, dental and velar spirants. As such its format might be best explained here.

6.211 The chart is ordered from top to bottom according to the sonority level of the graph preceding the obstruent. On top are the \check{V} sequences, then come the single vowels, followed by the less sonorant liquids, then the nasals and finally the obstruents.

6.212 Not all possible gradations of sonority are represented. So, for example, vowels are not split between the non-high and the less sonorant high ones. Only the differences between sonority levels are listed, which are significant for at least one of the stops or fricatives. A difference is significant if it:

"corresponds to a change in pattern."

6.213 So, for example, for the labial stops the difference in sonority between liquids and nasals is significant. can occur syllable finally after <r>, while <p> comes here after <m>. ex:

		/b/		/p/
after	s.f.	uuarb		?
liquid		'recruited'		
		146,22		
after	s.f.	lāmp		
nasal		'lamb'		
		II,239,9		

6.221 As is hinted at in this last example, obstruents are further broken down into syllable positions. s.i. stands for syllable initially, s.m. for syllable medially and s.f. for syllable finally. The in

uuarb 'recruited' 146,22

can then be classified as s.f..

6.222 The in

āber 'but' 149,16

functions as both a syllable onset and coda. As such, it could be marked 's.f. s.i.'. The here however occurs in, but perhaps not next to a syllable boundary. In order to stress this, a different notation could be used. a.s. stands for ambisyllabic.

6.223 Stops, as obstruents, tend to be at the edges of syllables. Their lower level of sonority prohibits them from occurring syllable medially between sonorants. Only another obstruent, and then in Notker's works only a dental fricative, can precede them within a

syllable. ex:

spé[^]re 'spears' 38,7

The special case of syllable medial stops before obstruents, i.e. of africates, will be handled later in the sections on fricatives. ex:

chó[^]pf 'head' 74,1

6.224 The different syllable positions will always be marked. Nevertheless, only after other obstruents can obstruents occur syllable medially.

6.231 Syllable final obstruents are usually, except perhaps in compounds, word final. ex:

	/b/	/p/
after s.f.	uuib [^]	?
VV	'woman'	
	14,15	

Syllable initial ones, however, often occur word medially. ex:

	/b/	/p/
after s.i.	uuiben [^]	scáp [^] áre [^]
VV	'women'	'sheepskin'
	94,2	II.284,1

In order then to crosscheck in the charts Benware's 3rd guideline, a special row, ordered last, could list single obstruents word initially. ex:

	/b/	/p/
Word	begó [^] nda	púr [^] purí [^] nen
Initial	'began'	'purple'
	110,11	12,17

6.232 In Modern German, according to Benware, of the single vowels only schwa can occur word finally. ex:

"Meere" [merə] 'seas'

Given his guidelines on syllable division then, all short vowels other than [] should not be allowed syllable finally, even if that entails making a following single obstruent ambisyllabic. ex:

"bitte" [bitə] 'please'

6.233 In de Nuptiis, however, of the single vowels, only high vowels cannot be established word finally. ex:

Notker	OHG
liúte 'people' 60.17	liuti
nímo 'I take' II.123,18	nimu

but. táge 'day, dat. sg.' I,39,1	tage 'day dat. sg.'
tága 'day, nom. pl.' I,101,11	taga 'day, nom. pl.'
tágo 'day, gen. pl.' II,64,6	tago 'day, gen. pl.'

While the single high vowels in

rúkke [ruke] 'back' 69.2a
sippun [sip n] 'relation' 110.8

should perhaps be analyzed as coming before an ambisyllabic stop, a single non-high vowel in the same environment need not necessarily pattern on analogy to the high ones. ex:

sagen [sag^ʰən] or [saʃgən] 'to say' I,74.11

6.234 The problem, however, of placing the syllable boundary after single [a] could perhaps only become significant if a rule, for example a fortition, got conditioned syllable initially even after a vowel, generating **[saʃken] 'to say'. ex:

Syllable Initial Fortition:

[-sonorant] → [+fortis] / \$ _____

If such a rule will not be posited, the issue might remain unresolved and, at least for the obstruent system, perhaps unimportant.

6.235 To get around this question in the charts then, two possible rows have been collapsed. Short vowels before ambisyllabic obstruents and those before syllable initial ones are listed together. ex:

	/b/	/p/
after s.i.	áber	síppun
V	a.s. 'but'	'relation'
	149,16	110,18

6.411 In some positions and <p> do not contrast. ex:

	/b/	/p/
after s.f.	lám̥p	
nasals	'lamb'	
	II,239.9	

Nevertheless, a guideline was proposed. Phonemes should be able to occur in all the same environments before the application of rules. Outside of restrictions three steps could be taken to account for such a lack in contrast.

6.421 One could try to derive it phonologically, according to the guidelines set down in the section on methods. A phonological explanation could be marked in the chart by writing the form between the fortis and lenis columns. ex:

	/b/	/p/
after s.f.	lám̥p	
nasals	'lamb'	
	II,239,9	

6.431 Sometimes a phonological explanation proves impossible. If so, perhaps the lack of contrast can be accounted for graphemically. One could notate a graphemic explanation by listing the two graphemically identical obstruents as contrasting phonemically. ex:

	/v/	/f/
after s.f.	uuólf	hálf
liquids	'wolf'	'helped'
	II,345,25	I,24,5

6.442 To arrive at such a graphemic explanation, however, one needs evidence that identical graphs really do contrast phonologically. This could be done with diachronic evidence. One might also cite forms of the words where the contrast is not obliterated. ex:

	/v/	/f/
after s.i.	uuólua	hélfen
liquids	'wolves'	'help'
	II,238,1	48,18

6.451 Sometimes such evidence cannot be found. Occasionally a

phonological explanation proves impossible too. If so, perhaps the lack of contrast might just show a hole in the lexicon. That is, there would be no phonological reason why phonemes could not contrast here, just no examples of it. Holes could be marked with a question mark. ex:

	/b/	/p/
after s.f.	uuárb	?
liquid	'recruited'	
	146,22	

6.461 In addition, in the course of analysis, two phonemes could be contrasted in a position from which one of them is restricted. ex:

	/h/	/X/
after s.i.	0	uuérches
liquid		'of work'
		137,4

A zero here might mark a phoneme as restricted from this environment.

7.000 Labial Stops

	/b/	/p/
after s.i.	uuíben	scápáre
VV	'women'	'sheepskin'
	94,2	II,284,1
s.f.	uuíb	?
	'woman'	
	14,5	
after s.i.	áber	síppun
short a.s.	'but'	'relation'
vowel	149,16	110,18
s.f.	ab	?
	'from'	
	II,391,14	
after s.i.	uuérben	púrpurun
liquid	'recruit'	'purple'
	161,12	63,74
s.f.	uuárb	?
	'recruited'	
	146,22	

after s.i.	l [́] ember	g [́] umpiten
nasal	'lamb'	'pond'
	II.486,6	II.211.3

s.f.	l [́] amp
	'lamb'
	II.239,9

after s.i.	ih p [́] eginne
obst.	'I begin'
	35.19

s.m.	s [́] pere
	'appears'
	38,7

Word	beg [́] onda	p [́] urpurinen
Initial	'began'	'purple'
	101.11	12.17

7.111 [p] and [b] contrast as syllable codas. ex:

/b/	/p/
s [́] iben	s [́] ippun
'seven'	'relation'
I.24,8	110.18

Before a syllable boundary, however, the contrast does not get confirmed. ex:

uu[́]ib 'woman' 4,15
 ab 'from' II.391,14
 uu[́]arb 'recruited' 146,22
 l[́]amp 'lamb' II.239,9

Can this be explained phonologically?

7.112 One might propose a syllable final fortition rule.

Syllable Final Fortition:

$[-\text{sonorant}] \rightarrow [+ \text{fortis}] / \text{---} \#$

Unfortunately such a syllable final collapse is not reflected in the dentals. ex:

/d/	/t/
t [^] oð	t [^] uot
'death'	'does'
119,1	131,15

7.113 One could ammend the rule so as to apply only to labials.

Labial Final Fortition:

$$\left[\begin{array}{l} -\text{sonorant} \\ -\text{coronal} \\ +\text{anterior} \end{array} \right] \rightarrow [+fortis] / _____\$$$

This would, however, entail specifying place of articulation in the structural description. Yet no place feature is mentioned in the conditioning factor? Why should only labials become fortis syllable finally? Perhaps one could instead account graphemicly for the lack of contrast.

7.121 Although they do not contrast, <p> and both occur word finally. ex:

uu[^]ib 'woman' 14.15

l[^]amp 'lamp' II,239.9

The graphemic rules that could account for this would have to be conditioned by more than just the word boundary:

<p,b> --> <p> / <m>_##

<p,b> --> / <not m>_##

Whether such a complicated process should be allowed or not is difficult to say. One could exclude the <p> in

l[^]amp 'lamb' II,239,9

from this group. Then only the in

uu[^]ib 'woman' 14,5

ab 'from' II,391,14

and uu[^]arb 'recruited' 146,22

need be explained graphemicly. ex:

<p.b> --> / <not m>_##

7.122 To posit any graphemic conditioning factor, however, one needs evidence that identicle graphs really do contrast phonologicly. The two options proposed for doing this were:

1) with diachronic evidence

2) by citing forms of these words where the contrast is not obliterated by a graphemic restriction. ex:

	/v/	/f/
after s.f.	uuólf	hálf
liquid	'wolf'	'helped'
	II.345,25	I,24,5

The above words can be compared to forms where the graph contrast is not lost. ex:

	/v/	/f/
after s.i.	nuólua	helfen
liquid	'wolves'	'help'
	II,238,1	48,18

7.123 [p] occurs syllable initially after vowels and liquids. ex:

scáp[^]are 'sheepskin' II,284,1

síppun 'relation' 110,18

púrpurun 'purple' 63,74

One looks for "apocopated" forms of these three examples with word finally. ex:

**scáb, **síb, **púrb.

These could show that <p> was restricted from word final position after non-nasals. Examples with <p>. ex:

**scáp, **síp, **púrp.

would speak against such a graphemic rule. Unfortunately, the writer can find none of these forms.

7.131 [p] from underlying /p/ occurs syllable finally in Modern German, and, presumeably, in Alemannic dialects too. ex:

"Flipp aus!" 'freak out!'

At least in Modern German, however, examples of syllable final [p]

from /p/ have all been borrowed in after the second sound shift.
 7.132 That the shift had ceased to be productive by de Nuptiis is supported by examples of unshifted /p/ in borrowed words. ex:

púrpurun 'purple' 63.74

As syllable codas, /p/ and /b/ contrast.

/b/	/p/
siben 'seven' I.24,8	sippun 'relation' 110,118

7.133 In light of these two things, one might argue that, if no rule is posited to prevent it, /p/ and /b/ should also be able to contrast as word codas, and thus syllable finally. The system would then allow syllable final [p] after liquids and vowels, even if no examples with it had been borrowed into the language yet. ex:

	/b/	/p/
after s.f.	uuib	?
VV	'woman'	
	14.5	

7.211 In the section on methods, it was argued that phonemes should be allowed to occur in all the same environments before the application of rules. If so, then a syllable medial fortition rule is needed to allow lenis /zb/ to generate fortis <sp> in

spére 'spears' 38.7.

Syllable Medial Fortition:

$[-\text{sonorant}] \rightarrow [+ \text{fortis}] / [-\text{sonorant}]$

Obstruents could be made fortis when bordered by an obstruent in the same syllable.

7.221 A second rule could be written to allow both /p/ and /b/ to generate <p> in:

ih peginne 'I begin' 35,19

Obstruents could make a following obstruent fortis, even across syllable boundaries. This second fortition rule would form a provisional "Anlautgesetz" to be refined later.

"Anlautgesetz":

$[-\text{sonorant}] \rightarrow [+ \text{fortis}] / [-\text{sonorant}] (\#) _$

7.222 The two rules could be combined into one process:

Fortition:

$[-\text{sonorant}] \rightarrow [+ \text{fortis}] / \left\{ \begin{array}{l} [-\text{sonorant}] \\ [-\text{sonorant}] (\#) _ \end{array} \right.$

7.231 In Notker's works as a whole, the word for 'lamb' is written 5 times. In 3 examples it ends with , and in two with <p>. ex:

lāmb 'lamb' II.146.26

lāmp 'lamb' II.239.9

Its plural is written once, and then with syllable initial . ex:

lēmber [lem\$ b r] 'lambs' II.486.6

7.233 A general syllable final fortition rule found little support in de Nuptiis. The issue, as it pertains to all obstruents, might more elegantly be handled in the summary(14.000). For now, however, perhaps the lower sonority of nasals, lowest for all the sonorants, might be provisionally taken into account. A fortition rule could help generate the <p> in

lāmp 'lamb' II.239.9

Syllable Final Fortition:

$[-\text{sonorant}] \rightarrow [+ \text{fortis}] / \left[\begin{array}{l} \text{nasal} \\ \text{sonority} \\ \text{or lower} \end{array} \right] _ \#$

Only the labial stops have been examined so far. Nevertheless, one might wish to provisionally extend the fortition rule to all

obstruents. By maximizing its application the rule becomes simpler and more natural. There is also a second, perhaps even more attractive reason for this. If the rule can be extended to apply to all obstruents, it can be integrated into the obstruent fortition rule already posited.

Fortition:

7.311 <f> after <m> alternates with <p><f> in :

gelimflichí 96,16

and gelimpflichéro 92,10

Both words are glossed 'suited'. In fact, the same is true for this alternation; scholars have traditionally chosen to derive [mpf] from an underlying /mf/.

7.312 A nasal is a stop; the mouth closes for [m] as it does for [p]. Often, in de Nuptiis, a fortis fricative can come after the nasal, as /f/ after /m/ in

gelimflichí /gelim\$fliXi/ 'suited' 96,16

To only pronounce a fricative after the nasal, a speaker must simultaneously stop nasalizing, and open his mouth. If he does not perform this double articulation perfectly, if he stops nasalizing a fraction before opening his mouth, he pronounces an epenthetic stop before the fricative. ex:

gelimpflichéro [gelim\$pfliXe[e,i]ro] 'suited' 92,20

7.313 The phenomena occurs in Modern English. The word "chance" is usually generated as [tʃants] instead of [tʃans]. It rhymes with "chants" [tʃants]. A rule accomplishing this for

gelimpflichéro 'suited' 92,10

could be written:

Epenthesis:

8.000 Dental Stops

	/d/	/t/
after s.i. VV	todes 'of death' 113,11	táten 'did' 122,14
s.f.	tod 'death' 118.22a	túot 'does' 129,9
after s.i. short a.s. V	líde 'songs' 44,9	sító 'custom' 103,10
s.f.	líð 'song' I.442.11	erfullet 'fulfilled' 143,19
after s.i. liquid	uuérden 'become' 89,17	uuórto 'of words' 145,3
s.f.	uuárd 'became' 19,9a	uuórt 'word' 143,19
after s.i. nasals	fíndest 'you find' 109,18	
s.f.	fánt 'found' 118,11	
after s.i.	óuh taz 'also that' 154,5	

s.m. sternen
 'stars'
 108.4

s.f. ist
 'is'
 129.6

Word	daz	tuot
Initial	'so that'	'does'
	103.17	113.13

8.111 One of the guidelines of this paper was that phonemes that only differ in fortition should be able to occur in all the same positions before the application of rules. /t/ and /d/ generate contrast in graphs after vowels and liquids. ex:

/d/	/t/
todes 'of death'	taten 'did'
131.11	122.14

Both stops then need to come after these sonorants.

8.122 The present fortition rule

Fortition:

generates /t/ and /d/ as [t] syllable finally after nasals, and in all positions after obstruents. ex:

fant 'found' 118,11

ouh taz 'also that' 154,5

8.113 In the dentals however, the lenis/fortis opposition continues to

collapse even syllable initially after nasals. ex:

fíndest 'you find' 109,18

If possible, one would try to account for this phonologically.

8.121 The fortition rule could be expanded to make obstruents in all syllable positions fortis after nasals. This would even simplify the rule, by deriving the [p] in

lám̄p 'lamb' II,239,9

and in ih peginne 'I begin' 35,19

with part of the same conditioning factor. ex:

Fortition:

8.122 Such a simpler fortition rule would account for dentals not contrasting after <n>. Unfortunately, it would also wipe out after [m] the p-b opposition in

/b/	/p/
lémber	gúmpiten
'lamb'	'pond'
II,486.6	II,211.3

8.123 The word

fíndest 'you find' 109,18

is written with <d>, the lenis graph. Perhaps a rule in this direction, a lenition, would be more appropriate.

8.124 [n] is a dental nasal, homorganic to [d] in

fíndest 'you find' 109,18

One could propose lenition after homorganic nasals.

Lenition:

$$\left[\begin{array}{l} -\text{sonorant} \\ \alpha\text{place} \end{array} \right] \rightarrow \left[-\text{fortis} \right] / \left[\begin{array}{l} +\text{nasal} \\ \alpha\text{place} \end{array} \right] (\$) \text{---}$$

/t/ and /d/ would both generate [d] after [n]. While this would derive 'you find' as

findest 109.18.

it would also generate 'found' as

**fand.

To prevent a syllable final <d> from surfacing after [n], fortition would have to be ordered after lenition.

8.125 In addition however to generating [d] in

findest 'you find' 109.18.

the present rule would also lenite the /p/ in

gumpiten 'pond' II,211.13.

[m], after all, as a labial, is homorganic to [p].

8.126 To avoid generating

**gumbiten 'pond'.

lenition could be restricted to dentals.

Lenition:

$$\left[\begin{array}{l} -\text{continuant} \\ +\text{coronal} \end{array} \right] \rightarrow \left[-\text{fortis} \right] / \left[\begin{array}{l} +\text{sonorant} \\ -\text{continuant} \\ +\text{coronal} \end{array} \right] (\$) \text{---}$$

8.127 Since the lenition rule applies across syllable boundaries, one might also hope to occasionally see its effects reach across these when they double as morpheme or word boundaries. And, as Jelinek(1897) pointed out, one does. The dental in

skinen+ten 'shining' 55.02

can be compared with the <d> in

sk^hinen+den 'shining' 85,16.

Alemannic /t/ is written fortis in

éinen##téil 'one part' 145.6.

The phoneme gets marked as lenited however in

min##deil 'my part' 48,1.

8.211 The <d> preterite marker in

rúnda 'praised' 129,17

and nánda 'named' 132.1a

stands in complimentary distribution with the <t> in

uuólta 'wanted' 29,9

and lértá 'taught' 5,10.

8.212 If possible, one would try to derive the <d> in

nánda 'named' 32,1a,

by expanding the lenition rule to apply after all nasals.

Lenition:

$$\left[\begin{array}{l} +\text{coronal} \\ -\text{continuant} \end{array} \right] \rightarrow \left[-\text{fortis} \right] / \left[\begin{array}{l} -\text{continuant} \\ +\text{sonorant} \end{array} \right] (\$)$$

8.213 Such a rule, however, specifies place of articulation in the structural description, but not in the conditioning factor. Why should not labials lenite after nasals too? ex:

gumpiten 'pond' II,211,3

8.214 One way out of this problem would be to posit a nasal assimilation rule to dental place of articulation. This could increase the environment of the lenition rule, while still limiting its application to dental stops.

Nasal Assimilation:

$$[+sonorant] \rightarrow [tcoronal] / _ (\$) [-sonorant]$$

$$[-continuant] \rightarrow [tcoronal]$$

Such a rule would of course have to be ordered before the lenition rule. Together they could derive

námda [nan\$da] 'named' 132,1a

from an underlying /nam\$ta/.

8.215 Rules are more natural, the more phonemes they affect. In light of this, perhaps one could extend the nasal assimilation to the labials and velars too.

Nasal Assimilation:

$$[+sonorant] \rightarrow [\alpha place] / _ (\$) [-sonorant]$$

$$[-continuant] \rightarrow [\alpha place]$$

8.221 That de Nuptiis usually fails to mark this assimilation across morpheme boundaries might be expected. An [n] allophone in

rúnda [rúun\$da], underlying /rúum\$ta/ 'praised' 129.17

would be both phonemicly and grammaticly related to the [m] in

rúnest underlying /rúum\$Vst/ 'you promise' 155,21a.

Within individual morphemes, however, one might look for more consistency.

8.222 Morpheme internally, the writer can find only one counter example to such a maximized nasal assimilation rule. Before graphs generated by labial /v/. usually the "dental" graph <n> and not "labial" <m> is written. ex:

finfto 'fifth' I,67,26

8.223 <n> and <m> however, do not conntast before /v/. Given this, one might interpret the <n> in

finfto 'fifth' I,67,26

as allophonically, if not also phonemicly, labial. The nasal even surfaces occsionally in the manuscript with the "labial" graph. The word for 'fifth' is written with <n> nine times in Notker's works as a whole. ex:

fínfto 'fifth' I,67,26

Once, however, it shows up with <m>. ex:

fímfta 'fifth' I,48,25

8.231 That in the other nine cases <n> is written is given a tentative phonological explanation by the Braune Grammar. The use of <n> before /v/:

"scheint darauf zu deuten, daß das früher bilabiale germ. f (i.e. Alemannic /v/) im Ahd labiodental geworden [ist] (1975:123 Anm.3)."

Before Alemannic /f/, however, <m> was apparently retained, because [f], or an epenthetic [p] before it, was bilabial.

8.232 While the phonetics of this may have been true, can one really maintain that this is what the <n>=<m> opposition marks here? The scribes were not spectrograms. Nasals in de Nuptiis do not divide phonemically into bilabial and labiodental ones. How can one presume that the speakers were even aware of such a difference, much less that they bothered to mark it?

8.233 But then why <n> before labial /v/, but not /f/? ex:

lenis	fortis
fínue	gelímflíchi
'five'	'suited'
I,197,29	96.16

The alternation looks phonologically conditioned. If so, an analyst would hope to account for it in this way. One possible explanation could be that <n> before /v/ helps mark the lack of epenthetic [p], an allophone not always marked with a stop graph before /f/. ex:

lenis	fortis
fínue	gelámpflíchéro
[vym\$ve]	[gelim\$pfliXero]
'five'	'suited'
I,197,29	92.20
fínf	gelámf
[vymf]	[gelampf]
'five'	'suited'
13,21	I,556,5

That would at least be a change of phonemic significance.

8.234 If one accepts this analysis, then only fortis fricatives should condition Epenthesis, and the rule be of course ordered before the fortition rule. Otherwise

fínf [vymf], underlying /vimv/ or /vymv/ 'five' 13,21

would be generated as

**[vympf].

Its syllable coda would not be able to contrast with the one in

gelámf [gelampf], underlying /gelamf/ 'suited' I,556,5.

9.000 Velar Stops

	/g/	/k/
after s.i. VV	lígen 'lie' 81,7	cóukele 'trickery' I,246,224
s.f.	lág 'lay' 46,16a	?
after s.i. V	tága 'days' 86,10	rukke 'back' 69,2a
s.f.	tág 'day' 170.1	rógh 'robe' I,523,24
after s.i. liquid	burgo 'castles' 19,10	fúrkun 'trident' 51,19
s.f.	burg 'castle' 139,10a	?
after s.i. nasal	sánges 'of song' 98,16a	zínkun 'prong' 95,08
s.f.	sáng 'song' 109,14	
after s.i. obst.	fískén 'fish, dat. pl.' 109,14	
s.i. before <a,o,u>	físca 'fish, nom. pl.' II,243,25	

s.m. skinet
 'shines'
 62,18

s.m. scázza
before 'treasures'
<a,o,u> 62,13a

s.f. mísktón
 'mixed'
 II,458,19

s.f. dísg
word 'table'
final 18,12

Word	gold	cántiken
Initially	'gold'	'canticles'
	23,16	II,540,28

9.111 The singular of

fískēn 'fish dat. pl.' 67,06

occurs in Boethius, but not in de Nuptiis. ex:

físg 'fish' I,167,28.

The word

dísg 'table' 18,12

whose plural is written

díske 'tables' II,55,9

in the Psalms, might serve as a passable substitute.

9.112 Without evidence to the contrary, one would posit <k> and <g> in the above words as marking a difference in fortition. After all, that is what they were interpreted as showing in

sínge 'to sing' 45,4

zínke 'prong' 95,08.

9.113 One problem with this is that de Nuptiis seems to have gotten the graphs mixed up. One would expect <g> in the more sonorant environment before a vowel, and <k> syllable finally. ex:

**físgēn 'fish dat. pl.'

**dísk 'table'

9.114 A second difficulty with this analysis is that <k> and <g> here both occur after <s>. ex:

dísg 'table' 18,12

and físken 'fish' dat. pl.' 67,06.

After obstruents, the fortition rule should blot out any lenis=fortis oppositions.

9.121 How then could this alternation be interpreted phonologically? Penzl argues, perhaps, that it should not be:

"Die Schreibung sg im Auslaut wie bei físg, fleísg stimmt mit der sonstigen Schreibung des velaren Verschlusslautes überein(1968:149)."

If this is to be taken as a graphemic rule, then:

<g.k> --> <g> / ___##

9.131 Penzl may be right. The <g> in

dísg 'table' 18,12

may just be graphemically conditioned. Before accepting this however, one might first explore a phonological explanation.

9.132 In the dative, genitive and plural of 'fish', the stop comes syllable initially. Together these forms occur a total of five times in Notker's works as a whole; each time written with <s><c> or <s><k>. ex:

físken [fis\$kn] 'fish dat. pl.' 67,06

físca [fis\$ka] 'fish acc. pl.' II,243,25

9.133 'Table' is written 3 times with the stop syllable initially. Once it occurs as <k>, and twice as <ch>--a graph that can perhaps only be interpreted as marking palatization. ex:

díske 'tables' II,559,9

tísche 'tables' II,73,23

Perhaps one should posit a rule.

Palatization 1:

[-sonorant] → [+continuant] / [-anterior] [+continuant] [-sonorant] [+anterior]

(#) — [+continuant]

9.134 This would generate [sʃ] from [sk]. To further derive just [ʃ] from [sʃ], and so complete the palatization process, one would need a second rule.

S-deletion:

[+coronal] → ∅ / — (#) [+coronal] [+hi] [+continuant] [-sonorant]

9.211 Besides the alternation between <g> and <k,c>, de Nuptiis further differentiates <k> and <c> after <s>. <c> is generally written before the low or back vowels <a,o,u>. <k>, on the other hand, comes before what Penzl prefers to call the "Palatalvokale" <i,e> (1968:149). ex:

scázza 'treasures' 62,13a

skinet 'shines' 62,18

9.221 A graphemic explanation for this was hinted at in the introduction. <c>, when not preceded by <s>, only alternates with <k> before low and back vowels. ex:

cót 'god' 8,20

kót 'god' 163,18a

Before "Palatalvokale", <c> varies with <z>. ex:

cínken 'prong' 91,21

zínken 'prong' 95,8

9.222 If one assumes that <c> does not mark a [k] when it alternates with <z>, then <c>, as a velar, is restricted from coming before <i>

and <e>. ex:

cót 'god' 8,20

kíezzent 'pour' II,233,17

Likewise, when after <s>, <c> does not vary with <z>, and curiously the graph is also restricted from preceding front vowels. ex:

scázza 'treasures' 62,13a

skínet 'shines' 62,18

Could this not just reflect a continuation of an attempt by de Nuptiis to keep straight the two phonemes <c> can represent.

9.231 Unfortunately, however, the marking of word initial [k] and the one after [s] is not completely analogous, hinting perhaps at an alternative to a purely graphemicly conditioned solution. When not preceded by <s>, <c>, as a velar, is limited to coming before back and low vowels. <k> in this position however, is not similarly restricted to coming before front ones. de Nuptiis could conceivably have just had <k> after <s> before all vowels--both palatal and non-palatal. ex:

**skázza 'treasures'

instead of scázza 'treasures' 62,13a

9.232 It is a simpler system. When not preceded by <s>, <k> is much more common than <c> before all vowels. Why only after <s> are stop graphs so consistently segregated before palatal and non-palatal vowels?

9.233 The combination <s>+velar stop also occurs before consonants; specifically before <r> with the [k] syllable medial, and before <t> with the velar syllable final.

9.234 Before <t>, the graphs <s><k>, <s><ch>, <s><g> and even occasionally just <s> are in free variation in Notker's works as a whole. The sequence <s><c>, as far as the writer can tell, is conspicuously absent. ex:

mísktón 'mixed' I,803,27

míschton 'mixed' II,456,19

kemísgtiu 'mixed' I,792,17

gemísten 'mixed' I,707,20

The form with just <s> is especially interesting. ex:

gemísten 'mixed' I,707,20

Penzl discounts it:

"Deutlich ist zu sehen, daß bei Notker sk sc sg noch eine Konsonantenverbindung von Sibilant und velarem Verschlusslaut und kein einheitlicher Fortissibilant ist. Solche vereinzelt Schreibungen ohne c wie geuuünster 'gewünschter' von uuünsken uuista 'wischte ab' von uuisken sprechen keineswegs dagegen(1968:149)."

They might, however, in addition to examples with <s><ch>, be just the evidence needed to posit some form of palatization.

9.236 In de Nuptiis, <k> and <c> after <s> break down into the following pattern before <r>:

1) Before back or low vowels <c> is written three times and <k> none. ex:

scrodando 'examining' 46.7

2) Before front vowels, the sequence <s>+velar stop+<r> occurs in two words:

a) A word for 'jump' is written once with <c> and three times with <k>. ex:

skricchen 136.19

scricchen 24.6

b) The morpheme 'write' appears 22 times with <c>, and once with <k>. ex:

keskriben 'written' 97.12

scribent 'write' 55.21

scrifte 'writing' 124.21

9.237 One could perhaps analyze the <c> in

scribent 'write' 55.21

and in scrifte 'writings' 124.21

as graphemicly conditioned by the <c> in Latin

scriptio 'writing Lat.' 64.5.

If so, then the same pattern of distribution between <c> and <k> can be set up before <r>+vowel, that was established when no consonant intervened. <c> could get written before low and back vowels, while <k> come before "Palatalvokale".

9.238 <s><k> and just about any other type of spelling other than <s><c> also occur before <t>, ex:

mísktón 'mixed' II,456.19

[t,i,e] have two features in common that can distinguish them from [a,o,u]. They are all [-back] and [-low]. Perhaps one could write a revised palatization process:

Palatization 2:

S-deletion:

9.241 [sk] before a front phoneme was certainly allophonically

different (i.e. more front) than when before a low or back vowel. And when before a vowel, palatal or not, it was also probably different than when syllable final. Perhaps de Nuptiis marks all 3 different allophones of [k] after [s] as phonologically significant; that is, as marking changes in features.

9.242 If so however, it is certainly remarkable, singular in de Nuptiis and, so far as the writer knows, in Medieval writing systems as a whole. de Nuptiis marks some 2-way allophonic distinctions. ex:

fīndest	fānt
'you find'	'found'
109,18	118,11

However it has no other 3-way one and, as will be argued in the section on spirants, often fails to mark even some phonemic oppositions.

9.243 Rather than having the scribes distinguish 3 allophones, perhaps only one allophonic rule for [k] after [s] could be proposed. The question is which one? If palatization is only posited before front stops and vowels, then <c> and <k> can be phonologically derived after <s>. <g> then could be just graphemically conditioned word finally. Perhaps three arguments could speak for this:

1) The seemingly palatal spellings <s><ch> and <s> only occur before front vowels and stops. ex:

tīsche 'tables' II,73,23

gemīsten 'mixed' I,707,20

2) One could try to link phonologically the <s><k> in

fīskēn /fiskēn/ 'fish dat. pl.' 67,08

with the <s><c> in

fīscā /fiskā/ 'fish acc. pl.' II,243,25

and yet distinguish it so from the <s><g> in

fīsg /fisk/ 'fish nom. sg.' I,16,72.

If so, however, palatization could only be proposed syllable initially or before vowels. Unfortunately, if this is done, both the <s><ch> and the <s> in

mīschton /miskto[o.u]n/ 'mixed' II,456,19

and gemīsten /gemisksten/ 'mixed' I,707,20

would be analyzed as marking an unpalatized [k] before the <t>.

3) <k> and <c> do not occur word finally--a very glaring

graphemic boundary which, it will be argued in the section on spirants, conditions two other graphemic restrictions.

9.311 The careful reader will have by now noticed that both of the two processes of palatization discussed so far would violate a guideline.

Palatization 1:

$[-\text{anterior}] \rightarrow [+ \text{continuant} / + \text{anterior}]$

$[+ \text{continuant} / - \text{sonorant} / + \text{anterior}] (\$)$ ——— $[+ \text{continuant}]$

S-deletion:

$[+ \text{coronal} / + \text{continuant} / - \text{sonorant}] \rightarrow \emptyset / \text{---} (\$)$ $[+ \text{coronal} / \text{thi} / + \text{continuant} / - \text{sonorant}]$

Palatization 2:

$[- \text{sonorant} / - \text{anterior}] \rightarrow [+ \text{continuant} / + \text{anterior}] / [+ \text{coronal} / + \text{continuant} / - \text{sonorant}]$

$(\$)$ ——— $([+ \text{sonorant} / + \text{corsonantal}])$ $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} [+ \text{anterior} / - \text{lo} / - \text{corsonantal}] \\ [+ \text{anterior} / - \text{lo} / - \text{continuant}] \end{array} \right.$

S-deletion:

9.312 In both analyses, for example, <s><k> was considered to mark palatization of [sk] to [ʃ] before the front vowel in

skinet 'shines' 62.18

This <s><k> spelling however cannot be interpreted as marking a collapse of [sk] with a phoneme or phoneme cluster; with [z], for example, or [st] or [sp]. ex:

sīto [zito] 'custom' 103.10

stēnnen [sternen] 'stars' 108.4

spēre [spe(e,1)re] 'spears' 38.7

9.313 Neither process of palatization then is a change of phonemic significance. And, according to the section on methods, only rules of this type would be interpreted out of spellings.

9.321 To account for the alternation between <k,c,g> in

fīsg 'fish nom. sg.' I 167.28

fīsca 'fish acc. pl.' II, 243.25

fīskēn 'fish dat. pl.' 67.08

one might then resort to two graphemic rules. If <k>, the most frequent graph for the fortis velar stop is accepted as basic, then <c> and <g> can be generated as allographs by:

<g,k> --> <g> / _##

<g,k> --> <c> / <s>_<a,o,u>

9.331 One of the "palatal" spellings however might still be accounted for phonologically, if one could show that it marked a change of phonemic importance. As Penzl points out, the preterite and past participle forms of

uuisken 'to wipe' I, 16.29

and ¹miskente 'mixing' II,639,1

are sometimes written

gem¹isten 'mixed' I,707,20

uu¹ista 'wiped' I,17,1

9.332 Given the <s><k> sequence in the infinitive and gerund, one might see the <s><t> cluster in the past tense as the graphemic output of [st], /skt/ before the application of rules. Preterite forms retaining a <k> could be accounted for on analogy with the non-preterite. ex:

miskente 'mixing' II,639,1

misk¹t¹on 'mixed' I,803,27

If so, then in

gem¹isten [gemist¹on], from underlying /gemisk¹t¹Vn/, 'mixed' I,707,20

an [st] could be generated from an underlying /skt/.

9.333 And since [st] is of course also generated from sequences where an underlying [skt] cannot be posited, the above change would be of phonemic significance. ex:

uu¹iset /u¹iz¹Vt/ 'leads' I,97,25

uu¹ista /u¹iz¹ta/ 'led' I,739,13

uu¹isken /u¹isk¹Vn/ 'wipe' I,16,29

uu¹ista /u¹isk¹ta/ 'wiped' I,17,1

9.334 One might write a rule, deleting the [k] in underlying /u¹isk¹ta/.

Velar Stop Deletion:

$$\left[\begin{array}{l} \text{-anterior} \\ \text{-sonorant} \\ \text{-continuant} \end{array} \right] \rightarrow \emptyset / \left[\text{-sonorant} \right] _ (\$) \left[\text{-sonorant} \right]$$

If the rule however can be safely maximized to apply to all stops, perhaps it should be, if rules are more natural the more phonemes they affect.

Stop Deletion:

$[-\text{sonorant}]$
 $[-\text{continuant}] \rightarrow \emptyset / [-\text{sonorant}] \text{ — } (\#) [-\text{sonorant}]$

9.335 Expanding the rule to apply to all obstruents however might run into difficulties in the sections on fricatives. If the [s] in [tst] got deleted by a rule, then the contrast in graphs and graph sequences below would have to be interpreted differently than they are in the sections on dentals.

sáʒta [tst] I,100.14

síʒzen [ts] I,5.9

éʒen [s] II,235.8

uuéʒen [z] I,5.5

guíʒsiu [ss] I,45.18

síto [t] I,74.28

líde [d] II,33.3

míttiu [tt] I,743.30

9.411 After nasals syllable finally, labial and dental stops are written fortis. ex:

lámp 'lamb' II,239.9

fánt 'found' 118.11

9.412 Without evidence to the contrary, one would expect to see the same pattern continue into the velars. Unfortunately only <g> occurs in this position, not <c> or <k>. ex:

sáŋg 'song' 109.14

not **sánk, or **sanc 'song'

9.421 Why the inconsistency? Could the velars be exempted from syllable final fortition? That would violate a guideline. Place of articulation was not mentioned in the fortition rule.

Fortition:

Perhaps one could propose a different phonological explanation.

9.422 That velars are not written <k> or <c> after <n> syllable finally, may be only because at the application of the fortition rule, the stops no longer existed after /n/. After assimilating the nasal to a velar, the stops themselves could have been deleted to leave no obstruent syllable finally. The <g> in

sang 'song' 109,14

would then not represent a lenis stop, but only mark the <n> as a velar nasal [ŋ]. And a nasal, as a sonorant, would not undergo fortition.

9.423 The two rules needed to derive [ŋ] from underlying /ng/ however, would entail some rule ordering.

Nasal Assimilation:

Velar Deletion:

This pair of rules would have to be themselves ordered, the second after the first. And of course both should occur before the fortition of obstruents syllable finally after nasals.

9.424 The new rule, Velar Deletion, would further have to come after an "Anlautgesetz" positing the fortition of obstruents after obstruents. [ŋg] and [ŋk] would allow this fortition, and could only do so while they still ended in an obstruent. ex:

sang cütteno 'song of the goddesses' 3,11

9.425 The careful reader will have noted by now that this entails splitting the fortition rule. The "Anlautgesetz", the fortition of obstruents after obstruents, would have to take place while [ŋg] and [ŋk] still ended in an obstruent. The fortition syllable finally after nasals however, must not be able to make the stops fortis. ex:

sáng 'song' 109,14
 not **sánk or **sánc

9.426 As such, the velar stop deletion rule needs to be ordered before this fortition--the same deletion rule that must now come after another fortition, the "Anlautgesetz". ex:

"Anlautgesetz":

$[-\text{sonorant}] \rightarrow [+ \text{fortis}] / [-\text{sonorant}] (\$)$

Velar Stop Deletion:

$[-\text{fortis}] \rightarrow \emptyset / [-\text{continuant}]$
 $[-\text{anterior}]$
 $[-\text{continuant}]$

Syllable Final Fortition:

$[-\text{sonorant}] \rightarrow [+ \text{fortis}] / [\text{nasal}]$
 $[\text{sonority}]$
 $[\text{or lower}] (\$)$

9.427 Perhaps even more unnatural than all these rule reorderings however, is the velar stop deletion rule itself. One could posit /g/ or /k/ after /n/, only to have the stop delete in all environments after the nasal. That would constitute, however, an "absolute neutralization". And these were disallowed in the section on methods.

9.441 The <g> in

dísg 'table' 8,12

was analyzed as graphemicly conditioned:

<g,k> --> <g> />##

Given this, the <g> in

sang 'sang' 109,14

could very well reflect a fortis [k], the same [k] as in

disg [disk] 'table' 18,12.

One might not need the stop deletion rule. The <g> in

sang [sank] 'sang' 109,14

if graphemicly conditioned, would not contradict the fortition reflected in

lamp [lamp] 'lamb' II,239,9

and fant [fant] 'found' 118,1.

9.511 Like /p/, the fortis velar does contrast with its lenis counterpart as a syllable coda.

lenis	fortis
siben 'seven' I,24,8	sippun 'relation' 110,18
taga 'days' 86,10	rukke 'back' 69,2a

For the labials, once contrast was established in syllable codas, the analysis was hard pressed to disallow it in word codas, i.e. syllable finally. If, within the framework of the guidelines, no rule could be posited preventing a [p] from /p/ syllable finally, the system was left able to generate the fortis labial here, even if none had been borrowed into the language yet. If this was justified, the same reasoning should apply to the velar stops. The system would then allow a word, and thus syllable, final [k] from /k/, even if no words with it had been borrowed in after the shift yet.

9.521 Unlike for /p/ however, there may be at least one example of such a newly borrowed syllable final [k] from /k/. A Latin word for 'robe' occurs twice in Notker's works as a whole. ex:

rokkos 'robe acc. pl. Lat.' II,70,10

roccis 'robe dat. pl. Lat.' II,249

9.522 A German word, borrowed from the Latin, comes up three times. Unfortunately, it only gets written in the nominative and accusative singular, i.e. with the velar word finally. ex:

rógh 'robe' I.523,24

rógh 'robe' I.494,24

rógh 'robe' I.523,25

9.523 If one assumes, however, that the velar in

rógh 'robe' I,523,24

corresponds phonemically to the one in

rokkos 'robes acc. pl. Lat.' II.70,10

then the <gh> in it should mark here a fortis [k]. How <gh> might be interpreted can be discussed later(19.000). If the graph, however, could be provisionally accepted as an alternate for <g>, then the [k] in

rógh 'robe' I,523,24

might be accounted for by the same graphemic rule that would generate, for example, <g> and <gh> in

dang [dank] 'thanks' I,48,29

dangh [dank] 'II,510,18

10.000 Spirants

10.111 With the analysis of the stops completed, one can now turn to the fricatives. Besides just filling out the obstruent system, the following examination could possibly reinforce or weaken the conclusions already made about the stops. So, for example, if fortition can be shown to be phonemic in the fricatives, can one really contest that this contrast did not exist in the stops.

11.000 Labial Fricatives

	/u/	/f/
after s.i.	tíue [^] l	ufen [^]
VV	'devil'	'on'
	II,469,23	39,4
s.f.	?	úf [^]
		'up' 19,9

after V	s.i.	hóue	tréffen
	a.s.	'court dat.'	'meet'
		102,3	I,2260,27
	s.f.	hóf	getráf
		'court nom.'	'met'
		87,16a	II,215,27
after liquid	s.i.	uuólua	helfen
		'wolves'	'help'
		II,238,1	I,265,22
	s.f.	uuolf	hálf
		'wolf'	'helped'
		II,345,2	I,24,5
after nasal	s.i.	finue	gelímpflichero
		'five'	'suited'
		I,197,29	92,10
	s.f.	fínf	gelámf
		'five'	'suited'
		13,21	I,556,5
after obst.	s.i.	ópfer	
		'sacrifice'	
		151,9a	
	s.m.	flégest	
		'you care'	
		134,13	
	s.f.	chópf	
		'head'	
		74,1	
Word		uílo	?
Initial		'much'	
		151,17	

11.111 The <u> after sonorants here alternates with <f> in Notker's works as a whole. ex:

<u>	<f>
tíueel	tíiefel
'devil'	'devil'
II,469,23	II,36,1
hóue	hófen
'court dat. sg.'	'court dat. pl.'

102,3	II,550,19
uuólua 'wolves' II,238,1	uuólfa 'wolves' II,238,1
fínue 'five' I,197,29	fínfe 'five' I,750,18

11.112 In de Nuptiis this infringement by <f> on the environment of <u> is carried even further. <u> marks an obstruent so rarely that, at least word internally, the writer can only find examples of it after vowels. ex:

hóue 'court dat.' 102,3

but fínfe 'five' 74,17

Across word boundaries, however, <u> as an obstruent occasionally comes after even consonantal sonorants. ex:

chríechischen uers 'Greek verse' 30,3

11.121 Perhaps one should account for this with a fortition rule specific to de Nuptiis. It could restrict lenis fricatives from occurring word internally after phonemes less sonorant than vowels.

Fricative Fortition:

Such a rule, however, uses an additional phonological boundary other than that of the syllable.

11.131 To avoid this, and yet still account for the data, perhaps a graphemic restriction, specific to de Nuptiis, could be proposed:

<u,C> --> <f> / C

11.211 <ff> after single vowels and <f> after VV reflects a pattern of complimentary distribution already established in the section on stops. In addition, Moulton has pointed out that even after VV, <f> occasionally alternates with <ff>. ex:

[^]tiefi 'depth' II,434,1

t^hieffi 'depth' II,267,17

11.212 Moulton draws the parallel:

"as lenis /v/ is spelled both u and f; fortis /f/ after long vowel or diphthong is spelled both f and ff(1979:246)."

11.221 The graph <ff> brings up an important point. Before drawing syllable boundaries, one should first agree upon which letter sequences represent single phonemes, and which ones clusters. Specifically, for the labials, should

o^pfer 'sacrifice' 151,9a

be divided syllabically between the <p> and the <f>, or should the sequence be analyzed as a single affricate phoneme.

11.222 As <ff> has been traditionally taken for a single fortis [f], <pf> has often been described by Penzl and others as the single graph

"einer labialen Affrikata(1964:292)."

These next few paragraphs might examine whether there are some advantages to rethinking this.

11.223 If <pf> marks a single phoneme, then labial stops can be restricted from preceding non-sonorants syllable internally. ex:

ch^op^f 'head' 74,1

If dental and velar affricates can also be posited, their corresponding stops could be likewise so restricted. In a paper centering on sonority then, an attractive generalization about the environment of stops might be made.

11.224 The spelling <p><f> in

o^pfer 'sacrifice' 151,9a

does not suggest a single affricate phoneme, but rather a consonant cluster. But then again, neither does the spelling <ff> for [f] in

tr^effen 'meet' I,260,27

11.225 Just how could Notker have represented an affricate with anything but such a letter combination like <pf>. Notker took his script from Latin. There were no affricates in Latin, nor single letter graphs for them.

11.226 A more attractive reason for not analyzing <pf> as a single phoneme might be that this could help simplify the obstruent system. If the entire class of affricates can be reanalyzed as consonant clusters, one less class of phonemes need be posited. Because of this, and for phonological reasons that should first become clear in the sections on dental and velar spirants, affricates might be more

elegantly analyzed in this paper as stop-fricative combinations.

11.311 <ff> does not occur syllable initially in de Nuptiis. <f> and <u> do however. When they alternate, it is in a manner that parallels the alternation between <b,d,g> and <p,t,k>. <f> occurs after obstruents, and <u> after sonorants. ex:

so uílo 'so much' 151,17

uuás fílo 'was much' 23,2

11.312 This alternation is not consistently carried through in de Nuptiis however. <f> occurs more often than <u>, even after sonorants. ex:

so fílo 'so much' 159,11

11.313 Indeed, in a reflection of how rare consonantal <u> is in de Nuptiis, only four words begin with a <u> that alternates with <f>. In each one of these, the word beginning with <u> occurs after a sonorant.

<u> after
a sonorant

so uílo
'so much'
151,17

stíefmúoter, uílo
'stepmother, much'
118,17

iro uáhsuuittun
'her hairbands'
12,11

ein uáleuuu
'a colorless one'
68,13

<f> after
a sonorant

so fílo
'so much'
159,11

"

sin fáhs
'his hair'
70,13

danne fáleuuuet
'then it lost color'
68,17

11.321 Juxtaposed to this group are of course the many words that always begin with <f>, regardless if a sonorant precedes them or not. ex:

iro flégest 'you care for her' 134,13

11.322 Syllable initially word medially, contrast between <u> and <f> was interpreted as distinguishing fortis and lenis fricatives. ex:

/v/
tíeu[^]el

/f/
tíe[^]fo

'devil'
II,469,23

'deeply'
I,208,23

11.323 Without evidence to the contrary, one would assume this same contrast in graphs marks the same opposition syllable initially word initially. ex:

/v/	/f/
so u ^h lo	iro flégest
'so much'	'you care for her'
151,17	134,13

11.331 A different analysis, put forth by Penzl, takes into account the consonant cluster [pf].

11.332 All modern Alemannic dialects, according to Penzl, have [pf] word initially. To propose that de Nuptiis does not seem odd. It would entail having word initial Proto-Germanic */p/ shift to */f/ in Notker's dialect. Then either Notker's dialect would die out or the process of spirantization reverse in it by the present day. Any other possible neighboring dialects with word initial /f/ from Proto-Germanic */p/ would also have to become extinct, or similarly change.

11.333 Unfortunately the sequence <p><f> never occurs at a word beginning in de Nuptiis. Penzl's solution to this dilemma is to assign the value [pf] to the word initial <f> that does not alternate with <u>. The <f> spelling is

"für graphisch erklärt(1968:144)".

leaving the graphemic rule:

<p> --> 0 / ##_<f>

11.334 And this is where Penzl's analysis ends, with one fricative phoneme syllable initially:

"'Halbfortis' f im engen Anschluß an vorhergehende Geräuschlaute(1972:102)"

In such close contact with sonorants however is:

"das Lenisallophon selbstverständlich, doch wird es nicht überall bei Notker systematisch geschrieben(1974:102)"

11.341 In the transformational framework, features are analyzed as binary. A phoneme or allophone can be [+ or - fortis], but not **[1/2 fortis]. It's perhaps unclear whether Penzl would argue here then for a basically lenis or fortis value for his labial fricative, although he seems to lean toward identifying it as lenis /v/. Moulton's paper is devoted to proving phonemic oppositions. He does not examine the labial fricatives in positions other than word medially, where he posits a lenis/fortis contrast. Clausen(1980:364) however, opts for a

basically fortis fricative /f/ in

uílo 'much' 151,17,

and there might be some manuscript evidence to support him here.
11.342 The word for 'verse' occurs twice in de Nuptiis, both times written with <u>. ex:

chríechischen uérs 'Greek verse' 30,3

in zuéin uérsen 'in two verses' 51,3

11.343 In Notker's works as a whole, 'verse' does occasionally begin with <f>. ex:

férs 'verse' II.591,10

In de Nuptiis however, only forms with <u> occur.

11.344 A word initial contrast was set up between an <f> that alternated with <u>, and an <f> that did not. ex:

<f>	<u,f>
flégest 'you care' 134,13	fílo 'much' 159,11
	uílo 'much' 151,17

Perhaps a parallel phonological opposition, specific to de Nuptiis, could be posited between a <u> that alternates with <f>, and a <u> that does not. ex:

<u>	<u,f>
uérs 'verse' 30,3	fílo 'much' 159,11
	uílo 'much' 151,17

11.355 A 3-way contrast could then be drawn between [pf], the labial fortis fricative, and the lenis one:

[pf]	[f]	[v]
flégest 'you care' 134,13	fílo 'much' 159,11	uérs 'verse' 30,3

u^hflo
'much'
151,17

11.356 Such a word initial contrast would be welcome if an f=v opposition is posited syllable initially. ex:

/v/	/f/
u ^h u ^h o ^h l ^h ua	h ^h e ^h l ^h f ^h e ^h n
[u ^h o ^h l ^h ʒva]	[h ^h e ^h l ^h f ^h ɔ̃n]
'wolves'	'help'
II,238,1	I,265,22

After all, Benware's third guideline requires that syllables only begin with sequences that can also occur word initially.

11.361 The careful reader will have noticed by now, however, a fundamental incongruence between this analysis and the analysis of the stops syllable initially. The alternation of <b,d,g> with <p,t,k> was analyzed as reflecting lenes phonemes. A provisional "Anlautgesetz", the fortition of obstruents after obstruents, was posited to account for this alternation:

"Anlautgesetz":

[+sonorant] → [+fortis] / [-sonorant] (#) —

11.362 The <f/u> alternation has long been considered part of the "Anlautgesetz". Moulton talks of the:

"alternation between b,d,g,v. and p,t,k.(c),f(1979:241)."

Penzl is even more specific, specifying word initial position:

"Der Wechsel zwischen f und u im Anlaut in fären und uären ist parallel dem bei den Verschlusslauten(1972:143)."

11.363 But if the <u,f> alternation in

so u^hilo 'so much' 151,17

uu^has f^hilo 'was much' 23,2

reflects a basically fortis phoneme /f/, then it must be analyzed differently than the alternation for the lenes stops /b,d,g/. And that would imply positing a lenition rule for fricatives after sonorants, in addition to a fortition rule for stops after obstruents.

Stop "Anlautgesetz":

$[-\text{sonorant}] \rightarrow [+ \text{fortis}] / [-\text{sonorant}] (\#) \text{---}$
 $[-\text{continuant}]$

Fricative "Anlautgesetz":

$[-\text{sonorant}] \rightarrow [-\text{fortis}] / [+ \text{sonorant}] (\#) \text{---}$
 $[+\text{continuant}]$

11.364 Rather than having opposite rules for fricatives and stops, it might be easier to posit the <f,u> alternation as reflecting a basically lenis /v/. Both the stop and fricative alternation could then be accounted for in one "Anlautgesetz".

"Anlautgesetz":

$[-\text{sonorant}] \rightarrow [+ \text{fortis}] / [-\text{sonorant}] (\#) \text{---}$

11.371 This, however, leaves Benware's 3rd guideline unfulfilled. Fortis /f/ generates contrast with /v/ syllable initially word medially. ex:

	/v/	/f/
s.i.	t ^h ieuel 'devil' II,469,23	ūfen 'on' 39,4

One looks for it then syllable initially, word initially.

11.372 After the second consonant shift word initial /p/ was borrowed into Alemannic from Latin. ex:

purpurun 'purple' 63,74

Perhaps similar forms, borrowed with word initial Latin /f/, could be shown to retain the fricative fortis. One might look for recently borrowed words written with an <f> that never alternates with lenis <u>.

11.373 The word for 'window'.

houe
'court dat.'
87,16a

hof
'court nom.'
I,736,26

uuólua
'wolves'
II,238,1

uuólf
'wolf'
II,345,2

fíuae
'five, inflect.'
I,197.29

fíni
'five'
13.21

There are perhaps two possible directions a phonological explanation of this could take.

11.421 One could try to derive the <f>. ex:

uuóif 'wolf' II.345.2

Part of the fortition rule proposed earlier could be ammended to generate [f] after all phonemes syllable finally.

Syllable Final Fortition:

$[-\text{sonorant}] \rightarrow [+ \text{fortis}] / _ \#$

11.422 Unfortunatley this would wipe out the lenis/fortis contrast in

/d/
uard
'becomme'
19,9a

/t/
uort
'word'
109,20

11.431 If the <f> in

uuólf 'wolf' II.345,2

cannot be phonologicly derived, perhaps one could generaate the <u> in

uuólua 'wolves' II,238,1.

11.432 If the obstruents however in

uuólua 'wolves' II,238,1

and uuólf 'wolf' II,345,2

are interpreted as phonemically lenis /v/, a lenition rule should not differentiate them.

Lenition:

$$[-\text{sonorant}] \rightarrow [-\text{fortis}] / [+ \text{sonorant}] (\#) ____$$

Lenis phonemes cannot become more lenis. And anyway, the above rule would again collapse, this time through lenition, the lenis-fortis opposition in

/d/	/t/
<u>u</u> ard	<u>u</u> ort
'became'	'word'
19.9a	109.20

11.433 According to Moulton, Penzl and Clausen, obstruents in Modern Alemannic dialects are phonemically voiceless. If the same is assumed for de Nuptiis, one might change the previous lenition rule into a voicing one. Lenis phonemes could become voiced syllable initially between sonorants.

Voicing:

$$[-\text{fortis}] \rightarrow [+ \text{voice}] / [+ \text{sonorant}] (\#) ____ [+ \text{sonorant}]$$

11.434 If all sonorants in de Nuptiis are [+voice], one could so distinguish them from the obstruents, which are [-voice]. Given this, the rule might be made more natural looking by placing voice in the conditioning factor.

Voicing:

$$[-\text{fortis}] \rightarrow [+ \text{voice}] / [+ \text{voice}] (\#) ____ [+ \text{voice}]$$

11.435 The [v] in

uuólua [uól\$va] 'wolves' II,238,1

would differ in voicing from the [v] in

uuólf [uól_oy] 'wolf' II,345,2.

And part of the fortition rule would differentiate both fricatives from the syllable final [f] in:

fínf [vým_f] 'five' 13.21.

Syllable Final Fortition:

11.436 As is pictured below, the fortition rule and the voicing rule would then divide the lenis obstruents analyzed so far into 3 phonological categories

Lenis Obstruents		
	[+voice]	[-voice]
[+fortis]		lám _p fánt sáng uuólf
[-fortis]	uuérben lémber	uuárb
	uuérden fíndest	uuárd
	búr _g o sánges	búr _g
	uuólua fínue	uuólf

11.441 Syllable final fortition after nasal sonority or lower was proposed earlier. A graph alternation reflected it in 3 of the 4 lenes obstruents studied so far. ex:

Lenis	Fortis
lémber 'lambs'	lám _p 'lamb'

II, 486, 6 II, 239, 9

fíndest fánt
'you find' 'found'
109, 18 18, 1

fínue fínf
'five, inflect.' 'five'
I, 197, 29 13, 21

11.442 The only exception was the substitution of <g> for <c> or <k> in

sáng 'song' 109, 14.

One might account for this, however, with a graphemic rule:

<k> --> <g> / ___##

11.443 In a sort of negative parallel to this, a graph alternation does not reflect a differentiation through voicing in 3 of the 4 lenes obstruents studied so far. ex:

[+voice]	[-voice]
uuerben 'to recruit' 161, 12	uuarb 'recruited' 146, 22
uuerden 'become' 89, 17a	uuard 'became' 19, 9a
burgo 'castles' 19, 10	búrg 'castle' 139, 10

11.444 The only exception.

[+voice]	[-voice]
uuólua 'wolves' II, 238, 1	uuólf 'wolf' II, 345, 2

might also be explained by a graphemic rule:

<u, C> --> / ___##

11.445 An analyst who accounts graphemicly for the <f/u> alternation in

uuólua 'wolves' II, 238, 1

and uuólf 'wolf' II.345.2

can drop the voicing rule. By this he not only simplifies the set of rules, but can also eliminate a 3-way allophonic categorization of lenes obstruents. Obstruents can be then only marked as fortis or lenis, not as either fortis, voiced lenis, or voiceless lenis. 11.446 Perhaps even more importantly, voice can be eliminated as a graphemicly significant feature. According to Penzl, Moulton and Clausen, fortition, and not voice should distinguish obstruent phonemes in de Nuptiis. Given this, an analyst might be cautious about making scribes mark as allophonic, features with which they were not already familiar with in their phonemic system. 11.447 The issue is of course not whether some 11th century monk kept his /v/ voiceless in

uuólua 'wolves' II.238.1.

He may very well have pronounced the fricative voiced. The question is, rather, whether he consciously marked two allophones in

uuólua 'wolves' II.238.1

and uuólf 'wolf' II.345.2.

If this is not likely, then perhaps it might be more plausible to propose that the alternation was graphemicly conditioned.

12.000 Dental Fricatives

	/z/	/s/
after s.i. VV	múse 'mice' II.438.13	héizen 'to be called' 133,18a
s.f.	mús 'mouse' II.438.13	hiez 'was called' 140.20
after s.i. V	uuésen 'to be' 61,3a	ézen 'eat' 105,7
s.f.	uuás 'was' 11,15a	uuáz 'what' 60.16
after s.i. liquid	also 'thus' 169,3	

	s.f.	nals	
		'not at all'	
		141,2	
after nasal	s.i.	unser	unzan
		'our'	'until'
		111.21	49,9
	s.f.	uns	unz
		'us'	'until'
		97.7a	92,11
after obst.	s.i.	sizzen	
		'to sit'	
		168.13	
	s.m.	zite	
		'times'	
		94,3a	
	s.f.	scaz	
		'treasure'	
		I,76,2	
Word Initial		sito	?
		'custom'	
		120.13	

12.111 A lenis=fortis opposition was posited for labial fricatives. In light of Nartey's frequency distributions then, one might hope to see the same opposition represented in the more natural dentals. Notker's syllable initial <s> after long vowels is reflected in Modern German by a lenis phoneme, while the graph <z> in this position parallels a fortis one. ex:

/z/	/s/
muse	heizen
'Mause'	'heiBen'
II,438,13	146.12

12.112 A similar contrast in Modern Swiss points to, according to Penzl:

"bei s auf Lenis im Inlaut, dagegen bei z auf Fortis(1968:145)."

12.211 The labial fortis fricative [f] was written double intervocalically after short vowels. ex:

tréffen 'meet' I,260,27

Without reasons to the contrary, one would hope to see the same pattern for [s], the corresponding dental one.

12.212 And, in part, one does. Although 'to eat' is always written with single <z> in de Nuptiis, about two thirds of the forms in the Notker Wortschatz have the double letters <zz>. ex:

ézen 'eat' 105.7

ézzen 'to eat' I,593.29

12.221 But why is this only carried out in part? An examination of those words consistently written with <zz> may provide an answer. 12.222 Joseph Greenberg analyzed 83 languages with africates. He concluded that:

"a language that has any africates among them has at least one in the dental-alveolar or alveo-palatal region(1965:30)."

What have traditionally been analyzed as africates, have been taken in this paper for stop-fricative combinations. Nevertheless, perhaps Greenberg's universal could be extended to also apply to such clusters.

12.223 Labial [f] was posited as coming syllable initially after labial [p]. ex:

ſpfer [opʃɛr] 'victim' 151.9a

One might expect the more natural dentals to behave the same. All modern Swiss dialects, according to Penzl, have [ts]. On the basis of these dialects, he posits word medial <z><z> after short vowels and <z> after consonantal sonorants as marking [ts]. ex:

sízzen 'to sit' 168.13

hérzen 'hearts' 124.4a

12.224 When marked with only a single <z> after short vowels then, perhaps [s] can contrast graphemicly with [ts]. ex:

ézen 'eat' 105.7

sízzen 'to sit' 168.13

And this might help account for why the dental fortis fricative is often not written double after short vowels, unlike the labial. ex:

tréffen 'meet' I,260.27

12.311 <z> and <s><s> both occur intervocalicly after short vowels. ex:

ézen 'eat' 105.7

guissiu 'certain' 99.05

Without evidence to the contrary, one would contrast them in fortition. Yet both graphs come down, in at least Modern German, as fortis. ex:

"gewisse" 'certain'

"essen" 'eat'

And anyway, the lenis dental is already marked in this position by single <s>. ex:

uuésen 'to be' 61.3a

12.312 In the dental stops, a 3-way d=t=tt opposition was proposed intervocalically after short vowels.

Lenis	Fortis	Stop Cluster
lída	síto	mitti
'song'	'custom'	'middle'
49.9	103.10	96.2a

Given this, perhaps one could set up a similar contrast for the dental fricatives too.

Lenis	Fortis	Stop Cluster
uuésen	ézen	guíssiú
'to be'	'eat'	'certain'
61.3a	105.7	99.05

12.313 The sequence <s><s> across a syllable boundary alternates with <s> syllable finally. ex:

guíssiú [guis\$~~s~~] 'certain' 99.05

guís [guis] 'certain' I,55.4

If this can be accounted for phonologically, then, according to the section on methods, perhaps it should be. A rule could disallow double consonants when not separated by a syllable boundary.

Double Consonant Deletion:

12.411 The sequences <z><z> and <s><s> do not occur at word

beginnings. <s> and <z> do. The two graphs contrast before vowels.
ex:

síd 'since' 43.19

zíte 'times' 94.3a

12.412 A stop-fricative combination was posited for the labials word initially, even though <p><f> does not occur in this position. ex:

flégest 'you care' 134.13

12.413 Without evidence to the contrary, and in light of Nartey's frequency distributions, one might assume this should imply the same type of cluster for the more natural dentals here. Unfortunately <z><z>, the graph cluster analyzed word medially as [ts], does not occur word initially. ex:

sízen [zit\$sen] 'sit' I.5.9

A comparison with Modern Alemannic dialects, however, points to, according to Penzl, a [ts] value for <z> word initially. ex:

zíte [tsii\$te] 'times' 94.3a

12.511 In addition to not appearing word initially, the cluster <z><z> does not occur word finally either. <z> and <s>, however, do. ex:

úns 'us' 97.7a

únz 'until' 92.11

12.512 In the section on labials, a stop-fricative cluster and two fricatives were posited word finally. ex:

/v/	/f/	/pf/
hóf [hov] court 87.16a	getráf [getraf] met II,215,27	chöpf [Xopf] head 74.1

12.521 At first glance, dental <z> and <s> seem to only show a 2-way contrast. Positioning <z> as [ts] however in

scáz 'treasure' I,76,

is supported by the word medial <z><z> sequence, which that word displays in the plural. ex:

scazza 'reassures' 62.13a

12.522 <s> then must denote a fricative. ex:

uuás 'was' 11.5a

guís 'certain' I,55,4

On the basis of the intervocalic forms of the fricatives above, however, one might assign the <s> in the two words a lenis and fortis value respectively.

[z]	[ss]
uuésen 'to be' 61.3a	guíssi 'certain' 99.05
[z]	[s]
uuás 'was' 11.5a	guís 'certain' I,55.4

12.531 The words

uuás 'Was' 60.16

and scáz 'Schatz' I,76.2

both show, in their Modern German glosses, contrast in the syllable codas. A similar contrast, according to Penzl, also reflected in all variants of today's Swiss German. Proposing that such an opposition did not exist in Medieval Alemannic is difficult, seeing that it must have also existed in Proto-Germanic.

12.532 If word final <z> must denote different obstruents however, one would like them to be as little different from each other as possible. It is perhaps partially for this reason, that Penzl posits

uuáz 'what' 60.16

as ending in fortis [s]. In this way, the violence done to Notker's otherwise more or less adequate writing system is lessened. Though <z> stands for both a single allophone and a cluster word finally, at least both values--like [f] and [pf] for word initial <f>--are fortis.

12.541 Phonological rules are more natural the more phonemes they affect and perhaps one could transfer this same form of evaluation to graphemic rules. The application of the above graphemic rule could be maximized by having it affect all double graph sequences bordered by a word boundary.

$$\langle G \rangle \rightarrow \emptyset \begin{cases} / \langle G \rangle _ \#\# \\ / \#\# _ \langle G \rangle \end{cases}$$

If so, then the same graphemic rule that generates

scáz 'treasure' I.76.2

from scázza 'treasures' 62.13a

could also account for why [ts] is written with a single letter word initially. ex:

zíte 'times' 94.3a

not **zzíte 'times' 94.3a

12.611 A comparison of the charts for the labial and dental fricatives shows a gap in the dentals. After liquids, the labial graphs contrast syllable initially. ex:

uuólua	hélfen
[uól\$va]	[hel\$fan]
'wolves'	'help'
II.238.1	I.265.22

Though only <f> is written word finally, this was analyzed as due to a graphemic rule. /v/ and /f/ were still allowed to contrast phonologically in:

uuólf	hálf
[uólv]	[half]
II.345.2	I.24.5

12.612 Strangely, however, in the most natural place of articulation, in the dentals, only the lenis graph <s> is written after liquids. ex:

áiso 'thus' 169.3

náls 'not at all' 141.2

uærßen 'verses' 51.3

uérß 'verse' 30.3

12.613 One of the guidelines of this paper was that phonemes should be able to occur in any sequence subject to sonority restrictions on syllables. But with the present set of rules, only the lenis dental fricative can generate manuscript spellings here. /s/ would surface as <z>. ex:

**uérz 'verse'

That <z> does not occur after liquids could of course be accounted for graphemically or by proposing a hole in the lexicon. Ideally, however,

a phonological explanation would, according to the section on methods, be preferred.

12.621 Dental stops lenite after homorganic nasals, or ~~was~~ as one might also describe them, homorganic sonorant stops. ex:
 min déil 'my part' 48,1

Lenition:

12.622 Liquids are [+coronal] in Modern Swiss (Penzl 1972:102). One might assume the same feature specification for /l,r/ in de Nuptiis. If so, then the lenition rule could be rewritten, allowing /s/ to lenite after liquids. The continuancy of the phoneme undergoing lenition could be looked upon as the feature limiting the conditioning factor.

Lenition:

[s] gets lenited after [l] and [r], and [t] after [n].

13.000 Back Continuants

	/h/	/X/
after s.i. [VV]	rúhôn 'raw Gen.' I.167,27	búche 'gut Dat.' II.68,24
s.f.	rúoh 'raw Nom.' I.167,28	búh 'gut Nom.' II.166,15
after s.i. [V]	slán 'to slay' I.105,9	sprácha 'language' 85.1
s.f.	sláh 'slay Imp.' I.373,9	spráh 'spoke' 47.21a
after s.i. liquid	0	uuerches 'of work'

137.4

s.f. 0

uuēr^h
'work'
6.6

after s.i. 0
nasal

stān^hches
'of stench'
24.1

s.f. 0

stāng
'stench'
14.2

after s.i. 0
obst.

blīc^hches
'of a glance'
67.10a

s.m. 0

chīnt
'child'
36.19

s.f. 0

blīg
'glance'
58.6a

Word hīna
Initial 'here'
10.1

chīnt
'child'
36.19

13.111 Between vowels, <ch> and the sequence <c><ch> contrast with each other and with <h>. ex:

gemā^hcho 'I make' 74.15

āc^hcher 'field' 97.22

nā^hhor 'nearer' 137.21a

13.112 <ch> and the velar graphs in the sequence <c><ch> correspond in Modern Alemannic dialects to fortis phonemes. In Modern English, the words

gesprō^hchen 162.2a

and rēc^hhent 5.1

can be glossed by, and related to 'spoken' and 'reckon'. Their velars descend from Proto-Germanic */k/.

13.113 One could propose that these phonemes shifted from fortis in Proto-Germanic, to lenis in Notker's day, back to fortis in Modern Swiss. It would not be as simple, however, as not positing any change in fortition. If <ch> is taken for the fortis fricative /X/, <c><ch>

can be analyzed as the fortis stop fricative combination /kX/.

13.211 <c><ch> does not appear syllable finally. Words that have the sequence across a syllable boundary are written with <g> when the obstruents are placed in final position. ex:

blic^hches 'of a glance' 67,10a

blig 'glance' 58,6a

13.212 This same <g> syllable finally parallels syllable initial <ch> after nasals. ex:

stanch^hes 'of stench' 24,11

stang 'stench' 14,2

13.213 When one rises up a few increments in sonority to the liquids, the pattern changes. <h>, and not <g>, is substituted syllable finally for syllable initial <ch>. ex:

uuer^hches 'of work' 137,4

uuerh 'work' 6,6

13.214 After vowels, the same pattern is repeated that occurs after the liquids. While <ch> is written word medially after vowels, <h> comes out word finally after them. ex:

b^hche 'gut Dat.' II,68,24

buh 'gut Nom.' II,166,15

In accounting for these alternations, one could begin with the vowels and work on down to the obstruents.

13.221 The <ch/h> alternation in

<h>	<ch>
b ^h uh 'gut Nom.' II,166,15	b ^h uches 'gut Dat.' II,68,24
uuer ^h h 'work' 6,6	uuer ^h ches 'of work' 137,4

looks suspiciously like the one in

<u>	<f>
houe	hof

'court Dat.'
102,3

uuólua
'wolves'
II,238,1

'court Nom.'
86,16a

uuólf
'wolf'
II,345,2

13.222 <u>, as a labial fricative, was restricted from word final position. Instead, it was argued that <f> could mark a [v] here:

<u,C> --> <f> / ___##

One might posit a similar graphemic rule for the velars:

<ch> --> <h> / ___##

13.223 Exceptions to this could be explained by analogy. <ch> could occur word finally once in

sprách 'spoke' 56.3

because that is the graph used in the infinitives. ex:

spréchen 'to speak' 81,12

13.231 An alternative, phonological explanation would of course, if possible, be preferred. One might expect it, however, to run into the same difficulties as for the <u/f> alternation in:

uuólua 'wolves' II,238.1

uuólf 'wolf' II,345.2

13.232 The <ch> in

uuérches 'of work' 137.4

was posited as a fortis [X]. The <h> in

uuérh 'work' 6.6

could not then be differentiated from it by a syllable final fortition rule.

Fortition:

$[-\text{sonorant}] \rightarrow [+ \text{fortis}] / ___\$$

Fortes obstruents cannot be made more fortis. And anyway, such a fortition rule would collapse the lenis/fortis contrast in:

/d/	/t/
t ^h od 'death' 118,22a	t ^h ot 'does' 129,9

13.233 The fortition could be restricted to velars. That would entail, however, positing place of articulation in the structural description, without mentioning a place feature in the conditioning factor. There is nothing velar about syllable final position.

13.234 A syllable final lenition rule would differentiate <ch> from <h> in:

uuérches 'of work' 137.4

uuérh 'work' 6,6

Like syllable final fortition however, it would obliterate the lenis=fortis opposition in

/d/	/t/
t ^h od 'death' 118.22a	t ^h ot 'does' 129.9

One wonders too, why a syllable boundary would condition lenition, especially when it triggers fortition after nasal sonority or lower. ex:

lám^hp 'lamb' II.239.9

13.235 Leaving <h>, one could concentrate on deriving <ch>. Again, however, the <ch> in

uuérches 'of work' 137.4

was interpreted as fortis [X]. A lenition rule affecting it would also apply to lenis allophones.

Lenition:

$[+sonorant] \rightarrow [-fortis] / [+sonorant] (\#) _$

The rule would obliterate the lenis/fortis opposition in:

/d/	/t/
tódes 'of death' 131.11	táten 'did' 122.14

13.241 To avoid this, perhaps a graphemic rule could allow <h> to mark [X] word finally. ex:

<ch> --> <h> /___##

Given this, one might then logically expect to see the nominative forms of

stánches 'of stench' 24.1

blíches 'of a glance' 67.110a

as **stánh 'stench'

**blích 'glance'.

Instead they come out as:

stáng 'stench' 14.2

blíg 'glance' 58.6a

An analyst would, according to the guidelines, prefer to account for this phonologically.

13.242 <k> was restricted from word final position. Instead, <g> was posited as marking both the fortis and lenis velar stops word finally. ex:

dísg 'table' 18.112

tág 'day' 170.1

13.243 To derive then the <g> in

stáng 'stench' 14.2

and blíg 'glance' 58.6a,

an analyst need perhaps only generate a velar stop--either [k] or [g]. One might assume, on analogy with the analyses of

stánches, underlying /stan\$Xes/ 'of stench' 24.1

blíches, underlying /blik\$Xes/ 'of a glance' 67.110a

/an underlying

stáŋg /stanX/ 'stench' 14.2

and blíg /blikX/ 'glance' 58.6a

If so, the simplest way the writer can find of doing this is sketched out below.

13.251 If nasals assimilate in place to a following obstruent, then underlying /stanX\$/ can change to [stáŋX\$].

Nasal Assimilation:

$$[+sonorant] \rightarrow [\alpha place] / _ (\$) [-sonorant]$$

$$[-continuant] \rightarrow [\alpha place]$$

13.252 The epenthesis rule could be ordered after nasal assimilation. If so, it can add a homorganic fortis stop between the nasal and fortis fricative, generating [stáŋkX\$].

Epenthesis:

$$\emptyset \rightarrow \left[\begin{array}{l} -continuant \\ -sonorant \\ +fortis \\ \alpha place \end{array} \right] / \left[\begin{array}{l} -continuant \\ +sonorant \\ \alpha place \end{array} \right] (\$) _ \left[\begin{array}{l} +continuant \\ +fortis \end{array} \right]$$

13.253 Both /blikX\$/ and /stáŋkX\$/ can then undergo a velar deletion rule, ordered after epenthesis. Syllable final velar obstruents could delete after other velar obstruents.

Velar Deletion:

$$\left[\begin{array}{l} -anterior \\ -sonorant \end{array} \right] \rightarrow \emptyset / \left[\begin{array}{l} -anterior \\ -sonorant \end{array} \right] _ \$$$

What would remain is /stáŋk\$/ and /blik\$/.

13.254 It is interesting to note that what the above rule deletes here is really just half of a stop-fricative combination (i.e. [X], from [kX]). These clusters could be analyzed as affricates, that is, as single phonemes. It would make the above process more complicated

however.

13.255 As mentioned earlier, word final velar stops, fortis and lenis, appear written with <g> word finally. ex:

dísg 'table' 18,12

Given this, the word final [k] in [stank\$] and [blik\$] could be represented with <g>. ex:

stáng 'stench' 24,1

blíg 'glance' 58.6a

13.311 The new rule posited, velar deletion, specifies [-anterior] in the conditioning factor. It can only be triggered by velars. If possible, one would like to extend the rule to the labials and dentals too. After all, the greater the application of a rule, the more natural the rule is.

13.312 So, for example, perhaps obstruents could be deleted syllable finally after dentals too. Unfortunately, that would lop off the [k] in

dísg [di:k] 'table' 18,12

if applicable after labial obstruents, the rule would delete the [f] in

chópf [Xopf] 'head' 74.1

13.313 So the deletion rule cannot be extended to other places of articulation. Perhaps, however, its application can still be maximized somewhat more in the velars.

13.312 Stop-fricative clusters were posited syllable initially and finally in the labials and dentals. ex:

	Labial	Dental
s.i.	flégest [pflegest] 'you care' 134,13	zíte [tsite] 'times' 94,3a
s.f.	chópf [Xopf] 'head' 74,1	scáz [skats] 'treasure' I,76,2

13.322 Such a combination, however, should not surface, at least syllable finally, in the velars. ex:

blícches [blik\$Xs] 'of a glance' 67,10a

but. blig [blik\$] 'glance' 58.6a

A rule prevents it.

Velar Deletion:

$[-\text{anterior}] \rightarrow \emptyset / [-\text{anterior}] _____\$$
 $[-\text{sonorant}]$

13.323 Could the conditioning factor of this rule be loosened, and its application extended? If it does not matter whether the syllable boundary is on the right or left, the rule could apply syllable initially too.

Velar Deletion:

$[-\text{anterior}] \rightarrow \emptyset / _____\$ [-\text{anterior}]$
 $[-\text{sonorant}]$

13.324 As [pf] and [ts] occur syllable initially and finally, so would [kX], in a sort of a negative parallel, not be generated syllable initially or finally.

13.411 With the discussion of fortis /X/ completed, the rest of this section can be devoted to the second, lenis back phoneme, commonly referred to as Germanic */h/. ex:

rúhon 'raw' I.167,27

13.412 If possible, one would of course wish to only describe Germanic */h/ here with the minimum amount of features needed to distinguish it from other phonemes, [-sonorant, -anterior, +continuant, -fortis]. The next few paragraphs can examine the graph alternations that this second phoneme undergoes and conditions. If a further feature specification proves necessary to make the rules for these alternations acceptable to the guidelines, then perhaps one should be added.

13.421 The Braune Grammar, for instance, gives arguments for just such an additional specification, either [+oral], as for the fricative

/χ/. or [-oral], as for the laryngeal /h/.

"Der Hauchlaut h im Wortinlaut zwischen Vokalen fällt bei N in vielen Wörtern nach kurzem Vokal aus, meist mit nachfolgender Kontraktion der beiden Vokale, z.B. zén (<zéhen '10')...

"Nach langem Vokal ist der Ausfall des h Ausnahme...In der Regel aber bleibt das h nach langem Vokal, der dann regelmäßig verkürzt wird. also sáhen (<sáhen)...

"Der Spirant h. vor dem die langen Vokale und Diphthonge nicht gekürzt werden...hat infolge seiner tief gutturalen Aussprache bei N das \hat{i} zu \hat{ie} , das \hat{u} zu \hat{uo} diphthongiert, z.B. líehte (<líhti 'leicht'), dúohta (<dúhta, Práet. zu dúnken), rúoh (<rúh 'rauh') aber flekt. rúher. (1975: 154. Anm. 8)."

13.422 The Braune Grammar speaks of "Laute" here, not phonemes. In a phonemic analysis then, an analyst needs to be careful. He runs the danger of interpreting into the grammar positions on issues which it does not raise. Nevertheless, if the grammar's observations are to be used, something must be interpreted out of them.

13.423 One might understand the above quote as positing two phonemes, a "Hauchlaut" /h/ and a "Spirant" /χ/. Such a fine phonemic distinction would have to be made if, using Penzl's method, one could contrast /h/ and / / in minimal pairs.

13.424 As far as the writer can tell, however, syllable finally after vowel sequences, the grammar lets [χ] condition diphthongization. ex:

rúoh <rúuh 'raw' I.167,28

Everywhere else [h] is posited; after single vowels, ex:

zén <zéhen 'ten' I.115,15

and syllable initially after double ones, ex:

rúhon <rúuhon 'raw' I.167,27.

The "Hauchlaut" and "Spirant" are in complimentary distribution.

13.431 No analyst would deny that there could have been allophones in different positions. Before the system can generate allophones, however, it must agree on a phoneme.

13.433 Penzl was perhaps the first to recognize this, and impose phonemic rigor on his analysis of Notker's writings. He also strove for symmetry:

"Bei den Geräuschlauten stehen nach Notkers Orthographie die Lenisspiranten f(u) s h den Fortisspiranten f(f) z ch gegenüber(1968:149)."

<h> then, as a "Spirant", would mark a fricative /χ/, and not the glide /h/. Penzl's classification provides a base for further

discussion.

13.511 One of the guidelines set out in the section on methods was that phonemes should be able to occur in any environment. It was argued that restrictions later placed on phonemes before the application of rules could not specify place features. In addition, rules themselves could not specify a place features in the SD or SC without also mentioning one in the conditioning factor. Keeping these two things in mind, one might begin this next section by contrasting <ch> and <h> syllable initially after vowels. ex:

	/ʃ/	/x/
s.i.	rúh ^o n	bú ^h ch ^e
VV	"raw"	"gut Dat."
	I.167,27	II.68,24

Both /X/ and / / should then be able to occur here.

13.512 Syllable finally the contrast, at least in graphs, disappears. ex:

	/ʃ/	/x/
s.f.	rú ^h ch	bú ^h
VV	"raw Nom."	"gut Nom."
	I.167,28	II.166,15

Since <ch> was restricted from word final position, however, the lack of contrast could be explained as graphemically conditioned. Certainly the diphthonged */uu/ in

rú^hch [rú^hʃ] 'raw Nom.' I.167,28

could help establish a contrast in the consonant it precedes with the one after the undiphthonged */uu/ in

bú^h [bú^hx] 'gut Nom.' II.166,15.

13.513 The present fortition rule should account for the lack of contrast after obstruents. ex:

blí^hch^es [blík^hʃəs] 'of a glance' 67.10a

The process used to derive

stá^hng [stá^hŋk] 'stench' 14,2

from underlying /stanX/ could help explain why neither velar fricative occurs syllable finally after nasals.

13.521 That only <h> occurs syllable finally after liquids, could again only be graphemically significant. ex:

uuerh 'work' 6.6

But should this be taken as evidence for both [] and [X] occurring here? Unfortunately, the only examples of syllable final <h> after liquids are in complimentary distribution with syllable initial fortis [X]. ex:

uuerches [uer\$Xəs] 'of work' 137.4

13.522 Can this be explained phonologically? A broader syllable final fortition rule could collapse [X] with [] here:

Fortition:

$[-\text{sonorant}] \rightarrow [+ \text{fortis}] / \text{---} \#$

Such a rule however would also obliterate the t=d contrast in:

	/d/	/t/
s.f.	t [^] od	t [^] uot
	'death'	'does'
	I.8.8	I.9.26

13.523 A simpler solution might be to reanalyze /x/ as /h/. If [oral] is accepted as a manner and not a place feature, /h/, as a laryngeal, can be restricted, before the application of rules, from bordering consonants. ex:

**[+oral] [+consonantal]

**[+consonantal] [+oral]

13.611 As quoted before, Braune observed that <h> often drops out intervocalically "nach kurzem Vokal". ex:

zēn[^]*[zehen] 'ten' I.155.15

13.612 J. Schatz is more specific(1927:242). <h> gets deleted intervocalically after short vowel, only if followed by a closed syllable. ex:

slān[^]*[slāhen] 'to slay' I.105.9

but slāho 'I slay' II.618.3

Deviant forms he explained by analogy. ex:

slāhen 'to slay' I.34.8

13.613 Lloyd. in a paper devoted to Notker's <h>, agreed with Schatz. Lloyd went on further. to speculate on the psychological motivation for the exceptions. Notker,

"who was in other ways out of tune with the times(1957:122)", sensed on analogy with

sláho 'I slay' II.618,3

that an <h> belonged in

slán 'to slay' I.105,9.

So he often wrote one in:

"taking pains to preserve the 'correct' selling-pronunciation and combat the 'sloppy colloquial speech'(1957:112)." ex:

sláhen 'to slay' I.34.8

13.621 The aim of Lloyd's argument is admittedly psychological. not phonological. Nevertheless. the graphemic alternation he and Schatz describe takes place in a specific environment. It can be integrated into a rule. How simple and natural that rule is, will depend on how <h> is interpreted phonemically:

1) as the fricative /x/:

Intervocalic Deletion:

$$\left[\begin{array}{l} -\text{fortis} \\ +\text{continuant} \\ -\text{anterior} \end{array} \right] \rightarrow \emptyset / \left[-\text{consonantal} \right] _ \left[-\text{consonantal} \right] \left[+\text{consonantal} \right]$$

2) or as the laryngeal /h/:

Intervocalic Deletion:

$$\left[-\text{oral} \right] \rightarrow \emptyset / \left[-\text{consonantal} \right] _ \left[-\text{consonantal} \right] \left[+\text{consonantal} \right] \#$$

13.622 As can be seen above, the rule deleting /χ/ requires more symbols. In addition, the conditioning factor in both rules does not specify place of articulation. Deleting [h] instead of [χ] relieves an analyst of trying to account for why only the velar lenis fricative is lost here, and not the dental or labial one. ex:

wésen [wézɛn] 'to be' 105,7
 hóuen [hovɛn] 'courts' II,349,3

/h/, as the only non-oral phoneme, need not be specified by place of articulation.

13.623 It is perhaps with some of these ideas in mind, that the Braune Grammar calls <h> here a "Hauchlaut", and Lloyd writes:

"Intervocalic h is generally assumed to be an aspirate(1957:110)."

13.711 After sequences of two non-consonantals, syllable initial Germanic */h/ conditions deletion. ex:

sahen [sahɛn] < OHG [saa\$hen] 'saw' I,14,19

13.712 One could choose between two rules:

1) one conditioned by [χ]:

Vowel Deletion:

$[-consonantal] \rightarrow \emptyset / [-consonantal] _ (\#) \left[\begin{array}{l} +continuant \\ -anterior \\ -fortis \\ -sonorant \end{array} \right] [-consonant]$

2) or one conditioned by [h]:

Vowel Deletion:

$[-consonantal] \rightarrow \emptyset / [-consonantal] _ (\#) [-oral] [-consonantal] _$

13.713 The rule with [h] uses less symbols. And as it prevents a string of four phonemes, none of which are oral consonants, perhaps it has some natural justification.

13.811 Syllable final Germanic */h/ lowers the second element of a sequence of high vowels. ex:

[^]ruoh [ruəh] < OHG *[ruuh] 'raw Nom.' I.167.28

[^]liehti [liəhtii] < OHG [liihstii] I.203.12

13.812 As a type of conditioning factor Penzl posits:

"für die spätere Lenis (germ. *h) eine stärker velare Aussprache als für die ahd. fortis h(h) (1968:139)."

Braune echoes this, proposing "eine tief gutturale Aussprache (1975:154, Anm. 9)" for Notker's "Spirant h". And Lloyd too speaks of a "tautosyllabic (spirant) h (1957:108)" causing diphthongization.

13.821 Germanic *h for Penzl is phonemically /χ/ in Notker's Alemannic. Perhaps by "starker velar" Penzl means that [χ] was here "further back" than [X]. If so, that is certainly worthy of note. It is the nature of fortis, not lenis, phonemes to be more peripheral, further back in this case.

13.822 Braune sees "eine tief gutturale Aussprache" pulling down the second elements in [ii] and [uu] into [iə] and [uə]. Empirically this seems correct, but why must the "tief gutturale Aussprache" be that of an oral fricative? Could not just the "lowness" of a following phoneme lower the second halves of high vowel sequences here?

13.823 /h/, if [-oral], is so "low", that it is not even integrated into the rest of the oral system. A rule conditioning lowering after it could be written:

Lowering:

$$[-\text{consonantal}] \rightarrow [-\text{hi}] / [-\text{consonantal}] \text{ --- } [-\text{oral}] \#$$

13.824 / / in contrast, if a velar, is quite possibly [+high]. As [-anterior], however, it could perhaps pull back the second [+anterior] vowel in:

[^]liehti **[liəχstii], from underlying /liiχstii/ 'light I.203.12

One wonders, however, how a [+high, -anterior] fricative would lower a [+high, -anterior] vowel in underlying **/ruuχ/. ex:

ruoh **[ruəχ], from underlying **/ruuχ/ 'raw Nom.' I.167.28

13.911 How Germanic */h/ is analyzed in Notker's writings could of course have an effect on how the phoneme is interpreted in Old High German as a whole. Penzl realized this, linking rules that Notker's

2) No sequence can^{occur} whenever possible, at a syllable boundary if it does not also come at a word boundary.

3) **[-consonantal] + [-consonantal]

14.122 Syllabification Rule

The template is expanded maximally to the left and syllables do not overlap (i.e. onsets are maximized).

14.131 Phonemic Inventory

[-consonantal]

	[+anterior]		[-anterior]	
	[+rnd]	[-rnd]		
[+hi]	y	i		u
[-hi, -lo]	ɘ	e		o
[+lo]		æ		a

[+consonantal, +sonorant]

l=[+lateral]

r=[-lateral, +continuant]

n=[-continuant, +coronal]

m=[-continuant, -coronal]

[-sonorant]

	[+anterior]		[-anterior]			
	[-coronal]	[+coronal]	[-anterior]			
	[+f]	[-f]	[+f]	[-f]		
[-cont]	p	b	t	d	k	g
[+cont]	f	v	s	z	X	h

14.132 Additional Feature Specifications

[-fortis, +cont, -son] --> [-oral]

[+ant, -cor, -son] --> [+rnd]

[+hi, -cons, -ant] --> [+rnd]

[+son, +cont, +cons] --> [+cor]

14.141 Phonological Restrictions

** [+stress] [+stress]

** [αconsonantal] [αconsonantal] [αconsonantal] [αconsonantal]

~~** [-consonantal] [-consonantal]
+hi +hi
αanterior -αanterior
+stress~~

** [+consonantal] [+consonantal]
+sonorant +sonorant
αcontinuant αcontinuant
βlateral βlateral

** \$ [+consonantal] [+consonantal]
+sonorant +sonorant

14.142 Phonological Rules

Final Vowel Lowering:

$$[-\text{consonantal}] \rightarrow [-\text{hi}] / [+ \text{consonantal}] _ \#$$

Preconsonantal Vowel Reduction:

$$[-\text{consonantal}] \rightarrow \begin{bmatrix} -\text{anterior} \\ -\text{hi} \\ -\text{lo} \\ -\text{round} \end{bmatrix} / \left\{ \begin{array}{l} [-\text{consonantal}] _ \\ [+ \text{stress}] _ \\ [+ \text{consonantal}] _ [+ \text{consonantal}] \end{array} \right.$$

Fronting:

$$[-\text{consonantal}] \rightarrow [+ \text{anterior}] / _ (\infty (\#) (\infty [-\text{consonantal}] [+ \text{anterior}]$$

Rounding:

$[-\text{consonantal}] \rightarrow [+round] / [+round]$

Vowel Assimilation 1:

$\begin{bmatrix} \alpha \text{ hi} \\ +\text{lo} \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow \begin{bmatrix} \text{matrix} \end{bmatrix} / \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \text{ hi} \\ +\text{stress} \\ \text{matrix} \end{bmatrix}$

Vowel Assimilation 2:

$\begin{bmatrix} \alpha \text{ hi} \\ -\text{lo} \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow \begin{bmatrix} \text{matrix} \end{bmatrix} / \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \text{ hi} \\ -\text{lo} \\ +\text{stress} \\ \text{matrix} \end{bmatrix}$

Portition:

$[-\text{sonorant}] \rightarrow [+fortis] / \begin{matrix} [-\text{sonorant}] \\ [-\text{sonorant}] (\#) \\ \begin{bmatrix} \text{nasal} \\ \text{sonority} \\ \text{or lower} \end{bmatrix} \# \end{matrix}$

Epenthesis:

$\emptyset \rightarrow \begin{bmatrix} -\text{continuant} \\ +\text{fortis} \\ \alpha \text{ place} \end{bmatrix} / \begin{bmatrix} -\text{continuant} \\ +\text{sonorant} \\ \alpha \text{ place} \end{bmatrix} \# \begin{bmatrix} +\text{fortis} \\ +\text{continuant} \end{bmatrix}$

Dental Lenition:

$\left[\begin{array}{l} +\text{coronal} \\ \alpha\text{continuant} \end{array} \right] \rightarrow [-\text{fortis}] / \left[\begin{array}{l} +\text{coronal} \\ +\text{sonorant} \\ \alpha\text{continuant} \end{array} \right] (\#) \text{---}$

Nasal Assimilation

$\left[\begin{array}{l} +\text{sonorant} \\ -\text{continuant} \end{array} \right] \rightarrow [\alpha\text{place}] / \text{---} (\#) \left[\begin{array}{l} -\text{sonorant} \\ \alpha\text{place} \end{array} \right]$

Stop Deletion:

$\left[\begin{array}{l} -\text{sonorant} \\ -\text{continuant} \end{array} \right] \rightarrow \emptyset / [-\text{sonorant}] \text{---} (\#) [-\text{sonorant}]$

Double Consonant Deletion:

$\left[\begin{array}{l} -\text{sonorant} \\ \alpha\text{place} \\ \beta\text{continuant} \end{array} \right] \rightarrow \emptyset / \left[\begin{array}{l} -\text{sonorant} \\ \alpha\text{place} \\ \beta\text{continuant} \end{array} \right]$

Velar Deletion:

$[-\text{anterior}]$
 $[-\text{sonorant}] \rightarrow \emptyset$

$\$$ — $[-\text{anterior}]$
 $[-\text{sonorant}]$

$[-\text{anterior}]$
 $[-\text{sonorant}]$ — $\$$

Intervocalic h-Deletion:

$[-\text{oral}] \rightarrow \emptyset / [-\text{consonantal}] _ [-\text{consonantal}] [+ \text{consonantal}] \#$

Vowel Deletion:

$[-\text{consonantal}] \rightarrow \emptyset / [-\text{consonantal}] _ (\$) [-\text{oral}] [-\text{consonantal}]$

Lowering:

$[-\text{consonantal}] \rightarrow [-\text{hi}] / [-\text{consonantal}] _ [-\text{oral}] \#$

14.143 Rule Orderings:

The order in which these rules have been listed is largely arbitrary. Some rule orderings are needed however.

1) Epenthesis > Fortition:

[v] is made fortis syllable finally after nasal sonority or lower. ex:

fínf [vimf], underlying /vimv/ 'five' I.66.26If

If, by Epenthesis, a [p] is then inserted after the [m], both /f/ and /v/ will generate [mpf]. ex:

gelámf [gəlampf], underlying /gelamf/ 'suited' I.556.6

The phonological motivation for the <n>=<m> graph contrast would be obliterated.

2) Nasal Assimilation > Epenthesis:

An /ŋ/ phoneme was not posited. Instead a velar allophone of /n/ can be generated before velars. ex:

stang [staŋk], from [staŋkX], from [staŋX], from underlying /stanX/ 'stench' 14.2

Epenthesis beforehand would produce *[stantX], and this would not generate the manuscript spelling.

3) Epenthesis > Velar Deletion:

Otherwise the [X] would not delete in:

stang [staŋk], from [staŋkX] 'stench' 14.2.

And again, this is not reflected in the spelling.

4) Nasal Assimilation > Dental Lenition:

Otherwise the dental would not lenite after a labial [m] in:

rúmnda [runda], from [runta], from underlying /rumta/ 'praised' 129.17

5) Dental Lenition > Fortition:

Otherwise the dental would not be made fortis in :

fant *[fant], from *[fand], underlying */fand/ or */fant/ 'found' 118,11

14.200 Graphemic Component

A graphemic component, sketched out in the section on methods(3.400), might parallel the phonological component. In the graphemic inventory, groups of features could be mapped onto graphs, much in the same way as phonemes in the phonemic inventory are mapped onto groups of features. In the following set of graphemic rules, graphs could then undergo much the same process that groups of features do in their rules.

14.211 Graphemic Inventory:

[p] → <p>	[f] → <f>
[t] → <t>	[s] → <z>
[k] → <k>	[ç] → <ch>

[b] → ⟨b⟩ [v] → ⟨u⟩

[d] → ⟨d⟩ [z] → ⟨s⟩

[g] → ⟨g⟩ [h] → ⟨h⟩

[m] → ⟨m⟩ [l] → ⟨l⟩

[n] → ⟨n⟩ [r] → ⟨r⟩

[ɑ̃] → ⟨ɑ̃⟩ [õ] → ⟨õ⟩

[ɛ̃] → ⟨ɛ̃⟩ [ũ] → ⟨ũ⟩

[ĩ] → ⟨ĩ⟩ [y] → ⟨ĩ, ũ⟩

[æ̃] → ⟨ɛ̃⟩ [∅] → ⟨õ, ẽ, õ⟩

[ĩ] → ⟨ĩ⟩

[ỹy] → ⟨ĩũ⟩

[ĩũ] → ⟨ɑ̃⟩

[é̃[ẽ, ĩ]] → ⟨é̃⟩

[ó̃[õ, ũ]] → ⟨ó̃⟩

[æ̃æ̃] → ⟨ɑ̃⟩

[ɑ̃ɑ̃] → ⟨ɑ̃⟩

$[i\bar{a}] \rightarrow \langle \overset{\circ}{i}e \rangle$ $\left. \begin{array}{l} [V, -hi] [u] \\ [V, +lo] [o] \end{array} \right\} \rightarrow \langle \overset{\circ}{o}u \rangle$
 $[y\bar{a}] \rightarrow \langle \overset{\circ}{u}e \rangle$
 $[\bar{u}] \rightarrow \langle \overset{\circ}{u}e \rangle$

$\left. \begin{array}{l} [V, -hi] [i] \\ [V, +lo] [e] \end{array} \right\} \rightarrow \langle \overset{\circ}{e}i \rangle$

$\left. \begin{array}{l} [V, -hi] [y] \\ [V, +lo] [\emptyset] \end{array} \right\} \rightarrow \langle \overset{\circ}{o}u \rangle$

$\left[\begin{array}{l} -\text{consonantal} \\ +\text{stress} \end{array} \right] \rightarrow \alpha \wedge / \left[\begin{array}{l} -\text{consonantal} \\ \alpha \text{ lower than} \\ \text{preceding vowel} \end{array} \right]$

+1 = circumflex
 -1 = accent

14.212 Graphemic Rules:

$\langle p \rangle \rightarrow \emptyset / _\# _ \langle f \rangle$ ex:

flégest [pfleg~~ə~~st] 'you care' 134.13

$\langle ch \rangle \rightarrow \langle h \rangle / _\# _$ ex:

sprácha [sprach~~a~~] 'languages' 85.1

spráh [sprax] 'spoke' 47.21a

$\langle u, c \rangle \rightarrow \langle f \rangle / _\# _$ ex:

uuólva [uólva] 'wolves' II.238.1

uuólv [uólv] 'wolf' II.345.2

< Graph> -> ø / < Graph> __ ##
/ ## __ < Graph> ex:

scázza [skatsa] 'treasures' 62,13a

scáz [skats] 'treasure' I,76,2

<k> -> <g> / __ ## ex:

fískēn [fiskən] 'fish Dat. Pl.' 67,6

físg [fisk] 'fish Nom. Sg.' I,167,28

<k> -> <c> / __ <a.o.u> ex:

fískēn [fiskēn] 'fish Dat. Pl.' 67,6

físcā [fiskā] 'fish Acc. Pl.' II,243,25

<k> -> <q> / __ <u><V> ex:

quís [kuis] 36.21

14.311 In phonological reconstruction. Lass argues:

"the 'odder' the system we construct, the more argumentative support it needs(1984:155)."

Perhaps the same logic could apply in the reconstruction of spelling practices. The 'odder' the graphemic component an analysis would posit, perhaps the closer the methods that led to such an analysis should be examined. Just as phonological rules are judged by how simple and natural they are, so might one also evaluate a set of graphemic rules according to their simplicity and naturalness.

14.321 A phonological rule is simpler the less symbols it uses. Perhaps, along this line, a graphemic rule should be so too. That <k> becomes <g> word finally would then be simpler than having the graph turn to <q> before <u>+ a vowel graph. ex:

<k> -> <g> / __ ## ex:

físg 'fsh' I,1167,28

<k> -> <q> / __ <u><V> ex:

quís 'certain' 36,21

The first rule uses one less symbol.

14.331 But although simpler, can one really say that the first rule is more natural? "Ease of articulation", or something like it, is supposed to motivate most natural rules in phonology. What, however, could motivate a graphemic rule?

14.332 Certainly, in the case of de Nuptiis, the influence of Latin, the language the scribes read out loud and wrote in, comes to mind. Notker's graphemic system was built on Latin, or perhaps some other German system originally based on Latin. Fitting an Alemannic phonological system into a Romance alphabet could understandably lead to problems. Most recently, for instance, Clausen has argued:

"the primary reason for Notker's failure to indicate affricates or rounded front vowels was the lack of suitable orthographic symbols at his disposal(1980:367)."

14.341 Scribes, however, did not just write and speak the Latin alphabet, but Latin words; becoming familiar, in time, not only with the Latin letters, but also with their patterns of distribution in words. They must have also become acquainted with a graph's different phonemic, if perhaps not phonetic, values, if these were different in different positions in words.

14.342 If Notker's Alemannic writing system is considered the daughter system of a Latin parent one, a following line of argument might be expressed universally.

14.351 So, for example, if the Latin of Notker's day marked two labial fricatives /v/ and /f/, only one occurred, and was written word finally.

w.i.	w.m.	w.f.
<u> uersus 'verse' 3.6	fauores 'blessings' 51.18	∅
<f> fecit 'did' 83.15	deificationis 'godly ones' 115.11	

<u>, when at a word end, could only mark a vowel. ex:

-

~~u~~ CORU

14.352 One might see in this a practice carried over into Notker's Alemannic writing system. Conceivably, only <f> and not also <u> was allowed to mark obstruents word finally. <u> here could then be reserved, as in Latin, for marking vowels. ex:

-

u

Word initially and medially, however, the two labial fricatives were left to contrast graphemically in Medieval Latin. ex:

w.i.	w.m.	w.f.
<u> uilo 'much' # 151,17	uuolua 'wolves' II,238,1	uuolf 'wolf' II,345,2
<f> flēgest 'you tend' 134,13	hēlfen 'help' I.265,22	hālf 'helped' I,24,5

14.361 According to the dtv-Atlas zur detuschen Sprache, Medieval Latin /k/, written as <c>, palatized before front vowels. It was then borrowed, at least eventually into Modern German, as [ts]. ex:

crucem 'cross' Lat. Acc. †

Kreuz 'cross' MG †

14.362 Alemannic speakers, in order to understand their own language, had to be able to differentiate between [k] and [ts]. One wonders then what kind of effect this Latin palatization might have had on a similar, though purely graphemic, practice in de Nuptiis. <c> alternates with <z> before front vowels, and <k> before non-front ones. ex:

<e.i>	<a.o.u>
cinken 'prong' 91,21	zinkun 'prong' 95,8
cōt 'god' 41,9	kōt 'god' 163,18a

14.363 An analyst is curious too, what eventual effect the palatization of Latin /k/ could have had on the spellings of the German velar in:

fīskēn 'fish Dat. Pl.' 67,6

fīscā 'fish, Acc. Pl.' II,243,25

fīsg 'fish Nom. pl.' I,167,28

/k/ was marked by <c> in classical Latin. ex:

culpa 'debts' Lat. Nom. Pl.

If the palatization of Latin /k/ spread, so that the phoneme retained its original value only before non-front vowels, then perhaps this could be cited in helping to account for why <c> does not mark German [k] in all the above three forms of Alemannic 'fish'.

14.371 The sequence <q><u> in Latin marks what one might assume was [kw] in the Latin of Saint Gall. ex:

quinta 'five Lat.' 147,10

One might see this at the root of a similar practice in de Nuptiis:

<k> -> <q> / <u><V> ex:

quís 'certain' 36,21

14.381 The 3 rules

<p> -> 0 / ## <f> ex:

ópfer 'Opfer' 151,9a

flégest 'pflegst' 134,13

<ch> -> <h> / ##

sprácha 'Sprachen' 85,1

spráh 'sprach' 47,21a

< Graph> -> / < Graph> ##
/ ## < Graph>

scazza 'Schätze' 62,113a

scaz 'Schatz' I.76,2

were posited on diachronic support--support reflected in the Modern German glosses of words they affect.

14.382 In addition however, the rules could also work to make Notker's Alemannic script more latinate. The sequence <p><f> does not occur word initially in Latin, nor <ch> word finally. Latin double letters, although possible word medially, do not come up next to a word boundary. ex:

ossis 'bone Lat. Gen.'

os 'bone Nom.'

14.391 Of course all motivational factors need not necessarily be Latin based. The sequence <c><c> occurs only once in de Nuptiis, in the word for 'bell'.

gloccun 'bell' 64,16

This may very well reflect Irish scribal tradition on an originally

Celtic word In addition, the writer's knowledge of paleography is too weak to speculate on any motivation for the rules placing diacritics. 14.392 In light of the preceding discussion, however, one might argue that an analysis of the graphemic rules could benefit from an investigation of Latin.

14.393 In addition, some of the graphemic rules proposed were not arrived at through internal reconstruction, but solely with the guidelines proposed for manuscript analysis. ex:

<u,C> -> <f> / _ ##

<k> -> <q> / _ <u><V>

<k> -> <g> / _ ##

<k> -> <c> / _ <a,o,u>

If these rules, through a comparison with Latin, could be analyzed as natural, then perhaps that could be cited when softening an attack on the methods that proposed them.

14.411 Perhaps the most interesting phonological rule, from a historical standpoint, is the fortition.

Fortition:

While the "Anlautgesetz" will be treated in detail later, the greater bulk of this obstruent summary too has been devoted to discussing it, and the syllable final fortition.

14.412 In summarizing Notker's graph alternations, N.E. Collinge notes that stops and labial fricatives followed an "Anlautgesetz". Nevertheless:

"sibilants were not varied(1985:121)".

The lenis dental fricative in

unde s^hingen 'and to sing' 111,14

does not get written as fortis <z> after obstruents. ex:

daz s^hingen 'that we sing' 115,9a

not, **daz zingen

14.421 Why the exception? One could try to explain it graphemically. Word initial <z> marks a stop-fricative cluster [ts]. ex:

z^hite 'times' 94,3a

Perhaps Notker did not feel it should also denote just a fricative in

**daz z^hingen 'that we sing'

14.422 While this may very well be true, a similar inhibition did not prevent the monk from giving <f>, another fricative graph, a double value word initially. ex:

fl^hegest [pfleg st] 'you care' 134.13

uu^has f^hilo [uas filo] 'was much' 23.2

14.431 Perhaps the choice of <s> in

daz s^hingen 'that we sing' 115,9a

could be accounted for phonologically.

14.432 The "Anlautgesetz" could be restricted from affecting the dental fricatives. But since the fortition applies to both the labial fricatives and dental stops, can one seriously entertain this? An alternate explanation draws support from Middle High German.

14.441 Stops and the labial fricatives collapse syllable finally in the Middle High period. ex:

rades	rates
'of a wheel'	'of council'

rat	rad
'wheel'	'council'

14.442 Dental fricatives, on the other hand, retain contrast here, even though their lenis/fortis opposition is lost too. ex:

ez	es
'it Nom.'	'it Gen.'

14.443 Most scholars see a contrast in place here, and Penzl finds no

reason why this opposition did not also exist in the Old High period. Its exact nature is even a topic of debate:

"Wir können nicht sicher sein, ob es eine Zungenspitzenartikulation bei /s/ war, die schibelantenartig gegenüber einem /z/ des Zungenblattes wirkte oder der Artikulationsunterschied vielleicht in erster Linie auf einer retroflektierten des /s/ gegenüber einer nichtretroflexen von /z/ beruhte (Penzl 1974:72)."

14.451 de Nuptiis retains the lenis <s> graph for the lenis dental fricative—even when made fortis, for example, by the "Anlautgesetz" after obstruents:

daz singen [das\$sin\$gən] 'that we sing' 115,9a

Classical Middle High German retains "lenis" <s> too, even when made fortis syllable finally. ex:

'es' [es] 'it Gen.'

14.452 The "Anlautgesetz" and the Middle High German "Auslautverhärtung" are both fortitions. Could one perhaps parallel the use in de Nuptiis of <s> in a fortis environment with a similar phenomena in Classical Middle High. In both languages then, <s> could also mark a z=s opposition in place, if not always one in fortition.

14.461 In a way then, perhaps the graphemic realization of the "Anlautgesetz" could be seen as confirming a guideline. For only two of the six sets of obstruents—for the [+coronal] and [-anterior] continuants—could one cite diachronic evidence supporting more than just a lenis≠fortis opposition. Modern German, according to Benware, has an X+h, that is a [+fortis +oral]≠[-fortis -oral] opposition, not simply a X≠Y, or [+fortis]≠[-fortis] one (1984:42). And in Classical Middle High German, an s≠z opposition in place, in addition to one in fortition, could account for why syllable final dental fricatives, though made fortis, were still differentiated graphemically. ex:

ez 'it Acc.'

es 'it Gen.'

14.462 Coincidentally, it is also only in these two obstruent sets, in the [+coronal] and [-anterior] continuants, that the "Anlautgesetz" is not marked. After obstruents, <s> and <h> do not come out as the "fortes" graphs <z> and <ch>, but instead remain unchanged. ex:

daz sîngen 'that we sing' 115,9a

sînes hûses 'of his house' 148,22

14.511 The present syllable final fortition rule is of course not the only one possible:

Syllable Final Fortition:

[sonorant] → [+fortis] / [nasal
sonority
or lower] — \$

Penzl, for instance, proposes a different "Auslautverhärtung". In the fricatives:

"Die Opposition der beiden Phonemreihen besteht...nur bei den Zahnlauten auch im Auslaut (/s/ /z/), wo der labiale und der velare Fortislaut (/f/ /X/) vorkommt(1972:102)."

Likewise, in the labial and velar stops:

"Im Auslaut steht zum Unterschied von den Reibelauten das Lenisphonem (kalb, tag, fleisch), bei dem Fortisallophone anzunehmen sind(1972:104)."

14.512 Non-dentals then, become fortis syllable finally. One might write a rule:

Penzl "Auslautverhartung":

[-sonorant
-coronal] → [+fortis] / — \$

14.521 Certainly, as Penzl points out, non-dental obstruent graphs do not contrast syllable finally. The six obstruent charts in this paper, contrasting lenis and fortis stops and fricatives, have only served to confirm this observation. ex:

[+continuant]	[-continuant]
uúib 'woman' 14,5	tág 'day' 170,1
hóf 'court' 87,16a	spráh 'spoke' 47,21a

14.531 If they do not contrast, however, syllable final non-dental obstruents do, at least in the labial stops, alternate. ex:

/b/

after s.i. uuérben
liquid 'recruit'
161.12

s.f. uuárb
'recruited'
146,222

after s.i. lémbir
nasal 'lambs'
486.6

s.f. lámp
'lamb'
II.239.9

And this alternation parallels a similar alternation in the dentals.

/d/

after s.i. uuérden
liquid 'become'
89.17

s.f. uuárd
'became'
19.9a

after s.i. fínden
nasal 'find'
109.18a

s.f. fánt
'found'
118.11

14.532 The "lenis" velar stop graph <g> appears instead of <k> word finally after all graphs, whether sonorant or obstruent. ex:

tág 'day' 170,1

sáng 'sang' 109,1

dísg 'table' 18,12

Given this, the <g> here might be best analyzed as graphemicly conditioned.

13.533 If one accepts this, however, then syllable finally, at least in the stops, there is a pattern corresponding to gradations in sonority. The "lenis" graph, when not otherwise graphemicly conditioned, can only come after liquid sonority or higher. Penzl's "Auslautverhärtung" would fail to capture this generalization.

14.541 A possible spin-off of it, however, could take into account the scholar's observations on syllable final fricatives.

14.551 Syllable initial <h> and <ch> are both written <h> syllable finally. ex:

/h/	/X/
s.i. rúh ^h 'raw Gen.' I,167.27	búch ^h 'gut Dat.' II,68,24
s.f. rú ^h 'raw Nom>' I,167.28	bú ^h 'gut Nom.' II,166,15

14.552 Penzl sees here two oral velar fricatives, /X/ and / /, collapsing syllable finally to [X], represented by <h>. ex:

/X/	/ /
rú ^h 'raw Nom.' I,167.28	bú ^h 'gut Nom.' II,166,15

The analysis would require a rule ordering, however. The lowering of [uu] and [ii] to [uə] and [iə] must take place before both fricatives fall together through fortition.

14.553 This paper interpreted the <h> in

rú^h 'raw Nom.' I,167.28

as a laryngeal /h/. In doing so it releases an analyst from positing the above rule ordering. In both analyses, however, at least oral [-anterior] obstruent continuants do not contrast syllable finally.

14.561 In the other non-dental fricatives, in the labials, obstruents do not contrast syllable finally either. ex:

/v/	/f/
s.i. uuólua 'wolves' II,238,1	hélfen 'help' I,265,22
s.f. uuólf 'wolf' II,345,2	hálf 'helped' I,24.5

14.562 Only after nasals is contrast carried into syllable final position--and then not in the fricative graphs, but only in the nasal graphs that precede them. ex:

/v/	/f/
s.i. fínue 'five' I,197.29	gelímpflichéro 'suited' 92.20
s.f. fínf 'five' 13.21	gelámf 'suited' I,556,5

14.563 The Braune Grammar suggests that this <n>#<m> opposition might reflect a labiodental=labial allophonic difference in pronunciation of the nasal (1975: 123, Anm. 1). This paper, in contrast, argued that the <n> in

fínf [vɪmf] 'five' 13.21

more likely marks the lack of epenthetic [p] present in

gelámf [gɔlamf] 'suited' I.556,5

Neither analysis, however, proposes an f/v opposition in fortition here.

14.571 In light of the preceding discussion then perhaps, if only for fricatives, one could posit an amended version of Penzl's non-dental "Auslautverhärtung".

Non-dental Fricative "Auslautverhärtung":

14.572 Dental fricatives contrast syllable finally, ex:

/z/	/s/
uuás 'was' 11,5a	uuáz 'what' 60,16

Nevertheless the contrast need not necessarily be one of fortition, but rather only one in place. At least that is what the otherwise lenis <s> graph seems to be able to mark syllable initially, retained even when [z] is made fortis by the "Anlautgesetz" in

daz síngen 'that we sing' 115,9a

14.573 Rules are more natural the more phonemes they apply to. Perhaps, then, one should maximize an amended Penzl "Auslautverhärtung" to affect all fricatives, not just non-dentals. This would even simplify the rule, by dropping the specification [-coronal] in its structural description.

Fricative "Auslautverhärtung":

$[-\text{sonorant}] \rightarrow [+ \text{fortis}] / _ \#$
 $[+\text{continuant}]$

14.574 Such a rule would not violate a guideline. It might even simplify the system overall by lifting a graphemic restriction on <u>. ex:

$\langle u \text{ } [-\text{consonantal}] \rangle \rightarrow \langle f \rangle / _ \# \#$

The alternation of fricatives in

uuóluu 'wolves' II,238,1

uuólf 'wolf' II,345.2

would be conditioned phonologically, not graphemically. The rule could be appended onto the present fortition rule:

Fortition:

$[-\text{sonorant}] \rightarrow [+ \text{fortis}]$ / $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} [-\text{sonorant}] \\ [-\text{sonorant}] (\#) _ \\ [\text{nasal sonority or lower}] _ \# \end{array} \right.$

$[-\text{sonorant}] \rightarrow [+ \text{fortis}] / _ \#$
 $[+\text{continuant}]$

14.581 When comparing phonological processes with each other, what is

more natural, or even more simple, has not yet been successfully codified. According to Lass:

"neither the idea of a formal evaluation in general, nor a quantifiable notion of naturalness/markedness have made any really enlightening contributions (1994:198),²"

Nevertheless there are guidelines, and Lass addresses some of them in his book (1994:195-200).

14.582 When comparing phonological processes with graphemic ones, however, what should be more natural or simple has scarcely been touched upon. Some suggestions were offered in the section on methods. Following them, syllable final fortition for fricatives should be posited.

14.583 Accepting the rule, however, entails positing two separate structural descriptions for one process--syllable final fortition. Fortition could no longer be captured in one rule affecting all non-sonorants.

14.584 In three environments all obstruents would be made fortis: syllable initially after an obstruent, syllable medially when just next to an obstruent, and syllable finally after nasal sonority or lower. ex:

	[p]	[f]
s.i.	ih peginne 'I begin' 35.19	uuás fiío 'was much' 23.2
s.m.	chöpf 'head' 74.1	háft 'incarceration' I,105.13
s.f.	lámþ 'lamb' II,239.9	fiíft 'five' 13.21

14.585 In one position, however, syllable finally after vowels and liquids, the pattern gets broken. Obstruents no longer act in a block, but rather fricatives become fortis, while stops remain unaffected. ex:

	[b]>/b/	[f]>/v/
s.f.	uuíþ 'woman' 14.15	hóf 'court' 86.116a

14.586 An alternative to this would be a word final graphemic restriction on <u>, paralleling the ones on <k> and <ch>. ex:

w.m.	w.f.
------	------

físken 'fish Dat. Pl.' 67.6	físg 'fish Nom.' I.167,28
sprácha 'languages' 85,1	sprah 'spoke' 47,21a
hóue 'court Dat.' 102.3	hóf 'court Nom.' 87.16a

Perhaps, if graphemic and phonological processes can be compared, this might be a simpler solution.

14.611 Still another approach to syllable final fortition would be to posit no rule at all. Such an analysis would try to account in a different way for the alternations in stops after nasals.

14.621 For the dentals, the lenition rule alone, if amended, could generate both

fíndest [fin\$dst] 'you find' 109.18

and fánt [fant] 'found' 118,11

Dentals would just have to be restricted to leniting only before a sonorant.

Amended Lenition:

14.622 Such an analysis would of course simplify the set of rules. After all, a process of fortition would be replaced by an amendment to the lenition rule. At the same time, however, an analyst would need to account for why only <t>, and, at least in de Nuptiis, never <d> occurs syllable finally after nasals. ex:

fánt 'found' 18,11

14.623 Accomplishing this puts perhaps two strains on the system. First, if the final fortition rule is abolished, an underlying /t/ must of course be assumed in all nasal-dental stop sequences. ex:

fíndest [fin\$dst], underlying /fin\$dst/ 'you find' 109,18

fánt [fant], underlying /fant/ 'found' 118,11

14.624 Secondly, such an analysis should perhaps somehow account for why the /t/ in

fánt 'found' 118.11

does not, on analogy with

fíndest 'you find' 109.18

at least sometimes come up as <d> syllable finally. ex:

**fánd 'found'

After all, syllable initially at least, a <d> from /t/ varies with <t>, presumably on analogy with the unlenited form. ex:

ter téil [tersteil] 'the part' 170.11

min déil [mindeil] 'my part' 48.1

but, einen ^{teil}teíl [einensteil] 'a part' 145.6

Why should not one also expect the same phenomena syllable finally. Without final fortition there would be no rule preventing a lenis [d] from occurring syllable finally.

14.631 Abolishing the final fortition rule would fail to let both dental stops generate

fánt [fant] 'found' 118.11

In addition, however, for the dental fricatives, amending the lenition rule would fail to let both /s/ and /z/ generate [z] syllable finally after liquids. ex:

ueŕs 'verse' 30.3

náls 'not at all' 141.2

Dentals, in the new rule, would not lenite before a syllable boundary.

Ammended Lenition:

14.641 In the velar stops, final <g>, after all graphs, including of course nasals, might be best accounted for graphemically. ex:

dīsg [disk] 'table' 18,112

stāng [stank] 'stench' 14,2

That still, however, leaves the labials to help an analyst decide whether to posit a final fortition rule or not. In light of this, perhaps a closer look at their distribution in the entire Notker canon might be warranted.

14.642 For the labials, in only three morphemes--'crooked', 'lamb' and 'dumb'--does /b/ occur syllable finally after nasals. In 'crooked', the stop appears here three times as <p>, and four times as . In 'lamb', /b/ comes out twice as <p> and three times as , while in 'dumb', the phoneme is written once as <p>, twice as . ex:

chrūmp 'crooked' II.105,25

gechrūmpta 'made crooked' II.197,3

gechrūmpte 'made crooked' I,750,23

chrūmb 'crooked' II.1106,18

" " II.126,13

" " II.169,29

" " II.382,21

lāmp 'lamb' II,239,9

" " II.329,21

lāmb 'lamb' II,146,26

" " II,146,20

" " II,146,22

tūmplih 'stupidly' II,265

tūmbheite 'stupidity' I,323,21

tūmb 'dumb' II,488,2

14.643 When not syllable final, /b/ after /m/ in these morphemes is always, as far as the writer can tell, written lenis. ex:

chrūmbi 'crookedness' I,458,15

lémber 'lambs' II.486.6

tumber 'dumb. inflect.' II.488.2

14.651 There are perhaps two directions an account could take of the <p/b> variation in

lám̄p 'lamb' II.239.9

lám̄b 'lamb' II.146.26

14.652 One could assume the form with as reflecting phonological reality, and write off forms with <p> as mistakes. After all, only 6 out of 15, or just 40% of the words listed above end in <p>.

14.653 Unfortunately, an analysis without a final fortition rule would fail to explain what motivated these mistakes syllable finally, but not initially. ex:

lamb underlying /lamb/ 'lamb' II.239.9

lember underlying /lem\$ber/ II.486.6

An analyst is struck by a sort of regularity in the mistakes. <p> occurs syllable finally in all three morphemes, independent, apparently, of the meanings of the morphs, but rather connected to the phonological environment the labial stops share.

14.611 A different approach, then, would allow a fortition rule to generate the <p> in

lám̄p [lamp] 'lamb' II.239.9

Examples with could get accounted for on analogy with forms of the same morph, in which the /b/ is not syllable final. In other words, Notker wrote 'lamb' with a instead of a <p> in

lám̄b [lamp] 'lamb' II.146.26

because he recognized it as being related to its plural

lémber [lem\$bər] 'lambs' II.486.6

14.662 Such an approach could resemble in method the analysis of the <u/f> variation for syllable initial /v/. So, for example, in the morph 'wolf', only once is a syllable initial [v] not written <f>. ex:

uuólua [uól\$ua] 'wolves' II.239.1

but, uuólfa [uól\$ua] 'wolves' II.329.25

uuólves [uól\$vəs] 'wolf Gen.' II.345.3

uuólfe [uóɫʃve] 'wolf Dat.' I,251.8

uuólfe [uóɫʃve] 'wolf Dat.' I.252.22

Nevertheless the one form with <u> was cited by Moulton(1979:246) and this paper as enough to set up a v=f opposition in

	/v/	/f/
after s.i. liquid	uuólua 'wolves' II,238.1	helfen 'help' I,265,22

14.663 If the <p> in

lám̄p [lám̄p] 'lamb' II,239.9

is explained through a syllable final fortition rule after nasals, the
t̄ in

fánt̄ [fánt̄] 'found' 118.11

can be accounted for in the same rule. The lenition rule then need not be restricted to affecting only those dentals that come before sonorants. This would not only increase the application of the lenition, but also simplify the process. In addition, such a maximized lenition rule would allow both /s/ and /z/ to generate [z] syllable finally after liquids. ex:

uērs̄ 'verse' 30.3

nals̄ 'not at all' 141.2

14.711 The three principles of syllable division in de Nuptiis were taken from Giegrich and Benware's analyses of it in Modern German. ex:

1) Onsets are maximized.

2) Word boundaries are always syllable boundaries.

3) No interlude may divide so as to yield sequences which do not also occur word initially or word finally(Benware 1984:87).

14.712 Following them, Modern German

'erheblich'

and 'Feigling'

should divide as

/erheesbliX/

/fai\$gliŋ/

14.713 According to Benware, however, leeway exists:

"when obstruent and sonorant stand on opposite sides of the morpheme boundary (Benware 1984:86)."

A syllabification as

/erheeb\$liX/

and /faig\$liŋ/

is "also possible (1984:86)". If possible, one would like to see where *de Nuptiis* stands on this.

14.721 The labial stop in the Alemannic morpheme for 'stupid' was analyzed as reflecting an underlying /b/. The word was split syllabically between the nasal and the stop. ex:

tumber /tum\$ɔr/ 'stupid Inflect.' II.488,2

14.722 Without evidence to the contrary, one would assume the same analysis could apply to the /mbli/ sequence in 'stupidly'. ex:

tumpliŋ underlying **/tum\$bliX/ 'stupidly' II.265

After all, [bl] is an acceptable syllable and word onset. ex:

bliŋ [blik] 'glance' 65,5

Unfortunately the lenis /b/ phoneme in

tumpliŋ underlying /tum\$bliX/ 'stupidly' II.265

is written <p>. If this <p> is interpreted as phonologically motivated however, the fortition rule cannot condition it because the /b/ is not syllable final.

14.731 In the inflected form of 'stupid' the stop is followed by a vowel, while in 'stupidly' it precedes a non-vowel. ex:

tumber 'stupid Inflect.' II.488,2

tumpliŋ 'stupidly' II.265

For the dentals, a similar pattern might be seen in, for example, the verb prefix int. ex:

inderet 'insulted' I.36.17

intríhtet 'terrifies' II.404.20

intháben 'contain' I.64.4

intságet 'aquits' II.103.21

14.732 The lenition rule should lenite the dental after [n] in all these words. Before a vowel, the [d], since able to occur syllable initially, should get generated as lenis. ex:

indéret [in\$deerət] 'insulted' I.36.17

14.733 Before an obstruent, however, the [d] will be made fortis by a fortition rule ordered after the lenition if either syllable final after nasal sonority or lower, or syllable internally next to another obstruent. ex:

inthaben [int\$habəŋ] 'contain' I.103.21

intsaget [int\$tsagət] 'aquits' II.103.21

14.734 Unfortunately, before a consonantal sonorant—even one before which dental stops often occur syllable initially—the [d] gets written fortis. ex:

drí [dríi] 'three' I.233.27

but, intríhtet *[intríhtət] 'terrifies' II.404.20

14.741 A syllable constraint, if ordered before the fortition rule, could account for

intríhtet 'terrifies' II.404.20

In it, one might disallow, syllable internally, a string of two non-vowels if not part of the same morpheme.

Syllable Constraint:

**[+consonantal] + [+consonantal]

14.742 After the lenition rule then, the [d] in

[ind\$riXstət]

could become fortis syllable finally after nasal sonority or lower. ex:

intríhtet [int\$riXstət], from [ind\$riXtət], from underlying /int\$riXtet/ 'terrifies' II.404.20

14.743 In the analysis of vowel sequences a similar syllable constraint allowed analyzing as bisyllabic <ia> and <io> in

dīa [di\$a] 'the Fem. Acc>' I.12,13

nīomer [ni(i)\$o\$m r] 'never' I.65,15

Syllable Constraint:

**[-consonantal] + [-consonantal]

The two processes could of course be joined.

Syllable Constraint:

**[±consonantal] + [±consonantal]

14.811 T. Bynon. in her textbook on historical linguistics. speaks of:

"the addition of the devoicing (i.e. fortition) rule into the grammar of early Middle High German(1977:155)."

R.E. Keller opts for an earlier dating. believing that:

"In final position the contrast between lenis and fortis was eliminated in late OHG(1978:276)."

14.812 This paper lies somewhere between those two opinions. It places. at least in Saint Gall. something of a partial "Auslautverhärtung" in the late Old High German period. Perhaps even more interesting than its dating, however. is the fortition itself.

14.821 Modern English and the Scandinavian languages do not have syllable final fortition. Given this. one might assume that Proto-Germanic did not either. New High German, however. has a rule:

NHG Syllable Final Fortition:

[-sonorant] → [+fortis] / _____ #

14.822 The issue of how this change took place has. as far as the writer knows. received little attention. Without evidence to the contrary. one would of course assume that the above rule was just adopted. as is. into Medieval German dialects. That would appear to be the simplest explanation. T. Bynon after all talks about:

"the addition of the devoicing (i.e. fortition) rule(1975:155)."

14.823 Penzl sees thereafter:

"ein Wechsel zwischen Fortis im Auslaut und Lenis im Inlaut weit verbreitet(1972:164)."

The examples he cites have obstruents becoming fortis across the board--after vocalic and consonantal sonorants. ex:

"lop Gen. lobes; golt Gen. goldes, tac Gen. tages(1972:164)"

14.831 The fortition rule in de Nuptiis, however, speaks for a more gradated process.

de Nuptiis Syllable Final Fortition:

$[sonorant] \rightarrow [tfortis] / \left[\begin{array}{l} \text{nasal} \\ \text{sonority} \\ \text{or lower} \end{array} \right] \#$

It reflects a possible middle phase between Proto-Germanic and New High German. If one accepts the rule, then an argument might be made for adding on Syllable Final Fortition in at least two stages, and allowing relative degrees of sonority to condition those stages.

14.832 First obstruents lose the fortis/lenis opposition syllable finally after nasals. ex:

lémp 'lamb' II.239.9

The rule can then be later generalized to condition fortition even after the more sonorant liquids and vowels. ex:

MHG 'lop' 'praise'

14.911 R. Jeffers and I. Lehiste, in their text on Historical Linguistics, allow for 4 types of rule change: rule loss, rule reordering, rule addition and rule inversion(1979:82).

14.912 Rules can be lost or reordered anywhere if, ideally:

"motivated by the resulting simplification of the grammar(Bynon 1977:126)".

Rules can be added, however:

"at one point only, namely at the end of the phonological rules(Bynon 1979:118)".

In rule inversion, surface forms get reinterpreted as underlying representations, while the original underlying forms get generated by a rule(Jeffers and Lehiste 1979:82).

14.921 In comparing a language's synchronic set of rules with a diachronic one for it, one might want to minimize, as much as possible, the number of those historical rule changes that need to be assumed to produce the synchronic grammar. Rules can only be added on at the end of the set of rules. Given this, the simplest chain of events would be, of course, to allow the rules to be added on historically, according to how they are ordered in the synchronic

grammar.

14.922 Alongside this, perhaps ~~the~~⁵ language in question has sister languages, and synchronic grammars have been proposed for them. If so, one might like to see near the top of a language's grammar those rules present in the other sister languages--rules which one might assume were inherited from an earlier parent language, if they did not develop later and spread by diffusion. Rules more peculiar to the language in question would hopefully, in general, come later in the ordering.

14.923 With these things in mind, one might single out those rules in de Nuptiis which are ordered. These could then be compared to corresponding rules proposed for Proto-Germanic and its daughter languages.

14.931 Nasal Assimilation, if already productive in Proto-Germanic, can help account for an alternation in the English and de Nuptiis word for 'think'. ex:

denchet [denXɔt] 'thinks' I.766.20

dahta [daXsta] 'thought' 10.17

In preterite form in Proto-Germanic [n] assimilated to a velar, only to be later deleted before a [Xt] sequence.

*[ʒaŋXsta] -> *[ðaXsta] 'thought Proto-Germanic'

14.932 Nasal assimilation in de Nuptiis then could reflect an ancient rule, inherited from Proto-Germanic. Coincidentally, in the de Nuptiis synchronic grammar, Nasal Assimilation is ordered before 4 rules: Epenthesis, Dental Lenition, and through these two, Velar Deletion and Fortition.

14.951 Epenthesis was ordered before three rules: Velar Deletion, Dental Lenition, and through Dental Lenition, Fortition. And Epenthesis seems to be present in at least one other branch of Germanic: Otfrid's Old Franconian. ex:

gelimpflichero [gɛ\$lim\$pflixɛ\$ro] 'suited' 92.20

limphen 'to suit' Otfrid

14.951 Velar Deletion and Dental Lenition, however, both ordered after Nasal Assimilation and Epenthesis, are also both peculiar, as far as the writer can tell, to Old Alemannic. The only remaining rule ordering then would be the one placing Fortition after Dental Lenition.

14.961 It is hard to tell how new Fortition is in de Nuptiis. The rule however, unless its effects were later wiped out by analogy, could not have been ordered before the second sound shift. Otherwise the [p] in

l^hamp [lamp] 'lamb' II,239.9

should come out as a stop-fricative cluster. ex:

**l^hampf [lampf] 'lampf'

In addition, however, the syllable final fortition, might be only a first stage toward a more general process in Middle High German. With this in mind, perhaps one could argue that the fortition rule may be so new that it is not even all here yet, and could be ordered last.

15.000 "Anlautgesetz"--Structure of a Rule

15.111 In section 16.000 the statistics of the "Anlautgesetz" in de Nuptiis can be analyzed. Beforehand, however, one might examine more closely the rule itself--specificly the different theories proposed so far.

15.112 To accomodate this, the four most recent treatments of the "Anlautgesetz" (Penzl 1972, Braune Grammar 1975, Moulton 1979, Clausning 1980) could be compared to each other and this paper's fortition rule. Out of this analysis should hopefully come some options by which the statistics could be interpreted.

15.113 In the transformational format, phonological processes get framed in rules consisting of three parts: the structural description or SD, the structural change or SC, and the CF or conditioning factor.

Phonological Rule:

[SD] -> [SC] / [CF] ___ [CF]

15.114 If the "Anlautgesetz" is to be fitted into such a rule, a discussion of it might be clearer if likewise broken down into three parts. The SD could be handled in the first section(15.200), followed by the SC(15.300) and, finally, by the CF(15.400).

15.211 Penzl, Moulton, Clausning and the Braune Grammar all speak of an alternation in stops and labial fricatives. ex:

"Notker's law can be defined as follows: The spellings p-b, k-g, t-d (and sometimes f-v) alternate with each other when preceded by a voiceless or voiced sound, respectively(Clausning 1980:358)."

Does this mean that the [+coronal] and [-anterior] fricatives should be phonologicly excluded from the SD? At least Clausning seems to argue so. In refuting the theory that the "Anlautgesetz" was motivated by a Celtic substratum he writes:

"Old Irish had, in addition to the process of lenition, nasalization of initial sounds by a preceding nasal and gemination by a preceding s. All consonants, not just p, b, d (and f), were

affected. It seems odd that German would take up only the process of lenition and only for a restricted group of sounds(1980:362)

An analyst who accepts this restricted SD would want to reflect it in the structural description. ex:

$$SD = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} [-\text{sonorant}] \\ [-\text{continuant}] \\ [-\text{sonorant}] \\ [+ \text{continuant}] \\ [+ \text{anterior}] \\ [-\text{coronal}] \end{array} \right.$$

15.212 In light of the discussion in (14.300), however one might be able to, through a guideline, allow the rule to affect /z,h/ and yet still not mark this graphemically. If so, the "Anlautgesetz" could be simplified and maximized by applying to all obstruents.

SD=[-sonorant]

15.311 Penzl and the Braune Grammar both argue that the "Anlautgesetz" reflects a fortition.

"Notker's Anlautswechsel drückt also tatsächlich Allophone der Lenisphoneme /b/ /d/ /g/ aus(Penzl 1972:104)."

"Notkers Wechseln zwischen den Zeichen u und f (uāren fāren) deutet auf diese Anlautsallophone hin. wobei wie bei den Verschlusslauten zumindest eine "Halbförtis" f im engen Anschluß an vorhergehende Geräuschlaute wahrscheinlich ist(Penzl 1972:102)."

"Die stimmlosen Lenes werden im Satzanlaut und nach stimmlosen Konsonanten zu (Halb)-Fortis verstärkt(Braune 1975:103 Anm. 1)."

15.321 One might ignore the qualification "halb" on [+fortis] as incompatible with the binary nature of feature theory. If so, then the structural change, if expressed formally could read:

SC=[+fortis]

15.322 Moulton is more cautious. He does not specify which features are changed by the "Anlautgesetz", but only that:

"the opposition lenis/fortis was suspended(1979:250)."

As the scholar does not posit a structural change however, his caution cannot be integrated into a rule.

15.331 Most recently, an alternate analysis to Penzl's and Braune's has been proposed by Clausen.

"Notker tends to use p,t,k (and f) at the beginning of a sentence. This usage implies that the fortis sounds are the normal values, which appear so when left in isolated position but which become lenis when put in a voiced environment(1980:364)."

Expressed formally then, this would read:

SC=[-fortis]

15.332 One wonders, however, how just a lenition could account for the two different dental graphs in

únde dár 'and there' 48.8a

die tága 'the days' 86.10

Should not both stops, if lenited "in a voiced environment(1979:364)", be written <d> after vowels? ex:

unde dár 'and there' 48.8a

**die daga 'the days'

15.333 Clausen is curious about this too, yet decides that perhaps:

"a slight difference in pronunciation made one form dental, voiced or unvoiced, susceptible to Notker's law and the other not(1979:363)."

15.334 In this paper, however, a syllable initial lenis/fortis opposition was proposed not only in the dentals, but in non-dentals too. ex:

Lenis	Fortis
ar ^h beite [ar\$beite] 'work' 118.14	púr ^h púr ^h un [pur\$pur ^h en] 'purple' 63.74
bur ^h go [bur\$go] 'castles' 19.10	fúr ^h kun [fur\$kn] 'trident' 51.19
tí ^h uel [ti ^h \$vø1] 'devil' II.469.23	ú ^h fen [uu\$fn] 'on' 39.4

If Clausen's analysis is adopted, then "slight differences in pronunciation" will have to be posited for the above pairs as well.

15.341 Arguing, however, that the "Anlautgesetz" is not a lenition is not the same as establishing it as a fortition. The process might have reflected a devoicing, aspiration, or glottalization for that matter. The issue, at least as far as voicing is concerned, is most thoroughly treated by Clausning.

15.342 Moulton, Penzl and the Braune Grammar assume that Notker's obstruents, both fortis and lenis, were voiceless, as in Modern Swiss.

"Die b.d.g bei N sind stimmlose Lenes, an stimmhafte Laute zu denken verbieten die Sprachtatsachen (Braune 1975:103 Anm.1)."

15.343 Clausning, however, notes that the lenes obstruents, while voiceless in today's Alemannic,

"were voiced lenes in pre-literary Germanic (1979:365)."

Conceivably then, the lenes obstruents could have been voiced in Notker a day too, and the switch to voicelessness taken place sometime in the thousand years since then. If so, the "Anlautgesetz" might only be a devoicing of voiced lenes obstruents.

SC=[-voice]

15.344 Why, according to Clausning, this should not be so, was first argued by G. Baesecke (1918:par. 59). Formulated by Clausning, the proposal reads:

"b.d. and g must be lenis because a b.d. or g occurring after them appears as p.t. or k. Clearly, there must be some distinction between these consonants and the sounds which produce the b.d. and g forms such as vowels and resonants, which we know are voiced. In short, b.d. and g must be de-voiced, but lenis, to be distinguished from p.t. and k (1979:366)."

15.345 In the transformational framework however, not just one, but two features can differentiate voiced lenes obstruents from sonorants. Sonorants are not only [+voice], but also [+sonorant]. Notker's lenes obstruents then could have been [+voice], and only become [+fortis] before a [sonorant].

"Anlautgesetz":

$$\left[\begin{array}{l} -\text{fortis} \\ (+\text{voice}) \end{array} \right] \rightarrow [+fortis] / [-\text{sonorant}] (\#) \text{---}$$

15.346 An alternate approach to this issue, one perhaps more in line with the section on methods, might be to ignore it. Only a fortition--and not a devoicing, aspiration or glottalization for that matter--could cause in lenes obstruents a change of phonemic significance, i.e. a merger with fortis ones.

15.411 Of all the parts of the "Anlautgesetz", perhaps what conditions the rule has received the most attention. In order to give the following discussion form then, the "Anlautgesetz" used so far might be restated below:

"Anlautgesetz":

$[-\text{sonorant}] \rightarrow [+ \text{fortis}] / [-\text{sonorant}] (\#) \text{---}$

Its conditioning factor might serve as a model by which others could be compared.

CF = $[-\text{sonorant}] (\#)$

15.421 The Braune Grammar suggests:

"Bei N wechseln die Wortanlaute b-p, g-k, d-t. So, daB p,t,k steht:

1) am Anfang eines Satzes(oder Satzteils)

2) im Satz, wenn das vorhergehende Wort auf einen stimmlosen Laut endigt(1975:103)."

Expressed formally, this might look like:

$CF = \left. \begin{array}{l} [-\text{voice}] \\ [\text{End of a} \\ \text{Clause}] \end{array} \right\} (\#) \text{---}$

15.422 The difference between this CF and the one proposed in the obstruent summary look twofold. First of all, stops become fortis "auf einen stimmlosen Laut(1975:103)." Voice, and not sonority, helps condition the change.

15.423 Perhaps even more important, however, Braune tries to allow for those spellings which cannot be accounted for through a previous obstruent. ex:

futura.##taz 'future. That' 42.2

To do so he introduces a second, syntactic conditioning factor:

"am Anfang eines Satzes(oder Satzteils)(1975:103)."

15.431 Moulton would restructure Braune's proposal:

"The letters b,d,g,v are written when the words and morphemes in question follow voiced phonemes... but the letters p,t,k(c),f are written in the same words and morphemes when they follow a pause or voiceless phonemes(1979:241)."

If one reads "syllable" for "words and morphemes", then:

$$CF = \left. \begin{array}{l} [-voice] \\ [Pause] \end{array} \right\} (\#) \text{---}$$

Instead of a syntactic conditioning factor like Braune, Moulton, the dialectologist, opts for one based on speech rhythm.

15.441 Penzl looks for a compromise between the two. Obstruents, he argues, are made fortis "nach Satzpause(1972:104)."

$$CF = \left. \begin{array}{l} [-voice] \\ [Sentence] \\ [Pause] \end{array} \right\} (\#) \text{---}$$

15.442 Penzl's early work deals with sentence clauses in de Nuptiis, but such clauses have not been defined or catalogued. Braune and Penzl's syntactic conditioning factor, in a paper that has so far ignored syntax, might be out of place.

15.452 Moulton believes speech rhythm plays a role in Modern Swiss phonology:

"At least in the Zurich dialect, the opposition lenis/fortis is suspended not only in clusters of obstruents, but also after a pause(1979:250)."

14.453 But even if this was true in Notker's day, can one really read the pauses out of the manuscript? At least Braune's syntactic conditioning factor could be confirmed after a lengthy analysis. But a pause? How does one find a pause?

15.454 Clausening offers a suggestion:

"Fortunately, we can be fairly sure when the pauses occur, because they are indicated in the manuscript by an orthographic system(1979:364)."

15.461 This may be true. Might it not be more direct, however, to drop the term "pause" altogether? One could, instead, just integrate this orthographic system into the conditioning factor. A feature [+Boundary], gradated like sonority, could differentiate the high point, low point and plain word boundary.

15.562 To allow for this, however, the "Anlautgesetz" would have to be restructured as a purely syllable initial fortition. Perhaps this is what everyone means anyway when they talk about the rule being conditioned after pauses or sentence clauses. Obstruents are syllable initial here.

15.563 Voiced phonemes could inhibit syllable initial fortition. The feature [+Boundary] would, in turn, inhibit the ability of voiced phonemes to keep a lenis obstruent lenis. An amended CF could read:

$$CF = \left([-voice] [+Boundary] \right) \# \text{---}$$

15.464 The above CF specifies voice and not sonorancy. According to Penzl, however, all sonorants in de Nuptiis should be [+voice], and all non-sonorants [-voice]. If so, one would think the choice of feature might not matter. After all, both voice and sonorancy can inhibit fortition. Only sonority, however, can do so in degrees.

15.471 In the statistical section following, the conditioning factor of the "Anlautgesetz" can be examined across different grades of sonority. After vowels, for example, will obstruents be written lenis more often than when after consonantal sonorants? If not, perhaps voice does belong in the conditioning factor. If sonority gradations however do prove to be significant, one might want to rewrite the CF to account for this:

$$CF = \left([\text{sonorant}] ([+ \text{Boundary}]) \right) \# \text{---}$$

15.472 The above rule accounts for gradations in sonority between vowels, liquids and nasals. The difference between stops and fricatives, however, gets ignored--just as it was ignored when assigning syllable peaks. ex:

stant 'stood' I,15.7

15.483 Perhaps, however, in the statistical section, lenes stops will be written lenis more often after fricatives, than when after the less sonorant stops. If so, one could write a different CF:

$$C\bar{F} = \left([sonorant] ([T\text{Boundary}]) \right) \$ \text{---}$$

The feature [sonorant] would not be qualified with a plus or minus. In this way, sonority gradations in sonorants and obstruents could be accounted for.

16.000 The "Anlautgesetz" in de Nuptiis

16.111 By the end of the first half of the paper, an obstruent system for de Nuptiis had been proposed. In the pages following, the workings of the "Anlautgesetz" were explored. What can come next is the statistical section: in what patterns and to what degree the "Anlautgesetz" affects lenes stops.

16.112 The "Anlautgesetz" was analyzed according to the percentage of the time Alemannic /b,d,g/ are written <b,d,g> across 3 graphemic boundaries. These were:

1) the high point (°), signified abstractly here by a period followed by a word boundary (.##). ex:

romulo.##ter 'Romulus. who' 54.19

2) the low point (◌), written with a comma followed by a word boundary (.##). ex:

mān chād.##kebieten 'it is said they offer' 158.14a

3) the blank space, when it functions as a word boundary (##). ex:

unde##gab 'and gave' 124.14

The analysis begins with tables listing percentages. The questions this data hopes to answer are:

1) Does the nationality of a preceding graph (i.e. whether it is in a German or Latin word) have an effect on a following lenis stop?

2) Are labials, dentals or velars affected consistently different by the "Anlautgesetz" than the others?

3) How do the different boundaries affect the conditioning of

the "Anlautgesetz". and to what degree?

4) What role does sonority, especially finer grades of sonority, play in Notker's alternation of stops?

The four questions themselves are handled in two parts. First lenes stops after sonorants are examined, then those after obstruents.

16.120 Charts

16.121 /b,d,g/ after Sonorant plus Low Point:

The percentage of Alemannic lenes stops written fortis <p,t,k> when preceded by a low point preceded by a sonorant graph: broken down according to the nationality of the sonorant and its degree of sonority.

Key: L=Latin, G=German, T=Total. F=Fortis. N=Nasal. C=Consonant. V=Vowel, R=Sonorant. LQ=Liquid

	L	G	T	L	G	T	T	T	T	%L	%G	%T
	-F	-F	-F	+F	+F	+F	L	G	L,G	-F	-F	-F
a	1	1	2	33	55	38	34	56	90	2.9	1.8	2.2
e	2	3	5	36	105	13	128	108	136	7.1	2.8	3.7
o	1	3	4	16	52	68	17	55	72	5.9	5.5	5.6
V+hi	4	7	11	75	212	287	79	219	298	5.1	3.2	3.7
i	0	2	2	19	31	50	19	33	52	0.0	6.1	3.8
u	0	2	2	1	17	18	1	19	20	0.0	10.5	10.0
V+hi	0	4	4	20	48	68	20	52	72	0.0	7.7	5.5
V	4	11	15	95	260	355	99	271	370	4.0	4.1	4.1
l	0	1	1	0	4	4	0	5	5	---	20.0	20.0
r	0	0	0	2	13	15	2	13	15	0.0	0.0	0.0
LQ	0	1	1	2	17	19	2	18	20	0.0	5.6	5.0
m	2	0	2	33	1	34	35	1	36	5.7	0.0	5.6
n	0	15	15	4	133	137	4	148	152	0.0	10.1	9.9
N	2	15	17	37	134	171	39	149	188	5.1	10.1	9.0
C	2	16	18	37	151	190	41	167	208	4.9	9.6	8.7
R	6	27	33	132	411	545	105	437	542			

16.122 Stop after Sonorant plus High Point:

The percentage of Alemannic lenes stops /b,d,g/ written fortis <p,t,k> when preceded by a high point preceded by a sonorant; broken down according to the nationality of the sonorant and its degree of sonority.

	L	G	T	L	G	T	T	T	T	%L	%G	%T
	-F	-F	-F	+F	+F	+F	L	G	L.G	-F	-F	-F
a	8	4	12	17	6	23	25	10	35	32.0	40.0	34.3
e	14	6	20	12	12	24	26	18	44	53.8	66.7	45.5
o	3	4	7	12	4	16	15	8	23	20.0	50.0	30.4
V+hi	25	14	39	41	22	63	66	36	102	37.9	38.9	38.2
i	7	0	7	11	0	11	18	0	18	38.9	---	38.9
u	2	0	7	2	0	2	2	2	4	100	0.0	50.0
V+hi	9	0	9	11	2	13	20	2	22	45.0	0.0	40.9
V	34	14	48	52	24	76	86	38	124	39.6	36.8	38.7
l	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	---	100	100
r	15	1	16	8	3	11	23	4	27	65.2	25.0	59.3
LQ	15	2	17	8	3	11	23	5	28	65.2	40.0	60.7
m	21	0	21	18	1	19	39	1	40	53.8	0.0	52.5
n	0	10	10	2	17	19	2	27	29	0.0	37.0	34.5
N	21	10	31	20	18	38	41	28	69	51.2	35.7	44.9
C	36	12	48	28	21	49	64	33	97	56.3	36.4	49.5
R	70	26	96	80	45	125	150	71	221			

16.123 Stop after Low Point plus Obstruent:

The percentage of Alemannic /b.d.g/ written fortis <p.t.k> when preceded by a low point preceded by an obstruent, broken down according to the nationality of the obstruent and its degree of sonority.

	L	G	T	L	G	T	T	T	T	%L	%G	%T
	-F	-F	-F	+F	+F	+F	L	G	L.G	-F	-G	-F
h	0	11	11	0	3	3	0	14	14	---	78.6	78.6
f	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	---	100	100
s	24	23	47	7	6	13	31	29	60	77.4	79.3	78.3
z	0	8	8	0	1	1	0	9	9	---	88.9	88.9
+CT	24	43	67	7	10	17	31	53	84	77.4	81.1	79.8
t	0	130	130	1	7	8	1	137	138	0.0	94.9	94.2
c	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	---	---	---
b	0	3	3	0	0	0	0	3	3	---	100	100
d	0	6	6	0	2	2	0	8	8	---	75.0	75.0
g	0	9	9	0	0	0	0	9	9	---	100	100
-CT	0	148	148	1	9	10	1	157	158	0.0	94.3	93.7
-R	24	191	1215	8	19	27	32	210	242	75.0	91.0	88.8

16.124 Stops after Obstruent plus High Point

The percentage of Alemannic /b,d,g/ written fortis <p,t,k> when preceded by a high point preceded by an obstruent, broken down according to the nationality of the obstruent and its degree of sonority.

	L	G	T	L	G	T	T	T	T	%L	%G	%T
	-F	-F	-F	+F	+F	+F	L	G	L,G	-F	-F	-F
h	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	---	0.0	0.0
f	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	---	---	---
s	62	8	70	2	1	3	64	9	73	96.9	8.9	95.9
z	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	---	0.0	0.0
+CT	62	8	70	2	3	5	64	11	75	96.9	72.7	93.3
t	55	22	87	5	4	9	70	26	96	92.9	84.6	90.6
c	7	0	7	0	0	0	7	0	7	100	---	100
b	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	---	---	---
d	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	---	100	100
g	0	3	3	0	0	0	0	3	3	---	100	100
-CT	72	26	98	5	4	9	77	30	107	93.6	86.7	91.6
R	10484	168		7	7	14	141	31	182	95.0	82.9	92.3

16.125 Stops Broken Down by Place

The percentage of Alemannic /b,d,g/ written fortis <p,t,k>, broken down according to the place of articulation of the stop, and whether it is preceded by a vowel, consonantal sonorant or obstruent.

a) when preceded by a high point:

	LB	DN	VL	T	LB	DN	VL	T	T	T	T	T	%LB	%DN	%VL	%T
	-F	-F	-F	-F	+F	+F	+F	+F	LB	DN	VL		-F	-F	-F	-F
+V	1	45	2	48	1	74	1	76	2	1193	124		50.0	37.8	66.7	38.7
+R-V	3	43	2	48	0	28	1	49	3	71	3	97	100	60.1	66.7	49.5
+R	4	88	4	96	1	1022		1255		1906		221	80.0	46.3	66.7	43.4
-R	12	153	3	168	0	14	0	14	12	1673		182	100	91.6	100	92.3

b) when preceded by a low point:

	LB	DN	VL	T	LB	DN	VL	T	T	T	T	T	%LB	%DN	%VL	%T
	-F	-F	-F	-F	+F	+F	+F	+F	LB	DN	VL		-F	-F	-F	-F
+V	1	10	4	15	16	31217		34517		32221		360	5.9	3.1	19.0	4.2
+R-V	2	15	1	18	7	17211		1909		18712		208	22.2	8.0	8.3	8.7
+R	3	25	5	33	23	48428		53526		50933		568	11.6	4.9	21.7	5.8
-R	10	19510		215	0	26	1	27	10	22111		242	100	88.2	90.1	88.8

c) when preceded by a space:

LB	DN	VL	T	LB	DN	VL	T	T	T	T	%LB	%DN	%VL	%T
-F	-F	-F	-F	+F	+F	+F	+F	LB	DN	VL	-F	-F	-F	-F

+V
+R-V
+R
-R

17.000 "Anlautgesetz" after Sonorants

17.100 German vs. Latin

7.111 The nationality of the preceding sonorant has been assumed to play little or no role in the "Anlautgesetz". This section examines whether *de Nuptiis* bears that out.

7.121 After Vowels: Across high points, a preceding Latin vowel occurs before a /b,d,g/ written fortis 34 out of 86 times or 39.5%. ex:

romulo.##ter 'Romulus who' 54.19

After a German vowel the ratio is slightly smaller, 14 out of 38 times, or 36.8%. ex:

neuuäre.##taz 'were not that' 59.17a

17.122 After a low point preceded by a Latin vowel the fortis form of /b,d,g/ is written in 4 out of a total of 99 examples, or 4.0% of the time. ex:

suspirare.##tía 'breathing, the' 75.22

But unlike the situation after high points, the percentage of German vowels before a fortis /b,d,g/ is slightly greater than the Latin--4.3%, or in 11 out of 271 times. ex:

sie.##tánnan 'she, then' 44.9

17.123 The figures for vowels before plain word boundaries--about 2,000 forms--are not yet broken down into Latin and German subtotals. The figures for vowels before high and low points however seem to confirm that the nationality of a preceding vowel has little to do with how it affects a following /b,d,g/.

17.131 After Consonantal Sonorants: Across a high point preceded by a Latin consonantal sonorant Alemannic /b,d,g/ appear as fortes <p,t,k> in 36 out of 64 instances or 56.3%. ex:

superam.##kebi[^]etende 'superior, offering' 130,6a

17.132 After a German sonorant the ratio drops almost to 20%, to 14 out of 38 times. Only 36.8% of the stops are written fortis. ex:

gu[^]innen.##petrógen 'to win, deceived' 44,7a

17.133 Just the opposite occurs after low points. Here /b.d.g/ appear as <p.t.k> after German sonorants over twice as often (10.7% or 18 out of 169 times) as after Latin sonorants (2 out of 41 entries, or 4.9%). ex:

ánderen.##pédiu 'others, therefore' 88,17

nouem.##ter 'nine, the' 93,15

17.134 Since the figures show no pattern it looks that here too, after consonantal sonorants as after vowels, the nationality of a preceding word plays little role in the "Anlautgesetz".

17.200 The possibility of the "Anlautgesetz" favoring a certain place of articulation--of perhaps Alemannic /b/ occurring more often as <p>, than /g/ as <k>--has received little attention in the literature. Whether this inattention was justified or not, is the subject of this next section.

17.221 /b.d.g/ after Vowels: After a high point preceded by a vowel, Alemannic /b.d.g/ occur as <p.t.k> in 1 out of 2, 45 out of 129 and 2 out of 3 times respectively. ex:

uera.##pédiu 'truly, therefore' 53,9

uirgine.##tia 'virgin, which' 68,8

túncheliu.##kier 'dark, greed' 87,13

This leaves dentals written as fortis the lowest percentage of the time (34.9%), followed by the labials (50.0%) and the velar stops (66.7%).

17.222 After low points preceded by vowels, labials are written 1 out of 17 times as fortis or 5.9%, dentals 10 out of 324 or 3.1%, and velar stops 4 out of 21 times or 19.0%. ex:

ánderen.##pédiu 'others therefore' 88,17

sie.##tánnan 'she then' 44,99

áho.##káhes 'water, quickly' 102,13

Again, dentals occur least often as fortis.

17.223 Only a mass figure is available for stops after word boundaries, lumping those after vowels and sonorant consonants into

one sum. In this position Alemannic /b/ occurs as <p> in 12 out of 413 entries or 2.9%, /d/ comes up as <t> in 19 out of 1797 or 1.0%, and /g/ as <k> in 5 out of 1036 or 0.5%. ex:

dánne##prénnet 'then it burns' 65,5

óffene##tie 'open which' 86,18

ioue##kehéizent 'named by Jove' 50,16a

17.231 After Sonorant Consonants: After sonorant consonants followed by a high point, /b/ comes out as <p> in 3 out of 3 entries or 100%, /d/ as <t> in 43, out of 71 words or 60.1%, and /g/ as <k> in 2 out of 3 or 66.7%. ex:

híezen.##pédiu 'called. by this' 2,15

deorum.##tin 'of the gods. your' 41,20a

superam.##kebietende 'better. offering' 130,6a

As was the case after low and high points preceded by vowels, dentals here again occur least often as fortis.

17.232 After low points preceded by a sonorant consonant, /b/ is written <p> 22.2% or 2 out of 9 times, /d/ as <t> 15 out of 187 or 8.0%, and /g/ as <k> 1 out of 12 times or 8.3%. ex:

ánderen.##pediu 'others. by that' 88,17

ófffen.##taz 'open. that' 36,21

áho.##kahes 'water. quickly' 102,13

Again the dentals occur, if just barely at 0.3% points behind the velars, least often as fortis.

17.233 It is hard to account for the tendency of /d/ to remain lenis after higher degrees of boundary. The unique influence of <n> on dentals which often lenites even fortis /t/ across a word boundary--cannot be the whole answer. After punctuation marks /d/ tends to stay lenis after vowels too. And even after sonorant consonants, figures for <n> before /d/ point in no clear direction.

17.234 <n> before high points does allow /d/ to become fortis less than half of the time (28% or 7 out of 25 times) as sonorants in general (60.1% in 43 out of 71 words). After low points though, <n> fails to show such an effect on the dental, leniting /d/ even slightly less often (9.5% of the time or in 13 out of 137 words) than sonorant consonants in general (8.0% or in 15 out of 187 entries).

17.235 Perhaps the reasons for the disproportionate amount of /d/'s remaining lenis after punctuation marks lie not with the dentals, but rather with the labial and velar stops. There are only 5 /b/'s after sonorants preceded by a high point, and only 5 /g/'s. The small amount of these stops here cannot have a positive effect on the accuracy of conclusions that are often based on the difference of a

few percentage points.

17.236 After plain word boundary examples are more numerous and lenes velar consonants and not dentals appear least often as fortis here. The figures for stops after high and low points can be compared to these. When this is done, it becomes difficult to maintain that place of articulation plays a role in the "Anlautgesetz".

17.300 Graphemic boundaries

17.311 Clausing argues that after high and low points:

"a pause is to be made and the p,t,k and f spellings tend to be used(1979:364)"

Does de Nuptiis bear this out?

17.321 After Vowels: After vowels before a high point. /b,d,g/ are written fortis 48 out of 124 times or 38.7%. ex:

romulo.##ter 'Romulus. who' 54.19

Across low points preceded by vowels, the "Anlautgesetz" is much more reliable, failing to take effect in just 15 out of 370 examples, or 4.1% of the time. ex:

sie.##tānnan 'she, then' 4.9

17.331 After Sonorant Consonants: After sonorant consonants followed by a high point. /b,d,g/ is written <p,t,k> in 50 out of 102 words or 49.0%. After low points preceded by a sonorant consonant, the ratio drops to one fifth that, 9.5%, or 20 out of 210 times. ex:

haben.##tōh 'have, nevertheless' 9.7

17.341 /b,d,g/. when preceded by any sonorant--vocalic or consonantal--are written fortis just 36 out of 3,270 times or 1.1%. ex:

aber##kelāzen 'but left' 31.12

This is well below the percentages for both vowels and sonorant consonants before low points(4.1% and 9.5% respectively).

17.351 The most frequent place that /b,d,g/ are written fortis is across high points after consonantal sonorants. And even there, only 49% of the time do the stops come out as <p,t,k>. If, as Clausing maintains, the fortis spellings "tend to be used" after punctuation marks, then it must be in manuscripts other than de Nuptiis.

17.400 Sonorancy

Since before Grimm, the graphs affecting a following /b,d,g/ have been broken down into two groups--obstruents and sonorants. Lenes stops

are written fortis after obstruents, and lenis after sonorants.
17.412 The question of what role finer distinctions of sonority might play, has to the writer's knowledge, not been adressed. Perhaps vowels keep a lenis stop lenis more often than nasals. This final section examines if, and to what degree, such finer distinctions of sonority are relevant to de Nupliis.

17.421 Sonorants before High Points: As mentioned in the section on syllable structure, the non-high vowels /a,o,u/ are the most sonorant sonorants, followed by the high vowels /i,u/. Then come the liquids /l,r/ and finally the nasals /m,n/.

17.422 Across high points preceeded by a non-high vowel, Alemannic /b,d,g/ is written fortis 39 out of 102 times or 38.2%. ex:

romulo.##ter "Romulus, who" 54,19

After the less sonorant high vowels, the ratio is, as one might expect, slightly larger: 40.9% or in 9 out of 22 entries. ex:

augusti.##taz 'illustrious, that' 2,18

17.423 Altogether, vowels before a high point occur in 48 out of 124 words or 38.7% before a /b,d,g/ written fortis.

17.431 After the liquids, /b,d,g/ is written fortis is 17 out of 28 examples or 60.7%. This is 1.5 times as often as after vowels. ex:

uidebatur.##tiser 'it seemed, this' 166,10

17.432 However after the least sonorant sonorants, after nasals, this upward trend does not continue. Lenes stops appear fortis after <m> and <nn> in only 31 out of 69 words or 43.2%. ex:

deorum.##tin 'of the gods, your' 41.20a

17.451 43.2%, the figure for nasals, is as one would expect, higher than the figures for the more sonorant low and high vowels (38.2% and 40.9%). Unfortunately, it is also considerably less than 60.7%; that is the percentage of lenes stops made fortis after liquids; phonemes more sonorant than nasals. Why the discrepancy?

17.452 Part of the reason may lie in the small amount of stops after liquids - only 28. Other factors not touched upon in this paper might also be at play. Out of 28 examples of <l> and <r> before a lenis stop across a high point, 24 are of Latin <r>. ex:

uidebatur.##tiser 'seemed, this' 166,101

17.453 Word final Latin /r/ appears in the nominative case for 3rd class nouns and in the passive marker in verbs. Verbs, stylisticly in Latin, tend to be written at the end of a clause. What effect this might have on the fortition rule may be beyond the scope of this analysis. But it does not mean that there might not also be such syntactic elements conditioning the "Anlautgesetz".

17.455 Sonority gradations across High Points: After all vowels plus high point Alemannic /b,d,g/ are written <p,t,k> 48 out of 124 times or 38.7%. After the less sonorant consonantal sonorants, the lenes stops come out fortis 1.25 times more often--47.4% or in 48 out of 97 entries. A two way division of sonorants--between vowels and consonantal sonorants--looks significant in de Nuptiis.

17.456 A finer, four part division is harder to establish. In the 3 cases such finer differences are measured--between high vowels and low vowels, between liquids and high vowels, and between nasals and liquids. Unfortunately in only two of these does de Nuptiis bear out one's expectations. Nasals do not allow fortition more often than the more sonorant liquids. Perhaps the data for the stops after low points will be better able to justify or reject a four part division.

17.461 Low Points: Across low points preceded by a non-high vowel, /b,d,g/ are written <p,t,k> 11 out of 298 times or 3.7%. ex:

3ie.##tannan 'she, then' 49,9

After the more sonorant high vowels, lenes stops come out, as expected, more often as fortis--5.5% of the time or in 4 out of 72 entries. ex:

si.tu 'be, you' 124.10

17.462 After liquids plus low point, /b,d,g/ are written fortis, contrary to what one would expect, slightly less often than when after high vowels. They only come out so in 1 out of 20 examples, or 5.0%. ex:

17.463 After nasals plus low point, lenes stops come out as fortis in 17 out of 188 examples or 9.0%. This is almost twice as often as when after the more sonorant liquids. ex:

offen.##taz 'open, that' 36.21

17.464 Why the inconsistency after liquids? They occur slightly less often (5.0%). Part of the answer may again lie in the small amount of liquids in this position. Only 20 times do liquids come before a low point plus a /b,d,g/. This compares to the 298 examples with non-high vowels, the 72 with high vowels, and the 188 with nasals.

17.465 If there had been one more example of <l> or <r> before a fortis /b,d,g/ (i.e. 2 out of 20), the rate would have been 10.0%. And that is above 9.0%, the rate for the less sonorant nasals. If there had been one less example (i.e. 0 out of 20), the liquids would have appeared even more sonorant than the non-high vowels.

17.471 Sonority Gradations before Low Points: Of the 370 cases of /b,d,g/ preceded by a vowel plus low point, in 15, or 4.1%, is the stop written fortis. ex:

sie,##tánnan 'she, then' 44,9

Over twice as often--8.7% of the time, or in 18 out of 208 examples--is fortition marked after sonorant consonants. ex:

offen,##taz 'open, then' 36,21

17.472 Apparently across low points too, the difference between vocalic and consonantal sonority is significant. And this helps confirm the same 2-part division proposed across high points.

17.473 The finer four part division is again, as after high points, harder to establish. In three comparisons are these finer differences measured: between high vowels and non-high ones, between liquids and high vowels, and between liquids and nasals. In only two of these comparisons are one's expectations confirmed. Liquids do not allow fortition more often than the more sonorant high vowels.

18.000 "Anlautgesetz" after Obstruents

18.111 After sonorants, both the nationality of the sonorant and the place of articulation of a following lenis stop could not be shown to be significant in the "Anlautgesetz". Graphemic boundaries and gradations in sonority however, do play a role in the fortition at least after sonorants. /b,d,g/ come out as <p,t,k> more often after higher degrees of boundary, and after lower degrees of sonority. This next section examines whether these trends hold true after obstruents.

18.200 German vs. Latin

18.211 Whether a sonorant preceding a lenis stop is German or Latin was not shown to affect the fortition of that stop. Without evidence to the contrary, one would expect this to be the case after obstruents too.

18.212 After Latin obstruents plus low point, /b,d,g/ appears as <p,t,k> 75.0% of the time or in 24 out of 32 entries. ex:

fabulas,##tia 'fabulous, which' 87,11

When the obstruent is German, the fortis forms of /b,d,g/ are more common, occurring in 91.0% of all examples, or in 191 out of 210. ex:

héizet,##tie 'calls the' 55,3

18.213 Across a high point, Latin obstruents come before a <p,t,k> from /b,d,g/ in 134 out of 141 examples, or 95.0%. ex:

thalamos,##tih 'Thalamos, you' 4,15

18.214 German obstruents here however behave differently than when

before low points. They come more often than the Latin ones before a fortis /b,d,g/--in 34 out of 41 cases or 82.9% of the time. ex:

rätet.##t^hih 'advises, you' 41,17

18.215 Stops after plain word boundaries are not broken down into German and Latin subtotals. Nevertheless, the percentages after low and high points show no clear pattern. Apparently the nationality of a preceding obstruent, as the nationality of a preceding sonorant, is not significant in the "Anlautgesetz".

18.300 Place of Articulation

18.311 After sonorants the place of articulation of a stop could not be shown to affect its fortition. Does this hold true after obstruents?

18.312 Across high point lenes labial and velar stops are written fortis 12 out of 12 and 3 out of 3 times respectively, or 100.0% of the time in both cases. ex:

est.##pediu 'is, because' 94,22a

hic.##kelóuuu 'this, belief' 113,14

/d/ on the other hand comes out as <t> only 91.6% or in 153 out of 167 entries. ex:

nemág.##tie 'cannot, the' 112,19

18.313 Across low points the dental is again the lenis stop least often written fortis after obstruents. It occurs as <t> only 88.2% of the time or in 195 out of 221 words. ex:

fólget.##tie 'follows, the' 85,18

In contrast /b/ is written <p> 100.0% of the time in 10 out of 10 words. /g/ appears as <k> in 90.1% or 10 out of 11 examples. ex:

neptunus.##prahta 'Neptune, brought' 72,22

unsih.##cóta 'us, gods' 31,10

18.314 But this pattern breaks off after plain word boundaries. Of the 3 lenes stops, the dental is here written most often fortis in 99.1% or 756 of the 763 examples. ex:

óuh##tie 'also the' 142,19

The labial follows in a close second, written fortis in 98.3% or 112 of 117 examples. The velar stop is made fortis in only 95.4% or 250 of 262 words. ex:

máged##pin 'maid am' 134,4

uns##cōten 'us gods' 32,21

18.315 After obstruents as after sonorants, place of articulation has little effect on the "Anlautgesetz".

18.400 Boundary

8.411 Sonorants occur before a fortis /b,d,g/ more often across high points than low points, and more frequently across low points than plain boundaries. Without reasons to the contrary, one might expect degrees of boundary to play a similar role after the obstruents.

18.421 Across high points, obstruents occur before a /b,d,g/ as <p,t,k> in 168 out of 182 words or 92.3% of the time. ex:

rātet.##tih 'advises, you' 41,17

18.431 Across low points fortition is somewhat rarer, occurring in 88.8% or 215 out of 242 examples. ex:

tūot.##tien 'does. the' 78,2

18.441 Unfortunately this trend reverses when just a plain word boundary separates the obstruent from the stop. /b,d,g/ is written fortis in this position almost without exception; in 1121 out of 1142 entries or 98.2%. ex:

ioh tien 'also the' 78,5

18.451 The proportion of lenes stops written fortis across a word boundary drops from across high points to across low points, then rises to across plain word boundaries. Although after sonorants degrees of boundary are significant, it is hard to establish this after obstruents.

18.500 Sonorancy

18.511 Consonantal sonorants are less sonorant than vowels, and this difference proved significant to the "Anlautgesetz". Of the obstruents, stops are less sonorant than fricatives. This next section examines whether this difference in sonority is also reflected in de Nuptiis.

18.521 Across a high point preceeded by a fricative, lenes Alemannic stops are written <p,t,k> 70 out of 75 times or 43.3%. ex:

thamos.##tih 'Thamos, you' 4,15

18.522 Contrary to expectation, stops occur less often before a fortis /b,d,g/; in only 91.6% or 98 of the 107 examples. ex:

rātet.##tih 'advises you' 41,17

18.531 Across low points, just the opposite is true. Here fricatives come before the fortis forms of lenes stops in 78.8% or 67 out of 84 words. ex:

nañ,##tie 'near, the' 54,15

18.532 After stops however, fortis /b,d,g/ is more common, occurring in 93.7% of all examples or in 148 out of 158 words. ex:

túot,##tien 'does, the' 78,2

18.541 Apparently gradations of boundary here parallel those of sonority. Neither plays a role when stops are preceded by obstruents.

19.000 Fortition

19.111 Vowels allow fortition less often than consonantal sonorants. Gradations in sonority then play a role in the "Anlautgesetz". In light of this, perhaps sonority and not voice should condition it.

19.112 At least after sonorants, stops are kept lenis less often after high points than they are after low points. Sonorants allow fortition more often across low points than across plain word boundaries. Gradations in boundary then might be also included in the conditioning factor.

19.113 Gradations in boundary and sonority are only significant when the stop is preceded by a sonorant. In a rule then, they should both be linked to positive sonority. Given this, one might write the following rule:

Anlautgesetz ^{syllable initial fortition}

19.121 One wonders if a similar solution, patterned on the syllable initial fortition rule, should account for the process syllable finally. Lenes stops are written fortis not only after obstruents and nasals. but also occasionally after liquids and even vowels. ex:

hálb 'half' I,27,26

hálp 'half' II,474,8

gráb 'buried' II,13,24

gráp 'buried' II,186,21

If one could show that gradations in sonority were statistically significant in this, i.e. that, for example, lenis stops were written fortis more often after liquids than vowels, then perhaps the following, ammended final fortition could be posited.

19.122 In order to check out such a theory, however, an analyst would first need to establish what spellings he would interpret as marking fortition. Certainly the fortis graphs <p,t,k> would count, but what about, for example, <ch> and <gh> when they occur syllable finally for lenis /g/. ex:

búrg 'castle' I,703,23

búrch 'castle' II,318,12

búrgh 'castle' II,482,10

19.123 In the section on velar stops, <gh> was interpreted as marking [k] syllable finally in

ro^hgh 'robe' I,523,24

Perhaps such an analysis might best start out by assuming this <gh> graph, along with all other variations from <b,d,g>, are attempts to mark fortition. The statistics of this, however, are left for another paper.

20.000 Conclusion

20.111 The de Nuptiis system was summarized earlier, and perhaps need not be repeated here.

20.112 Notker's "Anlautgesetz" has generated articles for the last 150 years. The only previous treatments of his obstruent system, however, were done by Penzl in '68 and '72. In them, the scholar contrasted minimal pairs to arrive at the correct number of phonemes, and then compared them to their corresponding ones in the modern dialects. Perhaps five things have enabled this analysis to go farther.

20.113 Syllable boundaries were established, insted of contrasting phonemes "im Anlaut, Inlaut und Auslaut". The analysis was rooted in the generative theory, and a method was worked out to separate graphemicly from phonologicly conditioned spellings.

20.114 Gradations in sonority were integrated into a fortition rule. And the conditioning factor of the "Anlautgesetz" was checked out statisticly with the aid of computer printouts.

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Data:

<p> from /b/

After ##

After Latin word:

m filium##purlicho 'exalted' 27,14

After German word:

i snelli paldet 'gives courage' 150,10

u diu paldo 'audacious' 27,2

e die piugen 'bows' 46,11a

u diu plauua 'blue' 26,5

e mereuuge plauer 'bluer' 72,1a

o runso plauuiu 'blue' 22,14

e scateuue pleicher 'paler' 72,2

a tritta pliin 'leaden' 28,2

e danne prennet 'burns' 65,5

i si prunnoda 'noise of water' 14,8a

o dero purlichi 'excelent' 10,6

After .##

After Latin word:

s. neptunus. prahta 'brought' 72,22

After German word:

u. erliteniu. pat 'asked' 128,1

n. anderen. pediu 'by that' 88,17

n. sin. pediu 'by that' 11,7

t. uuihtheit. pecham 'got' 5,17

t. rat. pediu 'by that' 49,18a

t. 1st. pediu 'by that' 88,17
t. stuont. pediu 'by that' 131,16
t. skinet. pediu 'by that' 108,1
t. chundet. pediu 'by that' 137,14
t. chanst. pediu 'by that' 108,18
t. saget. peheftare 'Detainer' 76,21a
s. uuistuomes. pist 'are' 116,15

After .##

After Latin Word:

a. uers. pediu 'by that' 53,9
p. hiezen. pediu 'by that' 2,15
n. cenzegosstun. pediu 'by that' 73,11
n. geuinnen. petrogen 'deceived' 44,7a
s. muras. pediu 'by that' 119,15
s. rationis. pediu 'by that' 94,10
t. est. pediu 'by that' 94,19a
t. est pediu 'by that' 94,22a
s. iussus. pediu 'by that' 35,12
t. reddit. pediu 'by that' 96,11
s. uiirtus. pezera 'better' 35,21a
t. resumebat. pi 'by that' 71,16

After German Word:

n. hiezen. pediu 'by that' 2,15
n. cenzegosstun. pediu 'by that' 73,11
n. geuinnen. petrogen 'deceived' 44,7a
t. uuirt. pediu 'by that' 68,2

s. pluotes. pediu 'by that' 73,18

t. troumet. pediu 'by that' 13,6

t. sint. pediu 'by that' 86,10a

There is one example that does not fit any category:

DC, pezeichenet 'signifies' 90,20

from /b/

After ##

After Latin Word:

s leminius bezeichenne 'signify' 92.5

After German Word:

s des bruoder 'brother' 40.3

After ,##

After Latin Word:

i. samosi. bediu 'by that' 109.1

e. conceptione, bediu 'by that' 142.4a

o, interogo, bediu 'by that' 18.4

e. impudice. bediu 'by that' 152.4

r. quatuor. bediu 'by that' 94.18

m. arithmetiam, bediu 'by that' 166.18

After German Word:

e, neuurte, bediu 'by that' 104,8

o, machondo, bediu 'by that' 118,13

e, uuortene, bediu 'by that' 99,1

a, leitera, bediu 'by that' 126,11

o. erfarnemo, begagenda 'meeting' 147.18

i, suozi, beidiu 'by that' 147,18

a. liebera, bi 'with' 168.14
o. skiezendo, blecchezeta 'lightninged' 146,11
o. diezentemo, boumen 'trees' 20,1
a. alla, brahta 'brought' 58,10a
u. muodiu, buocho 'books' 155,22
a. sconista, burlichiu 'exalted' 150,22
n. skinen, bediu 'by that' 107,21a
r. tuncheler, bediu 'by that' 68,19a
n. manen, bediu 'by that' 146,4
n. uwaren, bediu 'by that' 166.7
r. brueder, behouter 'trims' 137,11
n. hoheston, boumo 'tree' 20,6
n. angisten, brah 'broke' 129,13a

After .##

After Latin Word:

a. ceroma, bediu 'by that' 89.3

After German Word:

o

There are three examples that do not fall into any category:

DC,Y bezeichnenet 'signifies' 92,5

RO, bezeichnenet 'signifies' 92,4

E, bezeichnenet 'signifies' 61,21a

<q> for /g/

After ##

After Latin Word:

s artes quunnen 'won' 101,21a

After German Word:

t bist quon 'inherit' 120,7

t bist quon 'inherit' 111,8

h noh quon 'inherent' 46,6

s uuas quon 'inherent' 46,11

t chit quonen 'inherent' 3,10

t mit quaremo 'certain' 120,7

After .##

o

After .##

After Latin Word:

m. chordaarum. quoniu 'inherent' 111,1

After German Word:

<c> for /g/

After ##

After Latin Word:

s nilus cnadigen 'merciful' 156,6

After German Word:

g manig cot 'god' 55,3

g sang cuten 'good' 5,6

g sang cuttenno 'goddess' 3,11

s lutteres coldes 'of gold' 12,11a

h uelih cot 'god' 41,9

s uuas coldfaro 'gold colored' 23,8

t alt cot 'god' 8,20

t heizent cota 'gods' 135,21

t hert cota 'gods' 138.3
s unscoten 'gods' 41.22a
s uns coten 'gods' 32.21
t luft coto 'gods' 135.16
t mit cotelichemo 'divine' 3.19
t meist clanzta 'shine' 103.13
t first clizen 'shine' 165.2a
s des cnuoge 'enough' 50.9a
s sines cnoto 'definite' 15.16
t ist cnuocta 'satisfied' 29.8a
h ouh cruone 'green' 66.14
h turh crundende 'investigating' 32.16
s nahtes crunden 'investigate' 46.6
t peginnet cruen 'green' 66.15
t mit crasefareuuen 'grass colored' 57.10
t mit cramatichis 'grammaar' 113.12
t ist cruone 'green' 67.21a
t sint crehto 'of course' 142.14
z eteuuaz cruone 'green' 66.14

After ,##

After Latin Word:

a. cautissima, cnoto 'definite' 120.5

s. pollucis, clizen 'shine'

After Germaan Word:

h. unsih, cota 'gods' 31.10

t. ist, clasefareuue 'color of glass' 56.19

<k> from /g/

After ##

After Latin Word: -

e ioue keheizent 'called' 50,16a

After German Word:

o iro kehileiche 'betrothing' 48,15

e ze keidenne 'to atone' 17,20

n niumon keselligi 'social' 20,21

r aber kelazen 'left' 31,12

After .##

After Latin Word:

e, maie, kerot 'desires' 42,15

s, romulus, kebriefte 'description' 84,7a

After German Word:

o, aho, kahes 'fast' 102,13

a, gehileicha, keinota 'agreed' 9,16

u, haftendiu, kestateta 'based' 47,19

r, fiur, kezoletez '?' 28,9

t, stant, kebildotez 'formed' 66,19

t, chint, kebot 'commanded' 79,14

t, pant, kemuorhtez 'accomplished' 58,3

t, uuirt, kezeichendes 'signifying' 91,6

d, chad, kebieten 'commanding' 158,14a

b, salb, kemachotez 'made' 100,18a

d, uuard, kieng 'went' 85,13

After .##

After Latin Word:

m. superam. kebietende 'offering' 130,6aa

s. auspiciis. kebe 'greed' 87,13

c. hic. kelouuiu 'belief' 113,14

c. hic. kelouuiu 'belief' 113,17

After German Word:

iu. tuncheliu. kier 'greed' 87,13

<g> from /g/

After ##

After Latin Word:

s iouis gab 'gave' 12,7

s platonis geni 'rain' 163,10

s artes gezeichnet 'drawn' 449,14

After German Word:

h doh gagen 'against' 61,11

f uf gagen 'against' 30,17

t meist gagen 'against' 61,11a

z taz gebildot 'pictured' 127,1a

z daz gehileichet 'betrothed' 3,16a

z allez gesibenot 'divided into seven' 163,5

z daz geskehen 'happen' 8,5

t ist gnuht 'a sufficient amount' 77,9a

z taz getana 'done' 130,9

After ,##

After Latin Word:

e. caliope, gesamenoton 'congregated' 126,6

i. chi, gescriben 'written' 126.7a
e. marte, gesprachi 'speech' 24.10
m. senarivm, gedriualtoter 'tripled' 94.7a
m. corronam, geuorhta 'accomplished' 130.4
n. aon, geziertes 'ornated' 109,4

After German Word:

a. suocha, gab 'gave' 14.15
e. stande, gagen 'against' 86,2
i. keselligi, geanteroti 'imitated' 20,21
o. uuorto, gebot 'commanded' 145,3
a. einunga, geeiscot 'atoned' 37.22
e. umbe, gefristet 'postponed' 45,14
a. tierna, gefurehullotiu 'with the face covered' 103.17
o. recchentemo, geiscota 'atoned' 21.2
o. goto, gelaa '?' 42,10a
a. selda, geristig 'dignity' 106.19a
e. uzlaze, getaten 'did' 106,9
e. handelonde, gonoton 'definite' 121.2
e. zeladonne, gnuoge 'enough' 24.3
n. liden, gehelle 'brighten' 122.15
n. uuaren, gemeinmuoti 'of one mind' 133,6
n. ferten, gemetemest 'moderate' 154,16
n. stein, genamoter 'of the same name' 64,21a
r. nideror, geristlicho 'dignified' 57,21
n. tabellon, gescribena 'written' 84,16a
n. rinnenten, geteta 'did' 23,10
n. uuirten, getuo 'do' 41,12a

h. gesah. gagen 'against' 102,15a

After .##

After Latin Word:

i. olympi. glizemo 'shine' 154,9

After German Word:

n. michelen. gagen 'against' 86,4

There is one example that does not fit in any category.

III. gefallent 'fall' 92,19

t> from /t/

After ##

After Latin Word:

s epicurus truog 'carried' 167,1

a germina tuot 'does' 142,1a

m salarona laurogen 'sad' 8,20

r iopiter tunchelela 'sacred' 63,13

r lucifer tuot 'does' 117,20

m spectaculum tuen 'do' 86,15a

After German Word:

t uuart tate 'deed' 131,11

h uuelih teil 'part' 76,22

s micheles teiles 'part' 169,19

s halbes teiles 'part' 152,8

z taz teta 'did' 122,3

t umbesueift teta 'did' 22,13

t naht teta 'did' 139,1

z taz teta 'did' 9,21a

z taz teta 'did' 77,10
z taz teta 'did' 85,2a
t mit tinten 'ink' 14,5a
h ouh tougene 'obscure' 137,14
t mit tougenen 'sacraments' 3,17
t mit tougenen 'sacraments' 135,22
h ruclih toum 'vapor' 19,18
s des touues 'dew' 147,6
t potescaft tribendo 'driving' 50,1
t botescaft tribet 'drives' 121,13
s tes trosten 'comforting' 9,9
t sint truobe 'dreary' 58,21a
h ioh tue 'do' 102,3
z iz tunnesta 'storms' 70,15
t Brust tuoche 'cloth' 55,17a
z daz tuot 'does' 133,15
z daz tuot 'does' 129,7
t muot tuot 'does' 81,10
z daz tuot 'does' 108,4
z daz tuot 'does' 107,17a
t nit tuueren 'slant' 75,9
o gando tag 'day' 170,1
e tie taga 'days' 86,11
e die taga 'days' 86,10
e geburte tage 'days' 12,4
o dero tago 'days' 67,21
e unde taten 'deeds' 122,14

o dero tegan 'ten-parted' 160.16
e sie taten 'did' 122.14
o aftero teil 'part' 69.9
a obero teil 'part' 138.14a
u halbiu teil 'part' 126.17
e nemende teil 'part' 168.9
o fordero teil 'part' 70.9
a aftera teil 'part' 132.9
o inimichelmo teile 'parts' 170.18
i zuei teilet 'divides' 118.22
u diu teilta 'divided' 95.14
o dero temperaturun 'mixture of airs' 39.1
a dara teta 'did' 43.10
e umbe teta 'did' 56.18
i si teta 'did' 101.5
e magetine teta 'did' 14.8
u gelichiu tier 'animal' 75.6
a slahta tier 'animal' 60.12
u siu timberenten 'saddening' 6.19
o dero tindun 'inks' 110.11
o filo tiurlichho 'dearly' 14.21
o dero tiurron 'doors' 103.4
e unde tocchot 'fight' 143.13
e ane todes 'death' 129.19
a gerta todet 'kill' 118.12
e tanne todigen 'mortal' 99.17

o iro tohter 'daughter' 104.7
a dia tohter 'daughter' 11.20
o iro tohtera 'daughters' 43.9
u diu toufi 'baptism' 73,3
e ne toug 'suffice' 2,20a
a andera tougena 'sacred' 129,8a
e die tougenen 'sacred' 16,14
o allero tougenero 'sacred' 88,19
i himel tougeni 'sacrament' 103.18
o demo toume 'vapor' 105.12
o zeiro trage 'slow' 131,14
o demo tragebette 'stretcher' 160,11
e umbe tragheit 'lethargy' 45.15
e ze tragi 'slow' 44.16a
o iro tragun 'slow' 22,15
e muge trakon 'slow' 47.3
o minemo tranche 'drink' 124,2a
e folle trang 'drink' 129,2a
o iro tregela 'bearers' 145,9
e brutliche trettenoda '3 step dance' 122.15a
e umbe tribe 'drive' 115,7a
e gebute triben 'drive' 44,18
e die tribent 'drive' 153,4
e unde triuua 'virtue' 4,7
o tero troianiscun 'troyan' 1103,17a
e die troianiscun 'troyan' 103,17a
e die troianisken 'troyan' 104,1a

e uuize tropfen 'drops' 164,4
e manige tropfen 'drops' 81,21
e unde troum 'dream' 9,9
e unde trouma 'dreams' 136,9
e tie truhtinga 'those who take part in the wedding' 165,7
o dero truncheni 'drunkenness' 74.5
e ne truoge 'carried' 34,7a
e keihnisse truogen 'carried' 104.1
u siu truogin 'caried' 111,17
o iho trut 'darling' 131.119
e dine trutun 'darlings' 111.5
e ne truuueta 'trust' 39.9a
e alde tuala 'delay' 107.18a
e alde tualon 'delays' 47.3
a dia tubun 'doves' 167,6
o brutegono tue 'do' 102,3
a hara tue 'do' 115,6
e inlande tuen 'do' 105,4
e ne tuen 'do' 83.10
o iro tugede 'virtues' 2,13
o tero tugede 'virtues' 1104,17
e unde tunchele 'sacraments' 68,19
i si tuncheliu 'sacraments' 149,22
o plauuemo tuoche 'cloths' 61,17
o rotemo tuoche 'cloths' 56.15
a sia tuon 'do' 101,17

e arende tuon 'do' 40,16a
a mahta tuon 'do' 72,2
e geminne tuonde 'doing' 4,7
o so tuondo 'doing' 146,12
e ze tuonne 'do' 8,8
e ze tuonne 'do' 43,7
e die tuont 'do' 21,5
e die tuont 'do' 1,7
a scaffunga tuost 'do' 107,10
i tu tuost 3,14
e ofto tuot 'do' 113,13
a bedia tuot 'do' 149,17
i si tuot 'do' 78,19
o so tuot 'do' 149,14a
i bruti tuot 'do' 130,21
a aha tuot 'do' 105,18
u diu ture 'door' 134,11
o iro turen 'doors' 105,20
e ze turen 'doors' 5,21a
e ane tuuala 'delay' 51,10
a geruhta tuualta 'delayed' 157,15
a ordena tuuarotin 'put in motion' 79,5
i dri tuueres 'slanting' 86,13
n an tabellon 'tables' 169,3
n einen tabellon 'tables' 84,16
r ter tag 'day' 84,16
r tir tag 'day' 115,18a

r der tagerod 'dawn' 170.4
n quon tages 'day' 46.6
r der tago 'days' 105.10
r ter teil 'part' 170.11
r after teil 'part' 70.10
n einen teil 'part' 145.6
n halben teil 'part' 147.15
n uunsteren teile 'parts' 69.20
n sinen teilen 'parts' 96.12
n dritten teiles 'part' 95.16
n halben teiles 'part' 96.4
n ahtoden teiles 'part' 98.11
r er teilonde 'dividing' 96.14
n frouuon teta 'did' 133.14
n suozen teta 'did' 16.16
r uzer tiuren 'doors' 58.3
n in tod 'death' 118.22a
n dien todigen 'mortal' 117.7
n geeretostun tohter 'daughter' 12.8
n unbetrogenun tohter 'daughter' 11.13
n manen tuo 'do' 25.5
n minen tougenen 'sacred' 80.3
l himel tougeni 'sacrament' 103.18
n hellelichen tougenina 'sacraments' 32.2
n anderen tougeniu 'sacred' 32.16
r ter tougeno 'sacred' 32.1

n chuninglichen tragebette 'stretcher' 123,21
n ein tragebette 'stretcher' 123,2
n einen tragen 'carry' 155.14
n zeseuuun tragende 'carrying' 73.22
r dar treib 'drove' 55.12
n beinen trettot 'steps' 108.17
n in trinchen 'drink' 108,17
r dar trincenten 'drinking' 105.18a
n min triuua 'virtue' 4.7
n min triuua 'virtue' 81.11
r mir triuuo 'virtue' 45.10
r unser trost 'comfort' 111.21
r uuar troumet 'dreams' 13.6
m troum truogenara 'a deceiver' 143.1a
n uuilon truobenten 'saddening' 114,22
n uuinsterun truog 'carried' 77.19
r anderer truog 'carried' 72,8
r aber truog 'carried' 149,5
r uuederer truog 'carried' 72.4
r einer truog 'carried' 72.6a
l teil truogen 'carried' 132,9
n nehein tuala 'delay' 31,14
r er tue 'do' 81,22
r er tueres 'slanging' 86.2
n uuilon tuncheler 'obscure' 68,1
r er tuon 'do' 29,9
r nahor tuonde 'doing' 153,18

n mennisen tuont 'do' 144,8

n dien tuot 'does' 74,2

l himel tuot 'does' 129.9

l himel turnet 'turn' 166.22

n dien tutton 'wart' 86.2a

g manig tag 'day' 61.22

g tag timberen 'darkness' 170,1a

d heilesod tue 'do' 37.2

b halb tuncheliu 'dark' 87.12a

g sang tunchelora 'darkness' 122.21

g vnuozig tuont 'do' 130,13

g scaffung tuost 'do' 107.10

<t> from /t/

After .##

After Latin Word:

s. censorinus, tuont 'do' 151,18

After German Word:

a, dietam, tageliches 'daily' 60,17

e. suizzendo, teta 'did' 59,

a, kerista, teta 'did' 59,8

e, uuare, teta 'did' 151,18

a, liumendingaa, tougeninga 'secret gods' 51,20

o, uobendo, trahtota 'deliberated' 100.5a

i, gemeinmuoti, triuua 'virtue' 133,6a

o. aho, truffen 'met' 164,5

n. stan trat 'stepped' 40,20
r. behulter, truog 'carried' 61.17
r. kedrifaltoter, tuot 'does' 98,8
s. liehtes. tougenero 'scared' 153.13
h. dih. tougeniu 'sacred' 156.2
z. luzzelez. trolicho 'threatening' 103.22

After .##

After Latin Word:

t. monstrauit. tages 'day' 139,7a

After German Word:

0

<d> from /t/

After ##

After Latin Word:

0

After German Word:

n min deil 'part' 48.1

n tritten deiles 'part' 20.15

n in duon 'do' 27.16

n mitten dag 'day' 70.22

n siben daga 'days' 153.4

n in dagaltichero 'festive' 77,8

n tritten dages 'day' 84.22

After .##

0

After .##

0

<t> from /d/

After ##

After Latin Word:

i terni ter 'the' 93.16

r relabitur ter 'the' 82.9

After German Word:

e offene tie 'the' 86.18

e fiere tie 'the' 87.2

a ana tie 'the' 22.5

After .##

After Latin Word:

e. suspirare, tia 'the' 75.22

o. collato, tiu 'the' 104.17a

a. stella, tiu 'the' 63.16a

m. nouem, ter 'the' 93.15

m. cetum, ter 'the' 66.11a

s. orcus, taz 'that' 130.22

s. lemures, taz 'that' 142.6

s. themis, taz 'that' 148.20

s. taurus, taz 'that' 97.21

s. quis, taz 'that' 35.14

s. perfectus, taz 'that' 93.13a

s. paladis, taz 'that' 103.19

s. iouis, taz 'that' 110.8

s. consspicias, ten 'the' 114.13

s. palladis, ten 'the' 56,16a
s. iouis, ter 'the' 158,13a
s. lapidis, ter 'the' 58,6
s. mopsus, ter 'the' 141,7
s. spesas, tero 'the' 1161,2
s. fabulus, tia 'the' 87,11
s. musas, tie 'the' 43,11
s. eracitus, tiser 'this' 166,10
s. fortunas, tiu 'the' 25,5a
s. mirabilis, tiu 'the' 58,11
s. aduersitas, toh 'nevertheless' 27,5
s. censorinus, tuont 'do' 112,10

After German Word:

e. sie, tannan 'than' 44,9
e. choste, taz 'that' 35,7
e. chomene, taz 'that' 36,21
o. urhabo, tiu 'the' 79,3
o. geluhtero, tiu 'the' 8,22
i, si, tu 'you' 124,10
e. himachaare, tu 'you' 4,1a
n. herebergon, tar 'there' 85,7
n. offen, taz 'that' 36,21
n. gefrehtoton, taz 'that' 2,14
n. fiurin, taz 'that' 71,3a
n. lenzen, tia 'the' 67,20
n. ferien, tie 'the' 153,3

n. irslaagenen, tie 'the' 17.58
n. zierton, tiu 'the' 104.5
n. forderorun, tiu 'the' 104,5
n, gehien, tiu 'the' 45,22
n. haben, toh 'nevertheless' 27.3
n. ferstozen, toh 'nevvertheless' 27.3
g. tuog, tar 'there' 2,21
d. fedelgold, taz 'that' 70.14a
g. skrig, taz 'that' 152.10
g. anfang, ter 'the' 32.1
g. ring, ter 'the' 103.13
d maged, tero 'the' 49.13
g. sang, tero 'the' 111.8
g. ring, tiu 'the' 170.8
g. sang, tiu 'the' 111.14
b. lib, tod 'death' 119,1
g. ding, tu 'you' 41,2
d. chad, taz 'that' 148.7
d. uuard, taz 'that' 124,15a
d. uuard, taz 'that' 124,15a
g. ding, taz 'that' 32,19
b. halb, tes 'the' 68,10

t. uuirt, tannan 'than' 114,14
t. ist, tanne 'than' 36,16
t. ist, tanne 'than' 43,4
t. luft, tanne 'than' 120,16

t. ist. tar 'there' 103.10
t. luft, tar 'there' 103,10
h. strih, tar 'there' 93,3a
t. chit, tar 'there' 85.2
t. nechumest, tar 'there' 124.12
t. ist. tar 'there' 69.21
s. zellnnis, tar 'there' 91.2
t. gat, tar 'there' 43,21a
t. luft, tar 'there' 135.16
s. rates, tar 'there' 49.5a
t. heizet, tara 'there' 38.4
s. liehtes, tara 'there' 122,13
t. ist, taz 'that' 44.8
t. beginnet, taz 'that' 98.5
t. sint, taz 'that' 144.11
t. heizet, taz 'that' 96.5
t. kesaget, taz 'that' 150.14
t. heizet, taz 'that' 55,13
t. heizet, taz 'that' 146,14
t. heizet, taz 'that' 150,14
t. selchenet, taz 'that' 118,20
t. minnot, taz 'that' 156,13
t. sint, taz 'that' 21,4
t. skinet, taz 'that' 95,12a
t. keskinet, taz 'that' 36,13a
t. ist, taz 'that' 64,19
s. uuas, taz 'that' 125.2

s. uns. taz 'that' 2.8
h. sih. taz 'that' 54.19a
h. ih. taz 'that' 45.6
t. muhet. taz 'that' 31.9
t. uuirt. taz 'that' 13.5a
t. echert. taz 'that' 99.3
t. lustet. taz 'that' 23.17
t. uuirt. taz 'that' 35.8
t. bist. taz 'that' 42.2
t. gat. taz 'that' 153.7
t. heizet. taz 'that' 149.9
t. solchez. taz 'that' 164.16
t. kenimet. taz 'that' 14.20
t. dient. taz 'that' 118.14
t. bezeichnenet. taz 'that' 28.15
t. gescafiot. taz 'that' 65.19
t. anterot. taz 'that' 32.2
t. chosot. taz 'that' 48.6a
t. chomest. taz 'that' 48.6a
t. heizest. taz 'that' 66.7
s. uuas. taz 'that' 60.3
t. skinet. taz 'that' 96.11a
s. des. taz 'that' 89.8a
s. des. taz 'that' 13.12
s. uuas. taz 'that' 169.7
t. chit. taz 'that' 127.21

t. solit, taz 'that' 169,14
t. geheiligont, taz 'that' 119,6
t. meist, taz 'that' 10,4
t. uuirt, taz 'that' 93,8
t. skinet, taz 'that' 93,8
t. kefideret, taz 'that' 93,8
t. chit, taz 'that' 127,4
t. nieht, taz 'that' 98,20
t. kat, taz 'that' 97,18
h. geskah, taz 'that' 20,19
z. tez, taz 'that' 61,20a
t. reht, taz 'that' 42,18
t. skinet, taz 'that' 108,18
t. reht, taz 'that' 48,14
t. stuont, taz 'that' 29,4
t. bezeichnenet, taz 'that' 28,20
s. uuas, ten 'the' 94,9a
t. gestat, ten 'the' 94,9a
t. ist, ten 'the' 154,11
z. ungelichiz, ten 'the' 79,18a
z. reiz, ten 'the' 110,21
t. geeichot, ter 'the' 13,6a
t. sat, ter 'the' 72,15a
t. ast, ter 'the' 39,15a
t. uuanset, ter 'the' 103,10
h. ouh, ter 'the' 93,19a
t. ist, ter 'the' 53,1

t. heizet, ter 'the' 74,13
t. geeiscot, ter 'the' 63,2a
t. sihet, ter 'the' 70,10
z. saz, ter 'the' 157,17
t. neist, ter 'the' 170,12
t. huobet, ter 'the' 67,3
t. ist, ter 'the' 93,21
t. naht, ter 'the' 54,9
t. stal, ter 'the' 79,16
t. aiscot, ter 'the' 54,5
t. noizet, ter 'the' 66,16
t. maht, ter 'the' 68,5a
t. ist, ter 'the' 52,13
s. uuas, ter 'the' 139,8
t. sint, tero 'the' 69,20
t. ingurient, tero 'the' 104,12
t. bechennest, tero 'the' 109,8
t. sint, tero 'the' 126,13
s. ariadnes, tero 'the' 87,10
s. uers, tes 'the' 30,3
z. daz, tes 'the' 124,14
s. nahtes, tes 'the' 95,17a
t. chit, tes 'the' 95,17a
s. kuis, tes 'the' 107,6
t. chraft, tes 'the' 97,13
t. danchet, tes 'the' 83,5

t. kerist, teta 'did' 151.18
t. uuanet, tia 'the' 61.19a
s. todes. tia 'the' 131.9
t. fliegend. tia 'the' 135.7
z. hiez, tia 'the' 84.16
s. gehileiches. tia 'the' 49.1a
t. chit, tia 'the' 131.21
s. niuonnes, tie 'the' 92.9
h. dih. tie 'tie' 134.15
t. folget. tie 'the' 95.18
c. scoz, tie 'the' 146.9
t. gesihest. tie 'the' 138.15
t. sagent, tie 'the' 130.20
t. vobent, tie 'the' 100.10
t. sint, tie 'the' 162.20
h. nah. tie 'the' 54.15
t. gant, tie 'the' 19.19
h. zeichengelih. tie 'the' 74.20
t. sizzent, tie 'the' 105.5
t. heizet. tie 'the' 53.3
t. tuot. tien 'the' 78.2
t. gehiest, tih 'you' 108.10
t. ist, tirro 'this' 75.17a
t. chit, tiu 'the' 97.13
t. chraft, tiu 'the' 129.9
h. buch, tiu 'the' 127.13a
t. uuirt, tiu 'the' 96.5

t. munt. tiu 'the' 122.2
s. uuas. tiu 'the' 100,11
e. uuas. tiu 'the' 120,16a
t. ist. tiu 'the' 41,11
t. chint. tiu 'the' 74.8
h. sih. tiu 'the' 63.21a
t. scafot. tiu 'the' 5.6
a. sint. tiu 'the' 169.20
t. heizet. tiu 'the' 38.14
h. buoh. tiu 'the' 170.10
s. eis. tiu 'the' 128.16
t. gezelet. tiu 'the' 128.12
t. heizet. tiu 'the' 68.14
t. nebechennist. tiu 'the' 64.11a
t. kat. toh 'nevertheless' 45,18
t. stant. tri 'three' 86,13a
s. unistuomes. tu 'you' 117.4
t. salhont. tu 'you' 134,11
t. ketrenchet. tu 'you' 108,14
t. chit. tu 'you' 3.20
t. stat. turh 'through' 69,5

After .##

After Latin Word:

o. redimito. tannan 'than' 30,7
i. dispari. tara 'there' 36,6
i. augusti. taz 'that' 2,18

e. cedere. taz 'that' 16,20
e. uolueret. taz 'that' 31,13
a. futura. taz 'that' 42,2
i. compacti. temo 67,13
a. septima. ter 'the' 53,4
o. romulo. ter 'the' 54,19
a. sidera. tero 'the' 32,6
e. ammixtione. tero 'the' 24,15
e. uirgine. tia 'the' 38,7
e. dulciore. tie 'the' 38,7
e. cere. tie 'the' 43,12
e. contulisse. tie 'the' 67,18
e. dactissime. tin 'your' 42,14a
i. admitti. tisen 'this' 61,5a
a. natura. tiu 'the' 60,2
i. osculari. tiu 'the' 62,20
a. regna. tiu 'the' 32,12a
i. mundi. tiu 'the' 60,13
e. formate. tiu 'the' 60,13
o. depositio. to 'then' 5,9
e. intactunque. to 'then' 5,9
e. residere. to 'then' 79,9
a. congruentia. to 'then' 89,20
e. personare. to 'then' to 17,3
u. obtutu. toh 'nevertheless' 138,16
e. monere. tu 'you' 35,16

e. postulare. tu 'you' 48.5
e. labore. turh 'through' 32,15a
m. quadratum. tar 'there' 68.10
r. uidebantur. tar 'there' 19.9
r. ligiabatur. taz 'that' 69.9
r. dicebatur. taz 'that' 28,11
m. exitium. taz 'that' 28.21
m. electrum. taz 'that' 23.16
m. prunarum. taz 'that' 28.19
m. solitum. taz 'that' 42.10a

m. scribatem. ter 'the' 38.21
r. uocabatur. ter 'the' 66.12
r. conuocantur. ter 'the' 54.6a
m. ciliorum. tero 'the' 122.1
m. arbitrium. tero 'the' 32,8
r. gradiebatur. tero 'the' 73.16
m. sum. tia 'the' 2.17
m. principatum. tie 'the' 76.5
m. ennianum. tie 'the' 51,2a
m. numerum. tih 'you' 42,6a
m. deorum. tin 'your' 41.20a
r. uidebatur. tiser 'this' 166,10
r. adhibetur. tiu 'the' 53.12
r. temperabatur. tiu 'the' 23,7

m. datum. tiu 'the' 32.18a
m. centesimam. tiu 'the' 73.9
m. siderum. to 'then' 79.11
r. probarentur. to 'then' 169.6
r. ascenditur. to 'then' 39.14
r. numerantur. to 'then' 50.22a
r. adiretur. to 'then' 16.6
r. crederetur. toh 'nevertheless' 71.1a
r. ferebatur. taz 'that' 132.5a
t. monstravit. tages 'day' 139.7a
t. conscenderat. tannan 'than' 147.14
t. permittat. tannan 'than' 27.1
t. quiverunt. tanne 'than' 78.7
t. petuot. tanne 'than' 160.13
c. hic. tanne 'than' 160.13
c. hic. tanne 'than' 56.2a
t. erant. tanne 'than' 160.3a
t. dissinabat. tar 'there' 167.8
t. habebat. tar 'there' 52.2
s. defluebant. tar 'there' 124.19
s. domus. tar 'there' 164.13
s. aspicias. tar 'there' 108.6
s. iunonis. tar 'there' 58.12
t. manauerunt. tar 'there' 141.16a
t. est. tar 'there' 136.3a
s. incolis. tar 'there' 149.8
s. nuptiis. tar 'there' 133.4

s. urietas. tar 'there' 58,5
t. gignit. tara 'there' 93.13
t. pertraherbat. tara 'there' 22.15
t. prenitebat. tara 'there' 103.12
t. sumit. tara 'there' 145.12
t. reddit. tara 'there' 98.7
s. uitreas. tara 'there' 56.18
t. fecit. tara 'there' 96.19
t. ispirat. tara 'there' 45.6
t. faciunt. tara 'there' 84.21
t. quatiebat. taz 'that' 20.6
s. uenustatis. taz 'that' 100.13
s. philogeus. taz 'that' 39.20
s. heroes. taz 'that' 141.15
s. iouis. taz 'that' 28.16
t. memorabant. taz 'that' 29,5
t. concinebat. taz 'that' 99.2a
t. allubescat. taz 'that' 96.21
t. est. taz 'that' 4.19
s. serpentis. taz 'that' 149.13
t. renitebat. taz 'that' 28.14
s. ceteris. taz 'that' 131.18
s. honores. taz 'that' 122.3
t. defluebant. taz 'that' 164.3
s. mercurius. temo 'that' 37,14
s. uirus. temo 'the' 118,13

s. stellis. ten 'the' 63,6a
t. uocauerunt. ten 'the' 137,3a
s. gaudens. ten 'the' 118,17
s. sacramentis. ten 'the' 106,1
t. claudit. ter 'the' 90,21
s. comis. ter 'the' 73,19
s. acuminis. ter 'the' 100,8
s. louis. ter 'the' 158,11
s. uiribus. ter 'the' 89,6
s. hic. ter 'the' 43,9
s. piscibus. ter 'the' 56,13a
s. quesitas. ter 'the' 77,12
s. effigies. tero 'the' 125,8a
s. hic. tero 'the' 113,8
t. machont. tero 'the' 74,16
t. fuit. tero 'the' 123,16a
t. personabat. tes 'the' 158,2
t. appetobat. eos 'the' 23,20
s. pecudibus. tia 'the' 151,9
t. pecudibus. tia 'the' 151,9
t. cocitarunt. tie 'the' 137,16
t. illuminabant. tie 'the' 56,20a
s. sideribus. tie 'the' 55,1a
s. puras. tie 'the' 138,17
s. polis. tie 'the' 42,12
s. omnibus. tie 'the' 136,12
t. transiliunt. tie 'the' 138,12

s. decaddibus. tie 'the' 92,8
s. uinclis. tie 'the' 33,16
s. conspicias. tie 'the' 137,20a
t. herbidabant. tie 'the' 67,16
t. componunt. tie 'the' 135,9a
s. thalamos. tih 'you' 4,15
s. auchanus. tin 'your' 36,1
s. necessitas. tin 'your' 442,1
s. moribus. tinen 'your' 42,1
s. poetis. tir 'your' 109,4
s. homines. tise 'this' 144,13
t. est. tisen 'this' 158,18
s. intuens. tiser 'this' 167,6
t. replicabat. tiser 'this' 166,17
t. custodit. tiser 'this' 137,10a
s. eraclitus. tiser 'this' 166,10
t. consistit. tisiv 'this' 141,19
t. hesitabat. tiu 'the' 22,12
t. laborarit. tiu 'the' 34,10
t. hartet. tiu 'the' 68,16
s. mirabilis. tiu 'the' 58,11
t. rapiebant. tiu 'the' 26,4
t. memorabat. tiu 'the' 148,10a
t. existabat. tiu 'the' 149,21
t. ait. to 'then' 45,20
t. uenerunt. to 'then' 52,15

t. alternat. to 'then' 10.17
t. euomebat. to 'then' 124.13
t. tenebant. to 'then' 79.20
t. irrumpit. to 'then' 102.13
t. constiterunt. to 'then' 52.15
t. perfecit. to 'then' 50.13
t. corripuit. to 'then' 57.1
t. cepit. to 'then' 107.1a
t. deesset. to 'then' 169.19
t. ascenderet. to 'then' 37.9
t. conueniant. toh 'nevertheless' 18.22a
t. constiterunt. toh 'nevertheless' 27.9
t. perhibebant. toh 'nevertheless' 18.18
s. ceraunos. tri 'three' 64.9a
s. camenis. tu 'you' 109.8
s. inscensis. tu 'you' 111.7a
s. cetus. tu 'you' 157.7
s. aris. tu 'you' 116.4
s. socias. tu 'you' 4.3
s. importicibus. tu 'you' 115.21
s. patris. tu 'you' 153.19
x. nox tu 'you' 155.21a
s. conspiceres. tu 'you' 116.4a
s. bratteatas. tu 'you' 10.13
s. raptibus. tu 'you' 107.7a
c. hic. tu 'you' 112.15
s. uocis. tanne 'than' 2.14

After German Word:

- e. neuuare. taz 'that' 59.17a
- o. kelegetemo. taz 'that' 79.15
- a. uuorhta. taz 'that' 56.16a
- e. site. taz 'that' 79.19a
- a. erscutta. taz 'that' 33.21
- e. sueifte. taz 'that' 24.14
- e. kebogene. temo 'the' 70.4
- o. erdo. ten 'the' 59.7a
- o. sus. tes 'the' 82.3a
- o. ahto. tia 'the' 155.5
- a. muotrauuu. tih 'you' 32.1
- e. ferte. tiu 'the' 22.15
- n. christin. taz 'that' 27.4
- n. ernazen. taz 'that' 59.8a
- n. pergenten. taz 'that' 63.9
- n. brahtin. taz 'that' 89.8a
- n. ketan. taz 'that' 50.5
- n. scricchen. taz 'that' 24.6
- n. machonten. ter 'the' 86.9
- l. spel. ter 'the' 66.15a
- r. glater. tri 'three'
- t. machont. tero 'the' 74.16
- g. urspring. taz 'that' 154.3
- g. uuideruuartig. taz 'that' 77.10
- d. uuard. tes 'the' 87.9a

g. nemag. tie 'the' 112.19
t. houbet. tannan 157.22
s. himeles. taz 'that' 154.9
t. sint. taz 'that' 154.9
t. machot. taz 'that' 98.14
t. keouget. taz 'that' 61.20
t. fierstunt. taz 'that' 91.15
t. peheftet. taz 'that' 104.16
t. ist. taz 'that' 9.21
t. eigant. taz 'that' 85.2
s. yotes. taz 'that' 50.13
s. uuis. ten 'the' 146.8
t. ist. ter 'the' 66.2
t. naht. ter 'the' 74.12a
t. keheizent. ter 'the' 50.17
t. machot. ter 'the' 93.15
t. geskihet. tero 'the' 95.20
t. uuirdet. tes 'the' 131.11
s. souues. tes 'the' 25.5
s. uers. tes 'the' 30.3
s. uuindes. tes 'the' 20.3
t. ist. tia 'the' 129.4
t. gotheit. tie 'the' 139.3
t. heizent. tie 'the' 141.13
t. ratet. tih 'you' 141.13
s. potes. tir 'you' 42.3a
t. bist. tu 'you' 48.2

One entry does not fit into any category.

alfa I. tere 'the' 92.17

<d> from /t/

After ##

After Latin Word:

0

After German Word:

t ist danne 'then' 57.22

n unsih daz 'that' 2.19a

t sint daz 'that' 6.18

s himelis daz 'that' 54.12

z daz daz 'that' 83.17

t uerdent die 'the' 23.13

t geondost dien 'the' 117.7

After .##

0

After .##

0

<d> from /d/

After .##

After Latin Word:

e. nature. danne 'than' 137.21

o. mercurio. danne 'than' 147.15

e. ratione. danne 'than' 89.6

a. rarta, daz 'that' 127,21
e. minerue, daz 'that' 11,5a
e. fistule, daz 'that' 109,5a
e. nume, daz 'that' 54,18
a. diadema, daz 'that' 12,7
a. fama, daz 'that' 18,18
o. cyllenio, daz 'that' 49,21
e. fabule, daz 'that' 76,19
o. iuno, daz 'that' 54,5
e. anime, daz 'that' 12,12
a. facundia, daz 'that' 148,11
e. fabulose, daz 'that' 88,17a
e. anime, daz 'that' 12,19
i. saturni, daz 'that' 99,22a
o. iuno, daz 'that' 84,21a
e. curie, daz 'that' 84,10
a. astronomia, daz 'that' 127,2
a. libra, daz 'that' 69,1
i. egypti, daz 'that' 156,18
i. pegasi, daz 'that' 108,20
o. cupido, demo 'the' 79,18
e. rege, den 'the' 140,60
i. chi, den 'the' 91,19
i. chi, der 'the' 90,19
o. insinuatio, der 'the' 32,2
e. phitagoe, der 'the' 95,7a

o, mercurio, der 'the' 151.10
i, serpentarii, der 'the' 69.4a
a, capra, dero 'the' 144.12
a, causa, dia 'the' 60.70
a, pagina, dia 'the' 78.13
i, mundi, dia 'the' 129.8
i, nouemarii, die 'the' 74.6
i, egipani, die 'the' 144.11
a, furna, die 'the' 142.22
i, stoci, die 'the' 116.2
e, lune, die 'the' 65.20a
i, mercurii, die 'the' 21.4a
a, urania, dien 'the' 107.1a
a, memoria, diu 'the' 38.17
i, mundi, diu 'the' 166.21a
o, iuno, diu 'the' 144.20
e, blanche, diu 'the' 151.4
a, uesta, diu 'the' 62.16
a, corona, diu 'the' 87.7
a, gemma, diu 'the' 68.13a
a, luna, diu 'the' 142.1
a, musica, diu 'the' 98.14
a, filia, div 'the' 141.4
e, ioue, do 'then' 90.13a
a, maia, do 'than' 9.19a
e, dignitate, doh 'nevertheless' 2.8
a, satira, du 'you' 3.9

a. philogia, du 'you' 112,8
a. elementa, duingest 'coerce' 3,17
m. musarum, dah 'roof' 167,14
m. caducem, daz 'that' 16,33
m. inlactum, dar 'there' 164,11
m. ferrum, daz 'that' 38,11a
n. diapason, daz 'that' 96,8
m. stigem, daz 'that' 73,1
m. sophiam, daz 'that' 19,22
n. auton, daz 'that' 116,19
m. emoliam, daz 'that' 96,3a
m. sectam, daz 'that' 167,10
m. typhonem, daz 'that' 156,11
m. inaequalem, daz 'that' 163,22
m. deificationem, daz 'that' 147,6a
m. ceruam, daz 'that' 147,6a
m. electrum, daz 'that' 23,17
m. ingenium, daz 'that' 13,18
m. animatum, daz 'that' 129,7
m. planetarum, den 'the' 57,6a
m. himeneum, den 'the' 100,2
r. abbadir, den 'the' 100,2
m. cynosuram, den 'the' 85,22
r. fabor, der 'the' 53,20a
m. numerum, der 'the' 91,8a
m. denarium, der 'the' 94,17
m. montem, der 'the' 19,4

m. argionam, dero 'the' 9,2a
m. concentum, die 'the' 21,5
n. generen, die 'the' 112,14
m. syllogismum, die 'the' 113,6
m. perfectum, diu 'the' 98,3
m. consonatiam, diu 'the' 95,22a
m. uestam, diu 'the' 163,14
m. deam, diu 'the' 147,10a
m. speram, diu 'the' 38,15
m. decimam, diu 'the' 147,10a
m. secundam, diu 'the' 147,11
s. brosis, dannan 'than' 105,1
s. perhiodus, daz 'that' 5,12
s. 'icuis, daz 'that' 19,2a
s. campis, daz 'that' 19,2a
s. sesquiterius, daz 'that' 95,17a
t. est, daz 'that' 97,13
s. denarius, der 'the' 115,6
s. pliadibus, dero 'the' 9,21

After German Word:

a. sougta, dah 'roof' 118,18
e. uuachende, dahta 'thought' 88,1
a. nahta, dannan 'than' 164,7
a. lera, dannan 'than' 116,17
a. cota, dannan 'than' 31,10
i. si, danne 'than' 86,17

e. gehiende, danne 'than' 45.14a
e. sange, danne 'than' 98.17a
e. hefenonde, danne 'than' 120.10
e. uuile, danne 'than' 31.16a
e. forziche, dar 'there' 55.11a
e. zehimele, dar 'there' 159.21
i. hohi, dar 'there' 55.11a
o. dieto, dar 'there' 55.11a
e. burgliute, dar 'there' 2.12
e. uuerite, dar 'there' 162.15
e. stete, dar 'there' 109.19
a. erda, dar 'there' 143.18
a. chificha, dar 'there' 144.10
e. cestanne, dar 'there' 55.12
e. uuelle, dar 'there' 116.10
e. gominne, dar 'there' 45.13a
a. kedageta, dara 'there' 43.2a
u. habentiu, dara 'there' 127.20a
e. gelerte, dara 'there' 43.9a
e. gechose, dara 'there' 112.18
e. glihnisse, daz 'that' daz 131.5a
e. fouue, daz 'that' 100.19
o. iro, daz 'that' 21.10
a. eruuereta, daz 'that' 75.5
e. bridele, daz 'that' 85.14
o. vuercho, daz 'that' 160.20
e. echate, daz 'that' 73.11

e. gesaze. daz 'that' 73.11
o. farendo. daz 'that' 83.3a
o. pluomondo. daz 'that' 88.18
a. mettoda. daz 'that' 122.14
o. uuibello. daz 'that' 44.10
i. unsemfti. daz 'that' 131.21
i. snelli. daz 'that' 90.1
e. biege. daz 'that' 110.21
e. uware. daz 'that' 75.12
e. zeskepffenne. daz 'that' 17.19
o. redo. daz 'that' 94.15
e. chliuue. daz 'that' 57.2
i. uuandi. daz 'that' 62.5
a. sia. daz 'that' 91.3
e. legende. daz 'that' 56.11a
e. geile. daz 'that' 36.14
e. uuizenne. daz 'that' 87.13
a. ana. daz 'that' 91.5
e. umbe. daz 'that' 81.11
e. sune. daz 'that' 42.11
a. uuilligora. daz 'that' 44.2
e. eile. daz 'that' 129.4
i. duohti. daz 'that' 71.2
e. sloze. daz 'that' 90.21a
u. kuollichiu. daz 'that' 121.7
o. erdo. daz 'that' 138.10a

a. ana, daz 'that' 4.22
e. zegesehenne, daz 'that' 135,10
e. chome, daz 'that' 97,19
e. tuoche, daz 'that' 56,15
o. kebendo, daz 'that' 31.3
e. heize, daz 'that' 97,22a
e. gediene, daz 'that' 97,22a
a. ringa, daz 'that' 97.22a
o. iro, daz 'that' 104.8
e. andere, daz 'that' 168.20
e. flege, daz 'that' 148.22
o. uuillo, daz 'that' 42.1a
u. glizentiu 'that' 149.19
e. zeliche, daz 'that' 102,21
e. miliche, daz 'that' 102.22
i. si, daz 'that' 35.22
e. buhaite, daz 'that' 61.4
e. kezame, daz 'that' 83.12
a. nahta, daz 'that' 20.9
e. uware, daz 'that' 16,7
a. uolta, daaz 'that' 132,12
o. redo, daz 'that' 83.21a
i. si, daz 'that' 102.10
e. kebietende, daz 'that' 102.10
e. umbe, daz 'that' 49.5
a. keotalta, daz 'that' 13.11a
a. forhta, daz 'that' 89,13

e. ferte, daz 'that' 23.3
i. si, daz 'that' 88,9
i. si, daz 'that' 49.5a
o. fro. daz 'that' 33.19a
a. erista, daz 'that' 122.3a
u. anderiu, daz 'that' 122,5
a. dritta, daz 'that' 122,6
o. harto, daz 'that' 9.6
i. habeti, daz 'that' 34.16a
e. zegetroctenne, daz 'that' 130.3
u. diu, daz 'that' 137.17
e. zeichene, daz 'that' 138,21a
e. zechedenne, daz 'that' 105.6
e. sihte, daz 'that' 86,15
u. diu, daz 'that' 24.7
e. ende, daz 'that' 54.10
i. si, daz 'that' 64,8
i. si, daz 'that' 60,17a
o. iro, daz 'that' 96,3
i. eimberi, daz 'that' 128,19a
e. zeuuizenne, daz 'that' 133,4a
i. si, daz 'that' 4,19a
o. goto, daz 'that' 156,22
u. diu, daz 'that' 156,4
e. zetrinchenne, daz 'that' 128,4
e. muote, daz 'that' 41.22

e. liste, daz 'that' 127.2
o. scundetemo, daz 'that' 111.17
e. gesihte. demo 'the' 43.10
i. si. den 'the' 90.18a
e. steine. den 'the' 100.1a
a. gelubeda. den 'the' 49.22
e. stuole, den 'the' 162.1
i. si. den 'the' 8.13a
u. intlazenu, den 'the' 33.20
e. houbete. den 'the' 74.18
o. spero. den 'the' 57.7
e. arbeite. den 'the' 110.7
a. aba. den 'the' 104.4
o. gestelledo, den 'the' 164.19
e. albisze. den 'the' 37.10
o. spuetigo. denchennes 'thinking' 114.22
o. leuvo. der 'the' 153.7
a. frucnda. der 'the' 89.5
e. flehota, der 'the' 43.6
o. bluomo, der 'the' 156.12
e. bineze. der 'the' 159.1a
e. gemantelote. der 'the' 167.9
a. drata, der 'the' 86.8
o. selbo, der 'the' 132.1
e. tuonne, dero 'the' 8.8a
u. chomentiu, derro 'the' 78.18
o. arbeit, dero 'the' 160.20

o. sterno. dero 'the' 158,4
a. geuualta. dero 'the' 135.16
i. sconi. dero 'the' 103.13
a. festina. dero 'the' 138.6a
o. goto. dero 'the' 100.16
a. snora. dero 'the' 117.16a
e. inferte. des 'the' 113.20
e. unne. des 'the' 35.19
o. lentero. des 'the' 134.4
i. si. des 'the' 32.11a
e. vuurfe. des 'the' 32.11a
o. meino. des 'the' 130.12
e. habente. des 'the' 163.4
o. gerto. dia 'the' 40.18
a. habeta. dia 'the' 121.12
a. sidella. dia 'the' 79.12
a. reita. dia 'the' 155.19a
o. tugedo. die 'the' 104.17
e. gebenne. die 'the' 169.13
a. liutcota. die 'the' 54,7
e. michele. die 'the' 69.1a
a. geuualta. die 'the' 163,6
i. si. die 'the' 162.18a
i. tri. die 'the' 74,16
e. michele. die 'the' 69.3
a. erdkota. die 'the' 141.12

e. chlebente, die 'the' 65.21
o. boumo, die 'the' 113,8
e. legende, die 'the' 113,8
a. uuissa, die 'the' 164,11
e. ubele, die 'the' 142.15
e. ringe, die 'the' 135,21
o. statelicho, die 'the' 50,14
o. geskefto, die 'the' 127,1
a. falanza, die 'the' 85.1
e. liste, die 'the' 119.6
a. reda, die 'the' 112.17
a. uuitta, die 'the' 17,13
e. mite, die 'the' 84.8
o. nahentero, die 'the' 165.11
e. dringende, die 'the' 105,14
e. kerachte, die 'the' 20,7
a. sela, die 'the' 143.13
e. zechiesenne, die 'the' 111,1a
a. bedigeda, die 'the' 81,6
a. sela, die 'the' 166,2
a. geba, die 'the' 5.3
e. sange, die 'the' 112,2
a. zartota, dien 'the' 78.5
e. hirte, dien 'the' 53,21
e. machoe, dien 'the' 114.21
e. gehileiche, din 'your' 106,20
e. uuaare, dina 'your' 112,9

e. lone, dinero 'you' 110,6a
i. guoti, dionestes 'of service' 82,8
o. listo, dir 'you' 114,5a
a. geantuuvrta, diu 'the' 168,7
a. reia, diu 'the' 150,6
o. singentemo, diu 'the' 6,11a
o. fareuuo, diu 'the' 128,18
u. uuidermaza, diu 'the' 98,11
u. gaareuuu, diu 'the' 148,1
o. gutenno, diu 'the' 146,14
u. unforegeuuizeniu, diu 'the' 79,2
a. habeta, diu 'the' 79,2a
u. farendiu, diu 'the' 22,19
e. stete, diu 'the' 47,15
e. irmarte, diu 'the' 80,16
i. sinnigi, diu 'the' 84,1a
o. tiehsemo, diu 'the' 73,6a
o. farendo, diu 'the' 89,14
a. minna, diu 'the' 81,9
a. hebeta, diu 'the' 90,7a
o. erdo, diu 'the' 146,19
o. dingo, diu 'the' 88,19
a. missefareuua, diu 'the' 59,15a
u. tiu, diu 'the' 140,16a
a. herlicha, diu 'the' 84,15
i. manigi, diu 'the' 148,6

i. mageri. diu 'the' 99,18
o. helfo. diu 'the' 128,1a
o. meino. diu 'the' 127,14
u. briteliu. diu 'the' 126.12
a. teta. diu 'the' 22.13a
a. ana. diu 'the' 22.13
a. teta. do 'than' 133.14
a. teta. do 'than' 139.4
a. ana. do 'than' 139.4
e. fucre. do 'than' 27.2
i. gerista. do 'than' 15.18a
e. seuue. do 'than' 39,9
e. zesamine. do 'than' 96,20
e. loufe. doh 'nevertheless' 36,13
e. uuare. doh 'nevertheless' 133.19a
u. befangeni. doh 'nevertheless' 62.9a
i. chiuski. doh 'nevertheless' 76.6
o. iro. doh 'nevertheless' 14,19
i. si. doh 'nevertheless' 5.20
i. zuei. driu 'three' 144,7
e. fluoge. du 'you' 156,15
e. uuare. du 'you' 113,19a
a. saliga. du 'you' 117,10a
a. dierna. du 'you' 116.15a
e. uuolge. du 'you' 4.9
n. mennisken. dannan 'than' 144,14
n. facchelon. dannan 'than' 85,19

n. sin. danne 'than' 58,15a
n. uuunnon, danne 'than' 7.18
n. sulin, danne 'than' 105,7
r. mer, danne 'than' 159,18
n. ingemeiun, dar 'there' 17,19
n. chilechon, dar 'there' 17,4
n. gefilden, dar 'there' 19,3
n. gesazen, dar 'there' 38,12
n. gegeven, dar 'there' 113,1
n. chomen, dar 'there' 145,15
n. zeuwinsterun, daz 'that' 92,1
n. mageden, daz 'that' 11,2
n. gegraben, daz 'that' 103,18a
l. luzzel, daz 'that' 44,15a
n. inblahenen, daz 'that' 124,9
r. mer, daz 'that' 157,13
n. reiton, daz 'that' 83,3
n. zuien, daz 'that' 100,4
n. singenten, daz 'that' 3,10
n. organisten, daz 'that' 109,15
n. uuillen, daz 'that' 34,19
n. geskehen, daz 'that' 114,11
n. hugen, daz 'that' 11,10
n. gescriben, daz 'that' 91,8
n. tannan, daz 'that' 47,2
n. beginnen, daz 'that' 97,21

n. in. daz 'that' 41.14
n. uuorten, daz 'that' 78,18
n. pliin, daz 'that' 78,18
n. samen, daz 'that' 3,16
l. al. daz 'that' 111,4a
m. nim, daz 'that' 128.3
n. skimon, daz 'that' 65.7a
n. sternon.daz 'that' 87.4
n. skein. daz 'that' 12.3
n. kehalten, daz 'that' 83.9
n. gefiengen. daz 'that' 122.10
n. dienoen. daz 'that' 149.3
n. roson. daz 'that' 75,19
n. uuandon. daz 'that' 79.4
n. uuerden. daz 'that' 60.22
n. uuerden,daz 'that' 60.22
n. tiernun. daz 'that' 163,7
n. kelegen. daz 'that' 82,21a
n. trosten, daz 'that' 9,9
n. tualon, daz 'that' 47,3
n. cheden. daz 'that' 131.17
n. lichamen, daz 'that' 138.2
n. betaren. daz 'that' 73,10
n. nemahtin. daz 'that' 89,2
r. dir, daz 'that' 115,9a
n. zuein. daz 'that' 50,5a
n. uuandon, daz 'that' 128.14

n. zasamen. daz 'that' 115.1
n. keboten. daz 'that' 51,1
n. blicchen. daz 'that' 77.2a
n. silberin. daz 'that' 28,2
n. ladon. daz 'that' 134.10
n. gelazen. daz 'that' 155.1a
n. keboten. daz 'that' 123.21
n. varton. daz 'that' 116.11
n. uuerden. den 'the' 118.10
r. ter. den 3,9
r. uuertener. den 'the' 44,7
n. namen. den 'the' 90.7
l. spiegel. den 'the' 13.10
n. prunnen. den 'the' 109.1a
n. chamin. den 'the' 22,7
n. sternon. der 'the' 70.9
a. aternen. der 'the' 74,14
n. scozen. der 'the' 86.3
r. er. der 'the' 114.14
l. fogal. der 'the' 149,9
n. dracchen. der 'the' 61,18
n. namen. der 'the' 150,13
n. faren. der 'the' 38,3
n. namen. der 'the' 90,13
n. engeron. der 'the' 107.5
n. sun. der 'the' 133,8a

n. skeiden, dero 'the' 163,21a
n. kemeinskezzen, dero 'the' 51,1a
n. pringen, des 'the' 31,14
n. slidenten, des 'the' 61,19
n. uuellen, des 'the' 31,14
n. kesuasenten, dia 'the' 40,18
n. gemisten, dia 'the' 23,10
n. s... .. 49,20
n. 57,8
n. sternon, die 'the' 66,19
n. uuellen, die 'the' 116,11
r. bruoder, die 'the' 169,12
n. ersahen, die 'the' 123,14a
n. anderen, die 'the' 84,6
n. uarren, die 'the' 166,3
n. pildungon, die 'the' 126,22
n. sin, die 'the' 108,16a
n. sternon, die 'the' 65,2a
n. strimon, die 'the' 67,22
n. herosten, die 'the' 50,14a
n. diernun, die 'the' 126,2
n. gorpoton, die 'the' 141,17
n. spraten, die 'the' 166,4
n. bluomon, die 'the' 5,1
n. uobton, die 'the' 89,1
n. eruualion, die 'the' 16,14
n. faren, die 'the' 38,11

n. sternon, die 'the' 68,7
n. haben, die 'the' 67,19
n. inchunnen, diu 'the' 101,12
n. funden, diu 'the' 26,19
r. muoter, diu 'the' 128,10
n. ougon, diu 'the' 65,11
n. beneimden, diu 'the' 29,9
n. sin, diu 'the' 87,49
n. uuilosaldon, diu 'the' 23,20a
n. gegeben, diu 'the' 129,2
n. hien, diu 'the' 132,9a
n. ran, diu 'the' 23,15
n. furkun, diu 'the' 57,17
r. uuazer, diu 'the' 27,10
n. pegriffen, diu 'the' 60,6
n. ran, diu 'the' 23,8
n. dien, diu 'the' 47,5a
r. er, do 'than' 167,4
n. uuaren, do 'than' 125,15
n. meren, doh 'nevertheless' 113,10
n. iltin, doh 'nevertheless' 30,20
n. uuaren, doh 'nevertheless' 74,21
n. gerertedon, doh 'nevertheless' 20,17
n. uuunnon, doh 'nevertheless' 89,6a
n. uuerden, doh 'nevertheless' 83,1
n. magedcurtelun, du 'you' 134,12a

n, uuillen, du 'you' 36,1a
n, gegeben, durh 'through' 70,4a
d, chad, daz 'that' 39,19
d, uuard, diu 'the' 53,20
h, unsih, daz 'that' 2,19a
t, machont, daz 'that' 85,26
s, undanches, daz 'that' 33,2
s, liehtes, daz 'that' 39,19
z, hiez, daz 'that' 101,12
s, uuas. der 'the' 39,16
s, dienestes, den 'the' 49,22a
t, ist, dia 'the' 49,13a
s, himeles, dia 'the' 113,22
t, ist, diu 'the' 87,8
t, ist, diu 'the' 64,19
t, uuesteruuat, diu 'the' 83,9
s, rangleiches, do 'than' 88,14a
t, ist, doh 'nevertheless' 94,14
t, gebot, doh 'nevertheless' 94,14
h, gelih, durh 'through' 58,14a

The following do not fit into any category:

S, daz 'that' 42,9a

Y, der 'the' 91,20

A, der 'the' 150,13

A, der 'the' 109,18

After .##

After Latin Word:

o. inmedio. dannan 'than' 98,19
o. concludendo. dannan 'than' 113,3
i. presulati. dar 'there' 123,10
o. theatro. dar 'there' 111,10a
a. inthesalia. dar 'there' 108,15
o. circumductio. dar 'there' 12
o. plenitudo. dar 'there' 152,12
i. mundi. dar 'there' 153,12
a. niliaca. dar 'there' 146,5
i. saturni. dara 'there' 99,20
o. cyllenio. dara 'there' 88,9
a. uigilia. daz 'that' 132,9
a. tua. daz 'that' 115,15
e. latine. daz 'that' 68,13
e. trigene. daz 'that' 124,1
a. etruria. daz 'that' 130,19
e. micatore. daz 'that' 4,11
a. contentiosa. daz 'that' 148,1
a. ardua. daz 'that' 33,3a
e. pernoxque. daz 'that' 115,18
e. domine. demo 'the' 147,18
a. semina. der 'the' 111,9a
o. assumendo. der 'the' 113,2a
o. denario. der 'the' 94,20
a. dialectica. der 'the' 113,16
i. celebrati. dero 'the' 141,6

i. uocitari. dero 'the' 120,4
a. una. dero 'the' 65.14a
a. uaticinata. dero 'the' 141.1
e. subuexere. des 'the' 145.9
i. demorati. die 'the' 54,2a
a. urania. die 'the' 38,14
i. sui. die 'the' 138,21
a. eloquentia. die 'the' 88.22
i. collocari. die 'the' 125.12
i. iungi. dih 'the' 117.10
a. predicanda. diu 'the' 120,12
o. animo. diu 'the' 122.5a
e. prouenire. diu 'the' 8,2
e. proportione. diu 'the' 145.16a
a. illa. do 'then' 128,2
a. propria. do 'then' 130.15
e. meruisse. do 'then' 163.21
e. lune. do 'then' 100.18
e. sere. do 'then' 169.11
o. depositio. doh 'nevertheless' 76.21
i. aratri. du 'you' 156.15
e. lybie. du 'you' 156.15a
o. depositio. du 'you' 113,19
a. carmina. du 'you' 110,10
a. prouecta. du 'you' 150,21
r. euehuntur. dannan 'than' 156,16
r. nominatur. dar 'there' 142,1

r. adoratur. dara 'there' 91.5
m. speciem. dara 'there' 127.8
m. literarum. dara 'there' 124.15a
m. geminorum. daz 'there' 65.11a
m. palestrem. daz 'that' 89.4
m. ipsum. daz 'that' 116.19a
m. succentum. daz 'that' 21.7
m. poeticum. daz 'that' 155.4
m. deorum. den 'the' 118.16
m. manium. der 'the' 141.21
m. etiam. der 'the' 52.2a
m. uenenum. des 'the' 118.19
m. circum. des 'the' 152.7
m. infirmitatem. dia 'the' 58.10
r. deferentur. die 'the' 120.19
r. memorantur. die 'the' 132.19
r. signatur. die 'the' 92.19
m. typhohem. dih 'you' 156.5
m. osyrim. dih 'you' 156.5
m. celitum. dine 'your' 109.11
r. habebatur. doh 'nevertheless' 159.10
n. omen. dri 'three' 157.3
m. cytharam. du 'you' 109.9
m. patrem. du 'you' 154.10
s. lotes. daz 'that' 5.12
t. refulgebat. der 'the' 749

s. osiris. der 'the' 118.11
t. pregrauaauerit. dia 'the' 14.18a
t. tulerit. die 'the' 108.13
t. gestiebat. do 'then' 77.6
t. cepit. do 'then' 79.21a

After German Word:

u. gesmizeniu. daz 'that' 128.17
u. freuentiu. daz 'that' 33.14
a. unda. daz 'that' 22.20
a. drata. daz 'that' 23.4
o. brutloufto. daz 'that' 49.15
e. snite. daz 'that' 118.13a
a. truueta. daz 'that' 39.10
e. irre. daz 'that' 113.15
e. getribe. daz 'that' 107.17
e. lezze. daz 'that' 156.18
e. uuazere. daz 'that' 139.15
e. nebeuuulle. der 'th' 104.11
a. hina. der 'the' 170.12
o. demo. der 'the' 109.19
e. boume. des 'the' 153.6
e. fone. des 'the' 151.1
o. burgo. die 'the' 142.9
e. gechrumpfte. die 'the' 66.4
e. chunde. din 'your' 116.6
o. gebotenemo. diu 'the' 96.9
a. erda. diu 'the' 161.10

e. stande. doh 'nevertheless' 33,4
e. chade. du 'you' 110,18
n. doriscun. daz 'that' 159,2
n. anasihtigun. daz 'that' 129,7
r. fiur. daz 'that' 114,17
n. eichenen. daz 'that' 114,17
n. orten. daz 'that' 110,17a
n. chellen. daz 'that' 116,2
n. selon. der 'the' 130,21a
r. geheizener. der 'the' 65,4
n. uuarbelon. der 'the' 65,1
m. vuurm. der 'the' 149,14
n. skimen. dero 'the' 86,22
n. chniuuen. dero 'the' 86,22
n. hornen. dero 'the' 65,21a
n. gehellen. die 'the' 21,3a
n. offen. die 'the' 65,22
n. bringen. die 'the' 169,13
n. sagon. diu 'the' 140,15
n. ahselon. dri 'three' 86,1a
r. dir. dri 'three' 154,18
n. ingangen. du 'you' 35,10
t. centstunt. dannan 'than' 91,13
t. heizet. der 'the' 68,3
t. nimet. der 'the' 13,4
s. libes. der 'the' 97,11

z. scaftontez. des 'the' 104,1

t. kenamot. die 'the' 105,1a

h. ouh. diu 'the' 77.9

One example does not fit in any category:

VIII. dannan 'than' 92,5a